

ON A CAGINALP STYLE MODEL

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ABSTRACT. These are the findings from my submitted thesis “Well-posedness of heterogeneous Caginalp models” as a preprint consisting essentially of the contents from the thesis and a supplemental sketch.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The physical system considered and its mathematical description. An important problem in metallurgy naturally is modelling how metals solidify when cooled down. This problem naturally leads to the question of generally modelling the interplay of heat conduction and phase change in metals.

A natural way to describe the problem mathematically is modelling the portion of metal considered as a bounded open set $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$, and defining a temperature field $u : \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a phase field $\varphi : \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, where (T_1, T_2) is the timespan over which the system is modelled, $u(x, t)$ is the temperature at position x and time t , and $\varphi(x, t)$ is the phase at position x and time t , where $\varphi(x, t) = -1$ means the material is completely solid, and $\varphi(x, t) = 1$ means the material is completely liquid at position x and time t , and $\varphi(x, t) \in (-1, 1)$ means the material is neither completely solid nor completely liquid, with values closer to -1 indicating a more solid-like state, and values closer to 1 indicating a more liquid-like state.

1.2. A first simple model - the Stefan problem. Now the simplest model for this problem, in terms of the required physical understanding of phase transitions on a microscopic scale, assuming a homogeneous material that has phase and temperature independent heat capacity and thermal conductivity, is the so called classical Stefan problem.

The core assumptions of the classical Stefan problem are essentially:

- (1) The enthalpy density field of the system has the form $E(u, \varphi) := cu + \frac{l}{2}\varphi + E_0$, where $c, l > 0, E_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ are some constants.
- (2) Enthalpy is transported throughout the material only via heat conduction with constant thermal conductivity, that is we have the enthalpy balance equation

$$E(u, \varphi)_t = k\Delta u$$

in a variational sense to be specified later, where $\Delta = \sum_{i=1}^3 \partial_{x_i}^2$ is the Laplacian in spatial coordinates only.

- (3) There are only pure liquid and solid, $Im(\varphi) \subseteq \{-1, 1\}$.
- (4) Liquid and solid phases only coexist at the melting point u_m .

Now the first two assumptions are essentially a straightforward formalisation of the assumption of a homogeneous material that has phase and temperature independent heat capacity and thermal conductivity.

The first assumption simply formalizes the assumption that our material has constant heat capacity per unit volume c , which we will call heat capacity from now on, independent of phase and temperature, and additionally captures the positive amount of enthalpy per unit volume l stored in the liquid phase $\varphi = 1$ compared to the solid phase $\varphi = -1$ in the $\frac{l}{2}\varphi$ -term.

The second assumption is essentially the Fourier heat law for a material with constant thermal conductivity k .

Furthermore, the third and fourth assumptions are quite reasonable approximations to the physical reality on a macroscopic scale:

The third assumption makes sense since one basically only has states between liquid and solid in a very thin interface layer at the surfaces between liquid and solid portions of the material.

The fourth assumption that liquid and solid phases only coexist at the melting point u_m is also a very reasonable approximation, at least for macroscopic systems.

This is essentially because in real-world scenarios, except in specialized experiments where tiny portions of metal are heated extremely quickly using lasers or similar techniques, the temperature doesn't change too quickly, and further the Gibbs Thomson effect, as is usually the case for macroscopic systems, is small.

Under these conditions, one expects that, if the temperature is significantly above the melting point at some position, it already was significantly above the melting point at that position for a significant amount of time, so that, assuming the melting point to be independent of the geometry of the liquid-solid interface, ignoring the Gibbs Thompson effect which we assumed to be small, any solid at this point will have melted already.

Analogously, one expects that under these conditions, if the temperature at a point is significantly below the melting point at some position, any liquid at that position has frozen already.

But then one basically has that one only expects liquid and to coexist when the temperature is neither significantly above nor significantly below the melting point, so that it is approximately at the melting point, so that the fourth assumption approximately holds.

Formalizing these assumptions and further making the standard assumption that the temperature field is continuous, one obtains the classical Stefan problem, that is one imposes that the temperature field $u : \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and the phase field $\varphi : \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ are a continuous and a measurable function with $Im(\varphi) \subseteq \{-1, 1\}$ such that:

- (1) $(cu + \frac{l}{2}\varphi)_t = K\Delta_x u$, with c, l, K some positive constants, in the weak sense that, for every compactly supported smooth test function ψ on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ one has $\int \langle \psi_t, u + \frac{l}{2}\varphi \rangle_{x,t} = \int \langle K\Delta_x \psi, u \rangle_{x,t}$ where the integrals are to be understood in the Lebesgue sense.
- (2) $u|_\Gamma = u_m$, where Γ is the jumpset $\Gamma := \{x \in \Omega : 0 < \int_{B_\epsilon(x)} \chi < \int_{B_\epsilon(x)} 1, \forall \epsilon > 0\}$, and u_m is the melting point.

Now while this model is very simple regarding the required understanding of phase transitions on a microscopic scale, it has the drawback that working with that very irregular phase function is mathematically difficult, especially when trying to numerically approximate solutions, because finite element methods mainly consider functions that are in Sobolevspaces, and such a φ doesn't even have one weak derivative that is a function, if it isn't -1 almost everywhere or 1 almost everywhere.

1.3. An alternative - the Caginalp system. An alternative model that works with a far more regular, especially continuous, phase functions, requiring u and φ instead of just u to be continuous, is the so-called Caginalp system.

Just like in the Stefan problem, the first equation of the Caginalp system reads:

$$(u + \frac{l}{2}\varphi)_t = K\Delta_x u$$

which we now require to hold in a strong sense, requiring the relevant partial derivatives of u and φ to exist and to be continuous.

Just like in the Stefan problem the first equation is an enthalpy balance equation assuming a Fourier heat law: The enthalpy density multiplied by the heat capacity is $u + \frac{l}{2}\varphi$, which is something like enthalpy density in heat units, so the equation basically just says that the rate of change of the enthalpy density in heat units is simply the rate of change $K\Delta u$ of the enthalpy density due to heat flux according to the Fourier law, in heat units, for K the thermal conductivity divided by the heat capacity per volume.

The second equation of the Caginalp system is the phenomenological Landau-Ginzburg model A equation describing phase transitions for a given temperature u :

$$\tau\varphi_t = \xi^2\Delta_x\varphi + W'(\varphi) + 2u$$

with $W'(\varphi) := \frac{1}{2}(\varphi - \varphi^3)$, and again required to hold in a strong sense, requiring the relevant partial derivatives of φ to exist and to be continuous.

Now while it is reasonable to use this phenomenological equation describing how phases evolve given a temperature field as second equation, this choice lacks a solid physical derivation, making the whole Caginalp model somewhat phenomenological.

However, it has been shown in [Caginalp2] that if one introduces a further parameter in front of the W' and scales the parameters in a certain way, the Caginalp system converges to some Stefan problems in a certain sense, including the classical Stefan problem and the Stefan problem with Gibbs Thomson law, a variant of the Stefan Problem that incorporates the Gibbs Thomson effect, suggesting it probably is a quite reasonable description of the physics after all, at least on a macroscopic scale, if one parametrizes it correctly.

Furthermore it has been shown that fine tuned versions of somewhat more general Caginalp systems do actually quantitatively reproduce experimental data on a microscopic scale [KarmaRappel], suggesting that more general Caginalp style systems are promising for modelling melting and solidification processes on a microscopic scale too.

1.4. Limitations of the original Caginalp system. The original Caginalp system we have seen is suitable for modeling homogeneous materials with phase and temperature independent thermal conductivity and heat capacity at a macroscopic scale.

However, almost all materials actually have phase and temperature dependent thermal conductivity, and many of the materials considered in metallurgy are inhomogeneous, at least on a microscopic scale, containing for example nucleation sites where a locally different material is present, which is already solid when the rest of the material is still molten, allowing for the surrounding melt to easier solidify at that point because spontaneous nucleation is not required since the metal can instead simply attach to the preexisting nucleation site, so the assumptions of the Caginalp system are quite unrealistic for real world materials.

Furthermore the systems which quantitatively reproduced experimental data on a microscopic scale were of a somewhat more general form than the Caginalp system too, suggesting that for accurate predictions on the microscopic scale, the Caginalp systems simple structure is simply too rigid.

So while the original Caginalp system is a good model to qualitatively understand phase transitions, it is apparent that for accurate modelling of real-world materials, especially on the microscopic scale, one needs more general Caginalp style models that especially model heterogeneous materials.

2. EXISTING WELL-POSEDNESS RESULTS FOR CAGINALP STYLE SYSTEMS

Since the Caginalp system is quite well-known there are many works showing well-posedness results for more general Caginalp style models, so before we consider the new well-posedness result derived in this work, we take a look at what kinds of systems well-posedness results have been shown for already, so we can then see how the new result extends the results in the literature.

Now in order to get a systematic overview of well posedness results for thermally coupled phasefield models sufficiently similar to the original nonconserved Caginalp model, we first need a system to categorize the different models. In order to do this, it is compelling to see them as special cases of some overly general root model that are valid under certain assumptions and approximations, as this allows for comparison of the different assumptions and approximations the models need.

Thus, we classify the surveyed works as follows:

- (1) We fix a very general root form for Caginalp style systems.
- (2) We list particularly notable formal simplifications of that root form, grouped by which term in the root form is changed.

- (3) We categorize the works by the phasefield model considered, with the models being viewed as subvariants of the root form, with some of the simplifications applied, plus eventually further case specific simplifications or changes applied that do not fit into the classification scheme.

Works studying models that differ too strongly from the original nonconserved Caginalp system are not considered.

Additionally to classifying the surveyed works, we will summarize the main results and the main techniques, so one also sees at a glance what results were obtained, and how they were obtained.

The different boundary conditions considered in the surveyed references will only be mentioned and not included in the classification, as while they are crucial for obtaining uniqueness and hence well posedness of solutions, they are less physically relevant, at least for anything but long term behaviour ($t \rightarrow \infty$), because the volume of interest can always be embedded within a much larger reservoir, mostly isolating it from the boundary conditions for arbitrarily large finite times, though not for $t \rightarrow \infty$.

2.1. The root form. Considering the different Caginalp style phasefield models in the literature, as well as the standard modelling of heat conduction in continuum mechanics, the following extremely general form is chosen as root form:

$$\partial_t E(u, \varphi, x) = (\nabla \cdot (k(u, \varphi, x) \nabla u))(x) + f(x, t)$$

$$\partial_t \varphi = (\nabla \cdot (k_\varphi(u, \varphi, x) \nabla u))(x) - W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x)$$

Where u, φ are the phase and temperature fields from before, and:

- $k(x, \varphi, u) := (x, t) \mapsto k(u(x, t), \varphi(x, t), x) \in (0, \infty)$ is the thermal conductivity at position x in the current state.
- $\partial_t E(x, \varphi(x), u(x)) := \partial_t ((x, t) \mapsto E(u(x, t), \varphi(x, t), x))$ with the ∂_t either denoting a classical or a weak or even just a distributional derivative, is the enthalpy change, in simpler models it will usually be assumed to have the form $\partial_t (\lambda_1 u(x) + \lambda_2 \varphi(x))$ (this will be called linear enthalpy assumption), so the first equation basically becomes a heat equation linearly coupled to $\partial_t \varphi$.
- $\nabla \cdot, \nabla$ are the spatial divergence $\vec{f} \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^3 \partial_{x_i} f_i$ and gradient column vector $f \mapsto (\partial_{x_1} f, \partial_{x_2} f, \partial_{x_3} f)^t$, either in a classical, or in a weak, or in case of $\nabla \cdot$ sometimes even just in a distributional sense.
- The phase is assumed to propagate according to a heat equation with “phase-conductivity” $k_\varphi(u, \varphi, x)$.
- $f(x, t)$ is the possibly time dependent heat supply term, in enthalpy units, due to effectively temperature-independent and phase-independent processes, like for example radioactive decay. It will be assumed to be bounded at least.
- W is the double-well potential, and W' is some sort of derivative of it, sometimes a multivalued subderivative, for example for potentials with “walls”.
- $g(u, \varphi, x)$ expresses the effect of the temperature on phase evolution.

The root form itself is probably far too general to obtain any interesting well posedness results about models of that form with reasonable effort. This is no issue, however, since the root form is only used as a central point of reference.

2.2. Notable simplifications of the root model. Under additional assumptions and approximations, the terms of the root model can of course be individually replaced by mathematically more tractable terms, simplifying the model. Such simplifications can then be used, as described in the section on the systematics, to classify the different phasefield models considered in the surveyed works. More concretely, the following noteworthy simplifications are considered, grouped by the term that is simplified:

Simplifications of the $\partial_t E(u, \varphi, x)$ -term:

- (1) Linear enthalpy assumption ($E(u, \varphi, x) \approx E_0 + \partial_t(\lambda_1 u + \lambda_2 \varphi)$): Working with arbitrary $\partial_t E(u, \varphi, x)$ obviously makes the equations very hard to work with from a mathematical standpoint. Motivated by the standard heat equation and the fact that one actually has a nice expression for $\partial_t \varphi$ by the second equation, one quickly realizes that if $E(u, \varphi, x) = E_0 + \partial_t(\lambda_1 u + \lambda_2 \varphi)$, the first equation basically becomes a heat equation linearly coupled to the right hand side of the second equation, which is much more manageable. For some substances, this assumption is plainly wrong, as effectively pointed out in [Wiki], using the example of water at $20^\circ C$ and ice just below $0^\circ C$, having specific heat capacities of about $4184 J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$ and $2093 J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$, respectively. However, for temperatures large enough, the heat capacity $\frac{dE}{dT} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial T}$ (heat capacities are usually only defined when there is no phase change, so $\frac{dE}{dT} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial T}$ for measured heat capacities) per unit mass of many metals in the solid state is approximately constant according to the Dulong-Petit law, and if the heat capacity per unit mass, the specific heat capacity, of a metal, is approximately the same in the liquid phase, and also approximately constant in the liquid phase, too, then $\frac{\partial E}{\partial T}$ might just be constant around the melting point, and the assumption that $E(x, \varphi(x), u(x))$ is linear might approximately hold if $\frac{\partial E}{\partial \varphi}$ is approximately constant as well. An example of such a metal is Aluminum, according to the models in [NIST1] and [NIST2], its specific heat capacity in the solid phase between $900K$ and $933K$ stays in the range from $0.32 J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$ to $0.33 J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$, varying less than 3%, and its specific heat capacity in the liquid phase is basically constant from $933.5K$ to over $2600K$, at about $0.3175 J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$, decreasing only about $0.012 J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$, or less than 4%, from about $0.3295 J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$ in the solid phase at $933K$.
- (2) Narrow temperature range approximation for the enthalpy ($\partial_t E(u, \varphi, x) \approx E_\varphi(\varphi, x) + (\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} c)(\varphi, x)(u - T_m) \partial_t \varphi + c(\varphi, x) \partial_t u$): Assuming the temperature only narrowly varies around the melting point T_m , one can approximate $E(u, \varphi, x) \approx E(T_m, \varphi, x) + (\frac{\partial}{\partial u} E)(T_m, \varphi, x)(u - T_m)$, defining $E_\varphi(\varphi, x) := E(T_m, \varphi, x)$, intuitively the enthalpy due to phase, and $c(\varphi, x) := (\frac{\partial}{\partial u} E)(T_m, \varphi, x)$, intuitively something like the specific heat capacity, dependent on phase, if one ignores that the specific heat capacity is usually not defined when the phase changes. One can then write $E(u, \varphi, x) \approx E_\varphi(\varphi, x) + c(\varphi, x)(u - T_m)$, and accordingly, try to approximate $\partial_t E(u, \varphi, x) \approx \partial_t(E_\varphi(\varphi, x) + c(\varphi, x)u) = \partial_t E_\varphi(\varphi, x) + (\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} c)(\varphi, x)(u - T_m) \partial_t \varphi + c(\varphi, x) \partial_t u$.
- (3) Constant heat capacity assumption ($\partial_t E(u, \varphi, x) \approx E_\varphi(u, \varphi) + c \partial_t u$): Going further than the narrow temperature range approximation for the enthalpy, one can assume that $(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} c)(\varphi, x) \approx 0$, so c is approximately constant, yielding $\partial_t E(u, \varphi, x) \approx E_\varphi(\varphi, x) + c \partial_t u$. This is basically a middle ground between the less restrictive narrow temperature range approximation for the enthalpy and the more restrictive linear enthalpy assumption.

Simplifications of the $g(u, \varphi, x)$ -term:

- (1) Narrow temperature range approximation for the coupling function g ($g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(\varphi, x)(u - T_m(\varphi, x))$): Assuming the temperature only narrowly varies around some average melting point T_m , one can approximate $g(u, \varphi, x) \approx g(T_m, \varphi, x) + (\frac{\partial}{\partial u} g)(T_m, \varphi, x)(u - T_m)$. One quickly sees that $(\frac{\partial}{\partial u} g)(T_m, \varphi, x) =: \beta(\varphi, x)$ is basically a phase dependant coupling constant coupling $\partial_t \varphi$ to u . Assuming that lower φ means molten, and higher φ means solid, it is reasonable to assume that higher temperature u would lower $\partial_t \varphi$, so one would expect the coupling constant $\beta(\varphi, x)$ to be negative. Assuming $\beta(\varphi, x) < 0$ one further can, by abuse of notation, define $T_m(\varphi, x) := -\frac{g(T_m, \varphi, x)}{\beta(\varphi, x)}$ which is basically something like a position and phase dependent “melting point”, though the phase dependence of course makes the interpretation as “melting point” somewhat unsuitable, as the considered approximation can then be written as $g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(\varphi, x)(u - T_m(\varphi, x))$, which is negative for $u - T_m(\varphi, x) > 0$ (“melting”) and positive for $u - T_m(\varphi, x) < 0$ (“freezing”).

- (2) Phase independent freezing point assumption and constant freezing point assumption ($g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(\varphi, x)(u - T_m(x))$, $g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(\varphi, x)(u - T_m(x))$): Going further than the narrow temperature range approximation for the coupling function g , one can assume that $T_m(\varphi, x)$ is constant in φ or even constant, basically assuming, in the case of the phase independent freezing point assumption, that the temperature at which the coupling starts to increase the phase (“freezing”) is the same regardless of phase, and only depends on local impurities etc., so on the position, and assuming additionally, in the case of the constant freezing point assumption, that local impurities etc. are negligible or do not affect the melting point.
- (3) Phase independent coupling assumption and constant coupling assumption ($g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(x)(u - T_m(\varphi, x))$, $g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(x)(u - T_m(\varphi, x))$): Independently of the phase independent freezing point assumption one can, again based on the narrow temperature range assumption for g , go even further and assume that $\beta(\varphi, x)$ is independent of the phase or even constant, yielding $g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(x)(u - T_m(\varphi, x))$ or even $g(u, \varphi, x) \approx \beta(x)(u - T_m(x))$.

Simplifications of the $k(u, \varphi, x)$ -term:

- (1) Temperature independent thermal conductivity approximation ($k(u, \varphi, x) \approx k(T_m, \varphi, x)$): As the thermal conductivity of both metals and metal melts is usually very high, and often changes comparatively slowly when no phase changes happen, as seen for example for both solid and liquid aluminum near the melting point in the thermal conductivity plot in [LeitnerEtAl], it seems plausible that for metals, thermal conductivity can be approximated to be only phase dependent, but not temperature dependent, if only a limited temperature range around the melting point is considered, yielding the approximation $k(u, \varphi, x) \approx k(T_m, \varphi, x)$.
- (2) Phase independent thermal conductivity assumption ($k(u, \varphi, x) \approx k(u, x)$): Similarly, one can of course assume that the thermal conductivity is approximately phase independent, leading to the approximation $k(u, \varphi, x) \approx k(u, x)$ for some $k(u, x)$. This assumption is not very physical, at least for metals, because the thermal conductivity of metals usually drops significantly when they melt, however, especially in conjunction with the temperature independent thermal conductivity approximation it makes the maths much easier.
- (3) Homogeneous thermal conductivity assumption ($k(u, \varphi, x) \approx k(u, \varphi)$): Independently of the other two simplifications pertaining to this term, one can of course assume that the material is approximately homogeneous, at least regarding thermal conductivity, yielding the approximation $k(u, \varphi, x) \approx k(u, \varphi)$ for some $k(u, \varphi)$.

Simplifications of the $k_\varphi(u, \varphi, x)$ -term:

- (1) Constant phase conductivity assumption ($k_\varphi(u, \varphi, x) \approx k_\varphi$): Completely analogously to the simplifications of the $k(u, \varphi, x)$ term, various simplifications of the $k_\varphi(u, \varphi, x)$ term can be considered, however, due to the very speculative nature of phase conduction, one usually directly assumes $k_\varphi(u, \varphi, x) \approx \text{const.}$, therefore, this work considers this to be the only notable simplification pertaining to the $k_\varphi(u, \varphi, x)$ -term.

Simplifications of the $f(x, t)$ -term:

- (1) No internal heat source assumption ($f(x, t) = 0$): Since most materials don’t have an internal heat source, some authors may simply set $f(x, t) = 0$. Intermediate simplifications, like time independent f , are usually not considered.

2.3. An overview over the surveyed works. Now that we have fixed our systematics for classifying the surveyed works, we first give a quick overview over the surveyed works, listing for every reference:

- the model they consider,
- the results they obtain,

and further listing particularly noteworthy peculiarities of some of the works.

2.4. The models considered in the references. Adapting the models considered in the references to our notation we get the following list:

Reference	Phasefield model	Boundary conditions
[Caginalp]	$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + \frac{l}{2} \varphi_t &= k \Delta u \\ \tau \partial_t \varphi &= \xi^2 \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + 2(u - T_m) \\ \text{with } W'(\varphi) &= \frac{1}{2}(\varphi^3 - \varphi) \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} u(x) &= u_\Gamma(x) \\ \varphi(x) &= \varphi_\Gamma(x) \end{aligned}$
[CherMira]	$\begin{aligned} \epsilon \partial_t u + \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta u \\ \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + (u - T_m) \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \partial_n u &= 0 \\ \partial_t \varphi - \Delta_\Gamma \varphi + \lambda \varphi + \partial_n \varphi + g(\varphi) &= 0 \end{aligned}$
[Moroşanu]	$\begin{aligned} \rho c \partial_t u + \frac{l}{2} \partial_t \varphi &= k \Delta u + f(x, t) \\ \alpha \xi \partial_t \varphi &= \xi \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + \beta \cdot (u - T_m(x, t)) \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} k \partial_n u + \rho c \partial_t u - \Delta_\Gamma u + hu + g_1(u, x, t) &= w_1(x, t) \\ \xi \partial_n \varphi + \alpha \xi \partial_t \varphi - \Delta_\Gamma \varphi + c_0 \varphi + g_2(\varphi, x, t) &= w_2(x, t) \end{aligned}$
[FeirEtAl]	$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + \lambda \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta u \\ \partial_t \varphi &= O\varphi - W'(\varphi) + \lambda(u - T_m) \\ O\varphi &:= J[\varphi] - \varphi \end{aligned}$	$u = T_m$
[GrasSchi]	$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta u \\ \partial_t \varphi &= O\varphi - W'(\varphi) + (u - T_m) \\ O\varphi &:= -J[\varphi] - \kappa(x)\varphi \end{aligned}$	$u = T_m$
[CollGila]	$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + \partial_t E(\varphi) &= -A^{\epsilon_1} u + f(x, t) \\ \partial_t \varphi &\in -B^{\epsilon_2} \varphi - W'(\varphi) + E'(\varphi)u \\ \text{with } A^{\epsilon_1}, B^{\epsilon_2} &\text{ fractional powers of linear operators that fulfill some properties, } W' \text{ a possibly multivalued subdifferential, and} \\ E(\varphi) &:= (\int_0^\varphi l) + E_0 \end{aligned}$	Linear boundary conditions are encoded in the subvectorspaces $D(A), D(B) \subseteq L^2(\Omega)$ where A, B are defined, and are restricted by the assumptions on A, B .
[Rocca]	$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + \partial_t E(\varphi) &= \nabla \cdot (k(u) \nabla u) + m(x, t) \\ \mu \partial_t^2 \varphi + \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + E'(\varphi)(T_m^{-1} - u^{-1}) \\ \text{with } k(u) &= \alpha'(u) \text{ for } \alpha(u) := k_1 u - k_2 u^{-1} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \partial_n \alpha(u) + \gamma \alpha(u) &= \gamma \alpha(u_\Gamma) \\ \partial_n \varphi &= 0 \\ \text{where } u_\Gamma &\text{ is time-independent} \end{aligned}$
[CollEtAl]	$\begin{aligned} \epsilon \partial_t u + \partial_t E(\varphi) &= \nabla \cdot (k(u) \nabla u) + f(x, t) \\ \delta \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta \varphi - W'(x) + E'(\varphi)j'(u) \\ \text{with } k(u) &:= j''(u), \text{ for some nonnegative convex } j \text{ with } j'(T_m) = 0 \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \text{Either } u = T_m, \text{ or } -\partial_n j'(u) &= \eta(j'(u) - j'(u_\Gamma)) \\ \text{for some time dependent } u_\Gamma, & \\ \text{and } \partial_n \varphi = 0 & \end{aligned}$
[CherEtAl]	$\begin{aligned} \eta \partial_t u + \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta u \\ \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + (u - T_m) \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \partial_n u &= 0 \\ \varphi &= \psi_\Gamma \end{aligned}$
[GrasEtAl]	$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + \partial_t \varphi &= \Delta u + f(x, t) \\ \epsilon \partial_t^2 \varphi + \partial_t \varphi &= J[\varphi] - W'(\varphi) + (u - T_m) \end{aligned}$	$u = T_m$
[Colturat]	$\begin{aligned} u^{-1} \partial_t u + l \partial_t \varphi &= k_0 \Delta u + F(x, t) \\ \partial_t \varphi &\in \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + lu \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \partial_n u &= 0 \\ \partial_n \varphi &= 0 \end{aligned}$
[Laurenço]	$\begin{aligned} c \partial_t u + l(\varphi) \partial_t \varphi &= \nabla \cdot (k(\varphi) \nabla u) \\ \tau \partial_t \varphi &\in \xi^2 \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + l(\varphi)u \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \partial_n u &= 0 \\ \partial_n \varphi &= 0 \end{aligned}$

2.5. The results established in the references. Grouping the results into different result types, with the more ambiguous result types characterized as follows:

Result type	Description
well posedness	Existence plus some estimate of the form $ (u_1, \varphi_1) - (u_2, \varphi_2) _{V([0, T]; W)} \leq F_T(\text{data}_1, \text{data}_2)$ with $F_T(\text{data}_1, \text{data}_2) \rightarrow 0$ when the boundary conditions, initial conditions etc. in data_2 converge to data_1 . Obviously implies uniqueness too.
stability	Existence plus some estimate of the form $\forall t : (u_1(t), \varphi_1(t)) - (u_2(t), \varphi_2(t)) \leq c_{1,2} := F(\text{data}_1, \text{data}_2)$ with $F(\text{data}_1, \text{data}_2) \rightarrow 0$ when the boundary conditions, initial conditions etc. in data_2 converge to data_1 . Obviously is a special type of well posedness result.
long term behaviour	Results about the behaviour as $t \rightarrow \infty$, particularly ω -limit results, but technically also things like stability and global boundedness.

and additionally listing some of the main techniques used for each work, we have:

Reference	main results	main techniques
[Caginalp]	existence, uniqueness, smoothness	Reduction to standard semilinear parabolic form via change of variables to $A(u, \varphi)^t$ with constant A , yielding local existence, global existence via energy method by bounding the supremum norm via bounded invariant subsets.
[CherMira]	well posedness, global attractors	Existence theorem for analogous model with regular potential yields solution, as solutions can be bounded away from the singularities. The continuous dependence on the initial data etc. is shown with Gronwalls lemma, as usual.
[Moroşanu]	well posedness	A slight adaptation of a well posedness result for some reaction-diffusion style equation yields well posedness for the phase evolution if the temperature is given. Using the Leray–Schauder principle, the solution operator from that adapted result is then used to construct a solution to the whole problem.
[FeirEtAl]	well posedness, global boundedness, long term behaviour	Construction of the solution as a limit of solutions to parabolic systems, compactness of approximations and well posedness estimate use energy estimates using Gronwalls lemma.
[GrasSchi]	existence, uniqueness, global attractors	Pre-existing compactness argument from [FeirEtAl] with slightly different energy estimates.
[CollGila]	well posedness, long term behaviour	Construction of the solution as a limit of solutions to a simpler system solved via a Faedo Galerkin scheme, compactness of approximations and continuous dependence on initial data etc. via energy estimates using Gronwalls lemma.
[Rocca]	well posedness, boundedness and weak regularity results	Construction of the solution as a limit of solutions to a parametrized different simpler system, compactness of approximations via Aubin-Lions lemma and a generalized Arzela Ascoli theorem using energy estimates using Gronwalls lemma, continuous dependence on initial data etc. using Gronwalls lemma.
[CollEtAl]	existence, uniqueness, long term behaviour	Construction of the solution as a limit of solutions to simpler systems, compactness via energy estimates and then as usual passing to the limit via compactness.
[CherEtAl]	well posedness, global boundedness	Slight adaptation of the argumentative structure in [CherMira].

[GrasEtAl]	well posedness, long term behaviour	Short term existence via Schauder fixed point theorem, global existence via repeated extension and energy estimates via Gronwalls lemma, existence for less regular initial data via approximation of that initial data and passing to the limit. Well posedness estimate via Gronwalls lemma.
[Colturat]	existence, uniqueness, long term behaviour	Existence via backward finite difference scheme and passage to the limit via compactness via energy bounds, obtained using discrete induction. Uniqueness and the necessary bounds for the compactness for the long term behaviour results are shown via Gronwalls lemma.
[Laurenço]	existence, long term behaviour	Construction of the solution as a limit of solutions to regularized systems found using the Galerkin method, obtaining the compactness via energy estimates.

2.6. Noteworthy peculiarities of some references. Concluding our overview over the selected references, we note the following significant peculiarities of some of the references:

References	peculiarities
[FeirEtAl] [GrasSchi] [GrasEtAl]	Instead of the $\Delta\varphi$, some axiomatically specified operators are used in [FeirEtAl] and [GrasSchi], which are modeled after concrete examples of nonlocal operators involving convolution, making the systems that are practically considered integrodifferential. This also makes a boundary condition on φ unnecessary. Similarly, [?] directly uses a convolution operator, making the system integrodifferential, and also making a boundary condition on φ unnecessary again.
[CollGila]	Instead of the Δ 's, some axiomatically specified fractional Δ -like differential operators are used, and furthermore, this work works with a more general class of potentials W , so that W' is a possibly multivalued subdifferential, and the second equation is a differential inclusion. However, the system actually considered is not the strong form with the differential inclusion, but some weak formulation that resembles the strong form.
[CollEtAl]	The proofs in this work are somewhat sketchy, for example, at one point, they treat local solutions as if they were global "for simplicity". Generally, this work leaves much of the details to the reader.
[Colturat],[Laurenço]	These works work with a more general class of potentials W , including ones which jump. This requires the second equation to become a differential inclusion using the subdifferential of W as W' .

2.7. Classifying the models. After the overview we now proceed by classifying the works according to the model considered, as sketched in the beginning of this section on existing results. Since most references basically employ most simplifying assumptions and approximations, it is noted when a reference does not need a specific simplification. Constant coefficients are ignored.

Reference	Linear enthalpy assumption	Narrow temp. range approx. for E	Constant heat capacity assumption	Narrow temp. range approx. for g	Phase indep. freezing point assumpt.	constant freezing point assumption	Phase indep. coupling assumption	Constant coupling assumption	Temp. indep. thermal cond. approx.	Phase indep. thermal cond. assumpt.	Homogeneous thermal cond. assumpt.	Constant phase conductivity assumpt.	No internal heat source assumpt.	Case specific deviations
[Caginalp]														-
[CherMira]														-
[CherEtAl]														-
[GrasEtAl]														The second equation contains a $\epsilon \partial_t^2 \varphi$ term in addition to the $\partial_t \varphi$ term, and the $\Delta \varphi$ is replaced by a homogeneous (with position independent convolution kernel) convolution operator.
[FeirEtAl]												(X)		The $\Delta \varphi$ is replaced by an axiomatically specified possibly inhomogeneous operator modeled after convolution operators.
[GrasSchi]												(X)		The $\Delta \varphi$ is replaced by an axiomatically specified possibly inhomogeneous operator modeled after convolution operators.
[Moroşanu]						X							X	Time dependent T_m .
[Colturat]	X	X	X										X	The enthalpy considered is almost linear, but instead of $\lambda_1 u$, it uses $\log(u)$. Also, the double well potential used need not be differentiable, so the second “equation” is a differential inclusion, working with the subdifferential of W .

[Rocca]	X						X	X				X	The second equation contains a $\mu\partial_t^2\varphi$ term in addition to the $\partial_t\varphi$ term. Even though α is very restricted, $k(u) = \alpha'(u)$ is a temperature dependent thermal conductivity. Also $\beta(\varphi) = E'(\varphi)$.
[CollEtAl]	X			X			X	X	X			X	The coupling is something in between a fully general coupling, and a coupling of the form $\beta(\varphi(x))u(x)$, having the form $E'(\varphi)j'(u)$. Also $k(u) = j''(u)$, so given k, E from the first equation, the coupling is mostly determined.
[CollGila]	X						X	X			X	X	Instead of the two Laplace operators, this source uses constant operators $A^{\epsilon_1}, B^{\epsilon_2}$ possibly allowing for fully inhomogeneous but not state dependent heat and phase capacity and conduction. Also $\beta(\varphi) = E'(\varphi)$.
[Laurenço]	X						X	X		X			

2.8. A coarse outline of the state of the art. Looking at the classification of the considered systems, it is readily apparent that the existing literature quite often goes beyond a linear enthalpy function and often considers more complex coupling functions as well.

Furthermore, there seems to be a focus on homogeneous materials, considering for example that of the surveyed works only [Moroşanu] didn't have the constant freezing point assumption, and only [CollGila] didn't have the homogeneous thermal conductivity assumption.

This is not a significant gap in the research though, since the calculations for inhomogeneous materials can mostly be done along the same lines as the calculations for homogeneous materials, for example the energy method works very similarly, and also many of the results for heat equations work for the inhomogeneous case as well.

However, there also seems to be a lack of works dealing with materials with phase dependent thermal properties. Looking at the heat capacity, [Colturat] is the only surveyed work that doesn't work with a constant heat capacity, and the heat capacity used within this work is fixed to be u^{-1} , so especially phase independent. Looking at the thermal conductivity, similarly, [Laurenço] is the only surveyed work that works with a phase dependent thermal conductivity, and this work was found searching for systems that work with phase dependent thermal conductivity, and it only shows existence but not uniqueness of weak solutions.

Now unlike in the case of inhomogeneous materials, the case of materials with phase dependent thermal properties is much more difficult to treat than for example the case of phase and temperature independent heat capacity and thermal conductivity, because the phase dependent thermal properties make the system quasilinear.

Furthermore, most real world materials actually have phase dependent thermal properties, so this case is physically highly significant.

Given these circumstances, it seems that there is a gap in the literature regarding strong well-posedness results for materials with phase dependent thermal properties.

3. THE AIM OF THIS THESIS

Since it seems like there is a significant gap in the literature regarding strong well-posedness results for materials with phase dependent thermal properties, the main goal of this thesis will be to obtain strong well-posedness results for materials with at least partly phase dependent thermal properties, more concretely with phase dependent thermal conductivity, but no phase dependent heat capacity.

Furthermore, since considering inhomogeneous materials mainly just changes the technicalities of the computations, we consider a mostly inhomogeneous system. More concretely, we consider a system with only the parameters τ, ξ and the potential W from the Landau Ginzburg model A equation being position independent, and the completely general coupling function $g(u, \varphi, x)$ being position dependent.

We consider the system:

$$E(u, \varphi, x)_t = \nabla \cdot (k(\varphi, x) \nabla u)$$

$$\varphi_t = \lambda_\varphi \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x)$$

with some given initial condition and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions for u and φ .

Now that might look like the second equation can only model materials with homogeneous physical properties regarding phase transitions well, but by changing g , one can control the phase transition speed dependent on x and effectively perturb W dependent on x , changing the interface sharpness dependent on x , so the position dependent coupling term actually suffices for modelling quite general materials already, hence we do not generalize further in the second equation.

Another notable detail is that the $W'(\varphi)$ could obviously be included in the $g(u, \varphi, x)$, however, we consider it separately, so that the second equation optically more strongly resembles the Landau Ginzburg model A equation.

Additionally, this thesis aims to introduce the core techniques for showing well posedness of parabolic systems to a broad audience, including undergraduates. With this goal in mind, we present the fundamental techniques we need and mainly work with strong solutions, so we neither have to technically explain which calculations we can and which calculations we cannot do with some forms of weak solutions, nor do we leave these justifications to the reader.

4. BASIC DEFINITIONS

Before we formalize the problem, we shall first give the basic definitions required.

Firstly, we fix which class of domains Ω we consider here:

Definition 1. (domain definition)

We define Ω to be an open and bounded C^3 -domain in \mathbb{R}^3 .

Now we define some fundamental and commonly used function spaces we'll need further down the line, including the solution space $C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega} \times [T_1, T_2])$.

Definition 2. (basic function spaces & solution space)

We define, for $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$:

$$C^j(\Omega)$$

to be the space of continuous real valued functions $f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ on Ω such that all partial derivatives $\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_l}} f$ for $l \leq j, i_1, \dots, i_l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ exist in the classical sense and are continuous.

Based on $C^j(\Omega)$ we further define for $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$:

$$C^j(\overline{\Omega})$$

to be the subspace of functions $f \in C^j(\Omega)$ such that f and all partial derivatives guaranteed to exist by the definition of $C^j(\Omega)$ can be continuously extended to $\overline{\Omega}$.

For $f \in C^j(\overline{\Omega})$, we automatically have that f and all partial derivatives $\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_l}} f$ for $l \leq j, i_1, \dots, i_l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are bounded because they are continuously extendable to the compact set $\overline{\Omega}$. We use this to define the norm:

$$|f|_{C^j(\overline{\Omega})} := \max \left(\sup_{x \in \Omega} |f(x)|, \max_{l \leq j, i_1, \dots, i_l \in \{1, 2, 3\}} \sup_{x \in \Omega} |\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_l}} f(x)| \right)$$

Further we define for $j \in \mathbb{N}_0, k \in \{0, 1\}$:

$$C^{j,k}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$$

to be the space of continuous real valued functions $f(x_1, x_2, x_3, t)$ on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ such that all partial derivatives $\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_l}} f$ for $l \leq j, i_1, \dots, i_l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and if $k = 1$ also $\partial_t f$ exist in the classical sense and are continuous.

Based on $C^{j,k}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ we further define, analogously to the definition of $C^j(\overline{\Omega})$, for such $j \in \mathbb{N}_0, k \in \{0, 1\}$:

$$C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$$

to be the subspace of functions $f \in C^{j,k}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ such that f and all partial derivatives guaranteed to exist by the definition of $C^{j,k}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ can be continuously extended to $\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)}$.

Additionally, for each function space V of the spaces defined above we define V^n to be the space of vector valued functions with values in \mathbb{R}^n such that each component is in V , and on $C^j(\overline{\Omega})^n$ we define the norm exactly as for $C^j(\overline{\Omega})$, where the norms are now to be understood as euclidean norms of vectors:

$$|f|_{C^j(\overline{\Omega})^n} := \max \left(\sup_{x \in \Omega} |f(x)|, \max_{l \leq j, i_1, \dots, i_l \in \{1, 2, 3\}} \sup_{x \in \Omega} |\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_l}} f(x)| \right)$$

also, using that every function in $C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is automatically bounded, we define the C^0 -norm on $C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ as usual via:

$$|f|_{C^0} := \sup_{(x,t) \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} |f(x, t)|$$

Remark. Due to Schwarz's theorem, partial derivatives commute here, so we could also introduce multiindex notation, and for example define $|f|_{C^j(\overline{\Omega})}$ differently but equivalently in the sense of equivalence of norms via multiindices. However, we will mostly work with at most twice partially differentiable functions anyway, and hence don't really need that multiindex notation. Also, just like the C^j norms on $C^j(\overline{\Omega})$, we could, besides the C^0 -norm on $C^{0,0}$, define $C^{j,k}$ -norms on $C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, however, for the purpose of this thesis, we won't need to consider other norms besides the C^0 norm on the $C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, since in the calculations and continuity and boundedness results we will basically replace $C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ with a parabolic Hölder space of slightly more regular functions and with a slightly stronger norm. We essentially work on the Hölder spaces, and only define $C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ to properly define a very natural strong solution concept, and hence do not need higher order $C^{j,k}$ -norms. Now that we have defined the required spaces of continuously differentiable functions, we define classical homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and the subspaces encoding them. First, we define them for simple spatial fields:

Definition 3. (Neumann boundary conditions)

We define $f \in C^1(\overline{\Omega})$ to have homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions if

$$(\nabla f) \cdot \vec{n} = 0$$

holds pointwise on $\partial\Omega$, where:

- $\vec{n} = (n_1, n_2, n_3)^t$ is the normal vector field of $\overline{\Omega}$ in x_1, x_2, x_3 -coordinates.
- ∇f is the continuous extension of the classical gradient ∇f on Ω to $\overline{\Omega}$.

Now that we have defined the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, we encode them in subspaces of $C^j(\overline{\Omega})$:

Definition 4. We further define $C_N^j(\overline{\Omega})$ to be the linear subspace of functions in $C^j(\overline{\Omega})$ that have homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, for all $j \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$.

Remark. Each $C_N^j(\overline{\Omega})$ is a closed linear subspace of $C^j(\overline{\Omega})$. This is because the map $\nabla : C^j(\overline{\Omega}) \rightarrow C^0(\overline{\Omega})$; $f \mapsto$ continuous extension of the classical gradient to $\overline{\Omega}$ is continuous.

Because it is continuous, for any $x \in \partial\Omega$, the linear functional $(\nabla f(x)) \cdot \vec{n}(x)$ is continuous in f as well. But then the condition imposed is simply that f lies in the kernels of infinitely many continuous linear functionals, and hence is simply the intersection of infinitely many closed subspaces of $C^2(\overline{\Omega})$.

Now that we defined Neumann boundary conditions for simple spatial fields, we would like to define them for time dependent fields as well, by simply requiring that the time dependent field has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions at each time.

In order to do this, we'll now first define a simple notation to formalize the idea of considering a time dependent field at a time:

Definition 5. (time slice notation)

Since given a function $f : X \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow Y$ one often considers "time slices" $g : x \mapsto f(x, t)$, we define, for any function $f : X \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow Y$, the notation $f(t)$ for the map $X \rightarrow Y$; $x \mapsto f(x, t)$.

If $f : \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow Y$ (with Y some metric space) is further continuous and continuously extendable to $\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)$ (so especially if $f \in C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$), we further define $f(T_1)$ to be the map $x \mapsto \tilde{f}(x, T_1)$ and $f(T_2)$ to be the map $x \mapsto \tilde{f}(x, T_2)$, where \tilde{f} is the unique continuous extension of f to $\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)$.

Remark. If $f \in C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$, then also $f(t) \in C^j(\overline{\Omega})$ for any $t \in (T_1, T_2)$.

One easily sees this by noting that if \tilde{f} is the continuous extension of f , and $\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_j}} \tilde{f}$ is the continuous extension of some arbitrary spatial partial derivative of up to j -th order, to $\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)$, $\tilde{f}(t)$ is the continuous extension of $f(t)$ and $\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_j}} \tilde{f}(t)$ is the continuous extension of $\partial_{x_{i_1}} \dots \partial_{x_{i_j}} f(t)$, to $\overline{\Omega}$, so the required continuous extensions exist.

Also, for $t \in (T_1, T_2)$, time slices obviously commute with classical partial derivatives in space directions, it doesn't matter if one first takes such a time slice, and then takes the partial derivative, or the other way around. Thus, one can formally ambiguously write things like $\nabla f(t)$ for $t \in (T_1, T_2)$, because it does not matter whether the gradient or the time slice is applied first.

Actually, we even have that if $f \in C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$, also $f(T_1), f(T_2) \in C^j(\overline{\Omega})$, with taking partial derivatives in space directions and taking these extended time slices commuting again, with the time slice of the respective spatial derivative being well-defined because it is at least in $C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$, so continuously extendable to $\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)$. However, we won't need this in our proofs, it's just good to know for the intuitive understanding, so we won't prove this remark.

Definition 6. (Neumann boundary conditions for time dependent fields)

We define $f \in C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $j \geq 1$ to have homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions if $\forall t \in (T_1, T_2) : f(t)$ has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions.

Remark. Equivalently, we could require that $\forall t \in [T_1, T_2] : f(t)$ has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, because the condition that $\forall t \in (T_1, T_2) : f(t)$ has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions is obviously equivalent to the condition that $(\nabla f)(x, t) \cdot \vec{n}(x) = 0$ on $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, for ∇f the continuous extension of the gradient to $\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)$, and \vec{n} the normal vector field of $\overline{\Omega}$, but then

also, since $(\nabla f)(x, t) \cdot \vec{n}(x)$ is continuous on $\partial\Omega \times [T_1, T_2]$ and 0 on $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, which is dense in $\partial\Omega \times [T_1, T_2]$, $(\nabla f)(x, t) \cdot \vec{n}(x)$ is 0 on $\partial\Omega \times [T_1, T_2]$, which is again equivalent to $\forall t \in [T_1, T_2] : f(t)$ has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions. Again, we won't need this in our proofs, and just state it for the intuitive understanding, so we won't prove this.

Now as with the Neumann boundary conditions for time independent fields, we encode the Neumann boundary conditions for time independent fields in a subspacespace of $C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$:

Definition 7. We further define $C_N^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ to be the linear subspace of functions in $C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ that have homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, for all $j \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$.

Remark. Analogously to the case for simple spatial fields, if we defined the $C^{j,k}$ -norms on $C^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ analogously to the C^j -norms, by simply taking the maximum of the supremum norms of the function and all partial derivatives guaranteed to exist, we'd again find, essentially because the continuous extension of the spatial gradient is then again continuous with respect to the $C^{j,k}$ -norm for $j \geq 1$, and the Neumann boundary conditions can be alternatively characterized via $(\nabla f)(x, t) \cdot \vec{n}(x) = 0$ on $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, that the subspace $C_N^{j,k}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a closed subspace with respect to this $C^{j,k}$ -norms for $j \geq 1$.

Definition 8. (PDE notation)

As is usually done when considering strong solutions to parabolic PDEs we write, understanding all occurring partial derivatives in the classical sense:

- x shorthand for x_1, x_2, x_3 .
- u, φ shorthand for $u(x_1, x_2, x_3, t), \varphi(x_1, x_2, x_3, t)$.
- $\nabla \cdot (f_1, f_2, f_3)^t$ shorthand for the vector field divergence $\sum_{i=1}^3 \partial_{x_i} f_i$, for $f(x_1, x_2, x_3, t)$.
- ∇f shorthand for the spatial gradient column vector $(\partial_{x_1} f, \partial_{x_2} f, \partial_{x_3} f)^t$, for $f(x_1, x_2, x_3, t)$.
- $(\nabla_x f)(\dots, x_1, x_2, x_3, t)$ shorthand for the column vector $(\partial_{x_1} f, \partial_{x_2} f, \partial_{x_3} f)^t$, for f taking more variables besides x_1, x_2, x_3 and t .
- Δf shorthand for $\nabla \cdot (\nabla f) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \partial_{x_i}^2 f_i$, for $f(x_1, x_2, x_3, t)$.
- $(f)_i$ shorthand for the components for vector valued functions f .

Sometimes we instead consider the continuous extensions of functions, gradients and other quantities to $\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)}$, but denote them like the original quantities themselves, in this case, it is mentioned that a continuous extension is considered, at least when this is not clear from the context.

5. THE SYSTEM CONSIDERED

Now that we have the necessary preliminary definitions, we proceed by formally defining the system we want well-posedness results for.

Concretely, we consider the following system on cylindrical domains of the form $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, where Ω is an open and bounded C^3 -domain in \mathbb{R}^3 :

$$(5.1) \quad E(u, \varphi, x)_t = \nabla \cdot (k(\varphi, x) \nabla u)$$

$$(5.2) \quad \varphi_t = \lambda_\varphi \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x)$$

for an enthalpy $E(u, \varphi, x)$ of the form

$$E(u, \varphi, x) = c_u(x)u + c_\varphi(x)\varphi + E_0(x)$$

We consider it in a strong sense, that is we understand the differential operators in the classical sense, and require equation (5.1) and equation (5.2) hold pointwise on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$.

As solution space for u, φ we choose $C_N^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, implicitly imposing homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions.

Additionally we will always impose some initial condition, by requiring, using timeslice notation, given some functions $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in C^2(\overline{\Omega})$:

$$u(T_1) = u_{T_1}, \varphi(T_1) = \varphi_{T_1}$$

Furthermore, we of course make some uniform ellipticity, regularity and boundedness assumptions on the functions in the system, concretely we assume:

(1)

$$\forall \varphi \in \mathbb{R}, x \in \Omega : k(\varphi, x) \in [k_{min}, k_{max}] \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}$$

(2)

$$\forall x \in \Omega : c_u(x) \in [c_{min}, c_{max}] \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}$$

(3)

$$c_\varphi, c_u \in C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$$

(4)

g is Lipschitz with $|g(u, \varphi, x)|$ bounded by a constant

(5)

W' is Lipschitz with $|W'(\varphi)|$ is bounded by a constant

(6)

$k \in C^1(\mathbb{R} \times \Omega)$ with $k, \nabla k, \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k$ continuously extendable to $\overline{\mathbb{R} \times \Omega} = \mathbb{R} \times \overline{\Omega}$

(7)

$|\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k(\varphi, x)|, |\nabla_x k(\varphi, x)|$ are bounded by a constant

(8)

$k, \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k(\varphi, x), \nabla_x k(\varphi, x)$ are Lipschitz

Under these assumptions, we now formally define:

Definition 9. (solution definition)

Encoding the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions in the solution space, we define $u, \varphi \in C_N^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ to be a solution to the system equation (5.1), equation (5.2) with initial data $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$ if and only if:

- equation (5.1), equation (5.2) hold pointwise on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$.
- $u(T_1) = u_{T_1}, \varphi(T_1) = \varphi_{T_1}$

When the system considered or the initial data are clear from the context we often omit that particular information, writing for example only $u, \varphi \in C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a solution.

6. FOUNDATIONAL TECHNIQUES FOR WORKING WITH PARABOLIC SYSTEMS

In order to work with our parabolic system we will need the following standard techniques:

- a simple version of the energy method,
- embedding theorems and norm interpolation theorems,
- theorems for solving linear parabolic PDEs and bounding their solutions,
- a fixed point theorem, concretely Schaefer's fixed point theorem.

6.1. A high level overview. Now before we present the preliminary results we need, we shall give a high-level overview of what these techniques are, and why we need them, starting with the energy method.

One of the two most elementary techniques we need is the so-called energy method. The energy method in its simple form is a technique to, for some some function f on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, bound the so called L^2 -norm $|f(t)|_{L^2}$ for all $t \in (T_1, T_2)$ in terms of $|f(T_1)|_{L^2}$ and other quantities that essentially works as follows:

- (1) Express $\frac{d}{dt}|f(t)|_{L^2}^2$ as $\int_{\Omega} 2f(t)f_t(t)$ via the Feynmann trick, and use the properties of f , which is usually a solution to a parabolic PDE or a difference of solutions to parabolic PDEs, to express $f_t(t)$ without the time derivative.
- (2) Use partial integration and some elementary bounding tricks to compute a suitably well-behaved bound $\frac{d}{dt}|f(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq b(|f(t)|_{L^2}^2, t)$.
- (3) Use Gronwalls Lemma to derive a bound $|f(t)|_{L^2} \leq B(t, f(T_1))$

Concretely, we will need the energy method for the well-posedness, to get an initial “weak” well-posedness result, which we then “upgrade” using bounds on our solutions so we obtain a much “stronger” well-posedness result, that is, a well posedness result in a stronger norm.

This technique is not completely elementary, since it requires partial integration in multiple dimensions, so effectively the Gauß theorem, but except for that, it is quite intuitive and elementary.

The second type of elementary techniques we need are embedding theorems and norm interpolation theorems. At their core, both embedding theorems and norm interpolation theorems are about bounding norms in terms of other norms, so we consider them as one group of techniques. Since the embedding theorems are more fundamental, we shall first have a look at them:

Often described as the “bread and butter” of PDE researchers, embedding theorems are simple theorems that at their core essentially say that if a function f is in some normed function space V , it also is in some normed function space W , with $|f|_W \leq c|f|_V$ for some constant c , so the V -norm is at least as strong as the W -norm.

Now there are some details of some embedding theorems this simple characterization of embedding theorems glosses over, for example many of the function spaces considered in PDE research are equivalence classes modulo equality almost everywhere, but some, like Hölder spaces for example, aren’t, so the theorems sometimes show the existence of suitable unique representatives f of arbitrary equivalence classes v so that $|f|_W \leq c|v|_V$, but the core idea remains the same.

We will mostly need those embedding theorems to basically adapt results working with different types of function spaces to our setting.

Now that we have seen what embedding theorems are, we shall have a look at the lesser used norm interpolation theorems:

Essentially, norm interpolation theorems are results of the form $|f|_{V_1} \leq c|f|_{V_2}^{\theta}|f|_{V_3}^{1-\theta}$ for some $\theta \in (0, 1)$. Intuitively, they basically allow to control a norm $|*|_{V_1}$ in terms of a weaker norm $|*|_{V_2}$ and a stronger norm $|*|_{V_3}$.

They will be useful for us because if $|f|_{V_2}^{\theta}$ or $|f|_{V_3}^{\theta}$ goes to zero and the other stays bounded, the whole right hand side of $|f|_{V_1} \leq c|f|_{V_2}^{\theta}|f|_{V_3}^{1-\theta}$, and hence also $|f|_{V_1}$, go to zero, so if we have the stronger V_3 -norm bounded, having the weaker V_2 -norm go to zero then yields that the stronger V_1 norm goes to zero as well.

This will essentially allow us to use boundedness results to upgrade our well posedness results a first time.

Thirdly, we will need theorems for solving linear parabolic PDEs and bounding their solutions. These types of results guarantee the existence of higher regularity solutions to linear parabolic PDEs for source terms and coefficient functions of lower regularity with higher regularity bounds on the solutions in terms of lower regularity bounds on the source term and coefficients.

We will use these results extensively. Firstly we will use them to define a functional whose fixed points are exactly the solutions to our system with some given initial data, as well as to show the compactness required for applying Schaefer's fixed point theorem. Secondly we will use a very generally applicable computation based on a core trick that has been "rediscovered" countless times to convert the boundedness results to a continuity result that says the solutions to the linear parabolic PDEs depend continuously on the parameter functions, the initial data, and the source term, in some sense to be specified later, which will allow us to upgrade our well-posedness result a second time.

Fourth, there is the Schaefer fixed point theorem. This theorem simply states that if $\mathcal{F} : V \rightarrow V$ is a continuous map on some Banachspace V that is compact in the usual sense that bounded sets are mapped to precompact sets, and the so called escape set $\mathcal{E} := \{v \in V : \exists \lambda \in [0, 1] : v = \lambda \mathcal{F}(v)\}$ is bounded, \mathcal{F} has a fixed point.

We will apply this to our functional whose fixed points are solutions to our system to show the existence of solutions by fixed point method, as usual. Now showing existence for parabolic PDEs via fixed point methods always works similarly, but this is one of these cases where the core idea can be best seen in an example, so we won't sketch how this works here, since the existence proof in this thesis already showcases this better than a sketch would.

6.2. Basics required for the energy method. Now that we have concluded our high level overview, we continue by presenting the results we need, starting with the required foundations for working with the energy method. Concretely, we'll now first have a look at what L^2 norms and scalar products are and at the basics for working with them, then we'll have a look at the Feynman trick, and thirdly we'll see how the partial integration result we need follows from the Gauß theorem.

6.2.1. Foundations for working with the L^2 -norm. Since the energy method relies on L^2 -norms and scalar products, we'll now first present the foundations for working with L^2 -norms.

First, we have to define what the L^2 -norm is, since we will use it in conjunction with the L^2 scalar product, we do this by characterizing it as the norm induced by the L^2 -scalar product:

Definition 10. (The L^2 -Norm and scalar product)

We define, on $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$, as well as on each $C^0(\overline{\Omega})^n$, the L^2 -scalar product:

$$\langle f, g \rangle_{L^2} := \int_{\Omega} f \cdot g$$

and for $k \in C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ the symmetric bilinear form:

$$\langle f, g \rangle_k := \int_{\Omega} k(f \cdot g)$$

where in case of $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$, the \cdot is to be understood as multiplication, and in case of $C^0(\overline{\Omega})^n$, it is to be understood as a dot product.

Based on the L^2 scalar product we define the induced L^2 -norm on $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ and each $C^0(\overline{\Omega})^n$ via:

$$|f|_{L^2} := \sqrt{\langle f, f \rangle_{L^2}}$$

Now that we have defined the L^2 -norm, we'll have a look at some quite trivial but quite important fundamental properties of it:

Remark 11. Since the L^2 -norm is induced by the L^2 -scalar product we have

$$|\langle f, g \rangle_{L^2}| \leq |f|_{L^2} |g|_{L^2}$$

and

$$\langle f, f \rangle_{L^2} = \|f\|_{L^2}^2$$

Further, scalar multiplication with functions in $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ is a bounded linear function with respect to the L^2 -norm, that is one has, for $f \in C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ and g either in $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ or in $C^0(\overline{\Omega})^n$:

$$\|fg\|_{L^2} = \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} f^2 |g|^2} \leq \sqrt{\|f\|_{C^0}^2 \int_{\Omega} |g|^2} = \|f\|_{C^0} \|g\|_{L^2}$$

which implies that for $k \in C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ the bilinear form $\langle f, g \rangle_k = \langle f, kg \rangle_{L^2}$ is bounded with respect to the L^2 -norm on $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ and $C^0(\overline{\Omega})^n$, that is one has, writing kg for pointwise scalar multiplication of g with k :

$$|\langle f, g \rangle_k| = \left| \int_{\Omega} k(f \cdot g) \right| = |\langle f, kg \rangle_{L^2}| \leq \|f\|_{L^2} \|kg\|_{L^2} \leq \|k\|_{C^0} \|f\|_{L^2} \|g\|_{L^2}$$

additionally, for $k \in C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ with $k \geq k_0 > 0$, $\langle f, g \rangle_k$ obviously is positive definite and hence a scalar product that is actually coercive with respect to the L^2 -norm, that is one has:

$$\langle f, f \rangle_k = \int_{\Omega} f^2 k \geq \int_{\Omega} f^2 k_0 = k_0 \|f\|_{L^2}^2$$

furthermore, the L^2 -norm can of course be bounded by the C^0 -norm, one has for any $f \in C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ or $C^0(\overline{\Omega})^n$:

$$\|f\|_{L^2} = \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} |f|^2} \leq \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} |f|_{C^0}^2} = \sqrt{\text{Vol}(\Omega)} \|f\|_{C^0}$$

for $\text{Vol}(\Omega) := \int_{\Omega} 1$.

So the C^0 -norm is at least as strong as the L^2 -norm (it actually is stronger), which implies that convergence of a sequence with respect to the C^0 -norm implies convergence with respect to the L^2 -norm, which in turn implies, since we are considering metric spaces, that if $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ is equipped with the C^0 -norm, the induced topology is at least as fine as if it is equipped with the L^2 -norm.

Also, the bilinear forms $\langle *, * \rangle_{L^2}$ and $\langle *, * \rangle_k$ have very good continuity properties:

The estimates $|\langle f, g \rangle_{L^2}| \leq \|f\|_{L^2} \|g\|_{L^2}$ and $|\langle f, g \rangle_k| \leq \|k\|_{C^0} \|f\|_{L^2} \|g\|_{L^2}$ imply that both $\langle *, * \rangle_{L^2}$ and $\langle *, * \rangle_k$ for arbitrary $k \in C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ are so called bounded bilinear forms, with respect to the L^2 -norm on $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ and the normal absolute value on the target space, \mathbb{R} .

Now it is well known that for any vectorspaces V, W the bounded bilinear forms $B : V \times V \rightarrow W; (v, w) \mapsto B(v, w)$ with respect to a norm $\|*\|_V$ on V and a norm $\|*\|_W$ on the target space W are exactly the bilinear forms which are continuous with respect to that norms in the sense that if $f_n \rightarrow f$ and $g_n \rightarrow g$ with respect to $\|*\|_V$, also:

$$B(f_n, g_n) \rightarrow B(f, g)$$

with respect to $\|*\|_W$.

This also has further reaching implications:

We obviously get that if F, G are maps from some metric space X to V , that are at least continuous with respect to the metric induced on V via the $\|*\|_V$ -norm, then the map:

$$B(F, G) : X \rightarrow W; x \mapsto B(F(x), G(x))$$

is continuous with respect to the $|\ast|_W$ -norm, because for any sequence $x_n \rightarrow x$ in X we have that $F(x_n) \rightarrow F(x), G(x_n) \rightarrow G(x)$ in V with respect to $|\ast|_V$, and hence also via the continuity property of B :

$$B(F(x_n), G(x_n)) \rightarrow B(F(x), G(x))$$

with respect to the $|\ast|_W$ -norm.

Actually, this even holds for arbitrary topological spaces X , foreshadowing that $B(\ast, \ast)$ is continuous with respect to the product topology on $V \times V$, but we don't need that perspective, so we will leave it at this observation for metric spaces.

Applying those abstract results, we get the following two concrete findings which we will need later:

Firstly if $f_n \rightarrow f$ and $g_n \rightarrow g$ with respect to $|\ast|_{L^2}$, so especially also if $f_n \rightarrow f$ and $g_n \rightarrow g$ with respect to the stronger norm $|\ast|_{C^0}$, then:

$$\langle f_n, g_n \rangle_{L^2} \rightarrow \langle f, g \rangle_{L^2}$$

and

$$\langle f_n, g_n \rangle_k \rightarrow \langle f, g \rangle_k$$

holds in the usual sense of real convergence.

Secondly, if f, g are some functions from some interval I to $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$ which are at least continuous with respect to the L^2 -norm on $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$, so especially if they are continuous with respect to the stronger C^0 -norm, then:

$$\langle f, g \rangle_{L^2} : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, t \mapsto \langle f(t), g(t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

and

$$\langle f, g \rangle_k : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, t \mapsto \langle f(t), g(t) \rangle_k$$

are continuous functions in the usual sense.

While they are essentially quite trivial, these facts, in combination with the Feynman trick we'll have a look at now and the partial integration we'll see later will be very useful down the line.

The Feynman trick. Now that we have seen the fundamentals for working with the L^2 -norm, we'll have a look at the Feynman trick. The Feynman trick is the core result that allows for computing $\frac{d}{dt}|f(t)|_{L^2}^2$ from f and f_t , given some function $f \in C^{0,1}(\Omega \times [T_1, T_2])$. At its core, it essentially follows from the following results:

Theorem 12. (*continuity of timeslices*)

If $f \in C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, then the time-slice map:

$$[T_1, T_2] \rightarrow C^0(\Omega), t \mapsto f(t)$$

is continuous.

Proof. Since $f \in C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, f is uniformly continuous with some modulus of continuity η , but this also means that for every $t, t \in (T_1, T_2)$, we have that $\forall x \in \Omega : |f(x, t_1) - f(x, t_2)| \leq \eta(|t_1 - t_2|)$, so $|f(t_1) - f(t_2)|_{C^0} \leq \eta(|t_1 - t_2|)$, implying the continuity result.

Theorem 13. (*differentiability of timeslices*)

If $f \in C^{0,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, then:

$$\left(\frac{d}{dt}f\right)(t) := \lim_{h \rightarrow 0, h \neq 0} \frac{f(t+h) - f(t)}{h}$$

exists in $C^0(\overline{\Omega})$, and is equal to $f_t(t)$, for all $t \in (T_1, T_2)$.

Remark. Furthermore, the map $C^0(\overline{\Omega}), (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow C^0(\overline{\Omega}); t \mapsto \left(\frac{d}{dt}f\right)(t) = f_t(t)$ is obviously continuous and continuously extendable to T_1 and T_2 by $f_t(T_1)$ and $f_t(T_2)$, because $\left(\frac{d}{dt}f\right)(t) = f_t(t)$ is essentially just the continuous time slice map defined on $[T_1, T_2]$ from theorem 12 for f_t , restricted to (T_1, T_2) .

Also, one actually could further define $\left(\frac{d}{dt}f\right)(t)$ also at T_1 , where it would essentially be a one-sided derivative, and would then find that it is well-defined and $\left(\frac{d}{dt}f\right)(T_1) = f(T_1)$, however, we don't need that, so we stick with our convention of considering pointwise derivatives on open sets.

Proof idea. By essentially applying the fundamental theorem of calculus, treating t as the variable and x as a fixed parameter, one obtains the representation: $f(x, t) = f(x, t^*) + \int_{t^*}^t f_t(x, t)$, using that f_t is again, as function in $C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, uniformly continuous, and therefore has a modulus of continuity, one can then basically compute $\left(\frac{d}{dt}f\right)(t)$ from the limit definition using this representation.

Theorem 14. (*Feynman Trick for L^2 -norms*)

If $f \in C^{0,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, then $|f(t)|_{L^2}^2$ is differentiable on (T_1, T_2) in the classical sense, with derivative:

$$\frac{d}{dt}|f(t)|_{L^2}^2 = 2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

which is continuously extendable to the compact interval $[T_1, T_2]$, and hence integrable on (T_1, T_2) .

Proof. Firstly, we easily note that we have, for any $f, g \in C^0(\Omega)$, by the basics from remark 11, that: $2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$

is a continuous function on $[T_1, T_2]$, because $t \mapsto f(t)$ and $t \mapsto f_t(t)$ are continuous functions on $[T_1, T_2]$, with respect to the C^0 -norm by theorem 12, since $f, f_t \in C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times [T_1, T_2]})$.

Thus $2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$ restricted only to (T_1, T_2) can clearly be continuously extended to $[T_1, T_2]$ by the continuous function defined by the same expression on $[T_1, T_2]$.

Now considering $2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$ on $[T_1, T_2]$, we easily note that it can be integrated on (T_1, T_2) , because continuous functions can be integrated over compact intervals, so it can be integrated over $[T_1, T_2]$, but then it can obviously also be integrated over the subinterval (T_1, T_2) .

Thus if we can establish that pointwise $\frac{d}{dt}|f(t)|_{L^2}^2 = 2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$ in (T_1, T_2) , the rest of the theorem follows.

For this, we consider an arbitrary $t \in (T_1, T_2)$, and show, via the definition of derivative, that at t , $|f(t)|_{L^2}^2$ is differentiable with derivative $2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$.

That $|f(t)|_{L^2}^2$ is differentiable at t with derivative $2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$ simply means that for any sequence $h_n \rightarrow 0$ such that:

- each h_n is not zero,
- for each h_n the quantity $t + h_n$ is in (T_1, T_2) (which is more of a formal requirement, since when $h_n \rightarrow 0$, $t + h_n \notin (T_1, T_2)$ can only happen finitely often),

the limit:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|f(t + h_n)|_{L^2}^2 - |f(t)|_{L^2}^2}{h_n}$$

exists and takes the value $2\langle f(t), f_t(t) \rangle_{L^2}$.

Now we simply fix an arbitrary sequence $h_n \rightarrow 0$ that fulfills the stated requirements, and compute that:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|f(t+h_n)|_{L^2}^2 - |f(t)|_{L^2}^2}{h_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(t+h_n), f(t+h_n) \rangle_{L^2} - \langle f(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2}}{h_n} \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(t+h_n), f(t+h_n) \rangle_{L^2} - \langle f(t+h_n), f(t) \rangle_{L^2} + \langle f(t+h_n), f(t) \rangle_{L^2} - \langle f(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2}}{h_n} \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(t+h_n), f(t+h_n) - f(t) \rangle_{L^2} + \langle f(t+h_n) - f(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2}}{h_n} \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(t+h_n) - f(t), f(t+h_n) \rangle_{L^2} + \langle f(t+h_n) - f(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2}}{h_n} \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\langle \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t+h_n) \right\rangle_{L^2} + \left\langle \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t) \right\rangle_{L^2}
\end{aligned}$$

Now these transformations were merely due to the definition of $|\cdot|_{L^2}$ and the bilinearity and symmetry of the L^2 scalar product, but because of the continuity of the L^2 -scalar product with respect to the $|\cdot|_{C^0}$ -norm established in remark 11 we can continue:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\langle \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t+h_n) \right\rangle_{L^2} + \left\langle \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t) \right\rangle_{L^2} \\
&= \left\langle \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(t+h_n) \right\rangle_{L^2} + \left\langle \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t) \right\rangle_{L^2}
\end{aligned}$$

where the limits are to be taken with respect to the C^0 -norm.

However we have that:

- Due to theorem 12 $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(t+h_n)$ exists with respect to $|\cdot|_{C^0}$ and is $f(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} t+h_n) = f(t)$, because $t \mapsto f(t)$ is continuous on (T_1, T_2) with respect to $|\cdot|_{C^0}$.
- Due to theorem 13 $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}$ exists and is $f_t(t)$.

So that we finally get:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\langle \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(t+h_n) \right\rangle_{L^2} + \left\langle \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t) \right\rangle_{L^2} \\
&= \langle f_t(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2} + \langle f_t(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2} = 2\langle f_t(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2}
\end{aligned}$$

so that we overall obtain:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|f(t+h_n)|_{L^2}^2 - |f(t)|_{L^2}^2}{h_n} = 2\langle f_t(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

as required.

As usual when computing limits, existence of the initial limit $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|f(t+h_n)|_{L^2}^2 - |f(t)|_{L^2}^2}{h_n}$ follows by reading the computations backwards, that is because $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(t+h_n)$ exist and the L^2 scalar product is continuous, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\langle \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t+h_n) \right\rangle_{L^2} + \left\langle \frac{f(t+h_n) - f(t)}{h_n}, f(t) \right\rangle_{L^2}$ exists, which again implies that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(t+h_n) - f(t), f(t+h_n) \rangle_{L^2} + \langle f(t+h_n) - f(t), f(t) \rangle_{L^2}}{h_n}$$

exists and so on.

6.2.2. *Partial integration.* Thirdly we'll now see the partial integration, which, using the boundary conditions, will basically help us to transform terms like $\langle u(t), (\nabla \cdot (k(\varphi, x)\nabla u))(t) \rangle_{L^2}$ to more "symmetrical" terms like $-\langle \nabla u(t), \nabla u(t) \rangle_{k(\varphi, x)(t)}$, which will be key in the bounding argument.

The core result the partial integration follows from is a particular version of the very well-known Gauß theorem:

Theorem 15. (*Gauß theorem*)

If $F \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})^3$, then:

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot F = \int_{\partial\Omega} F \cdot \vec{n} dH^2$$

where H^2 is the two dimensional Hausdorff measure and \vec{n} is the normal vector field of $\bar{\Omega}$.

This immediately implies the following main partial integration result, tailored to elliptic operators in divergence form:

Corollary 16. (*Partial integration*)

If $f \in C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$ and $g, k \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$, then:

$$\langle \nabla \cdot (k\nabla f), g \rangle_{L^2} = \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot (k\nabla f))g = - \int_{\Omega} k(\nabla f) \cdot (\nabla g) = -\langle \nabla f, \nabla g \rangle_k$$

Remark. Choosing $k = 1$ yields the special case:

$$\langle \Delta f, g \rangle_{L^2} = \int_{\Omega} (\Delta f)g = - \int_{\Omega} (\nabla f) \cdot (\nabla g) = -\langle \nabla f, \nabla g \rangle_{L^2}$$

which we will need too.

Proof. We consider the vectorfield $gk\nabla f$. Since $f \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$ and $g, k \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$, obviously also $gk\nabla f \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$, thus the Gauß theorem can be applied to $gk\nabla f$ and yields:

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (gk\nabla f) = \int_{\partial\Omega} gk(\nabla f) \cdot \vec{n} dH^2 = \int_{\partial\Omega} 0 dH^2 = 0$$

because by definition of $C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$, $f \in C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$ has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, so $\nabla f \cdot \vec{n} = 0$ everywhere on $\partial\Omega$.

However, by the product rule for divergence, we then have:

$$0 = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (gk\nabla f) = \int_{\Omega} (\nabla g) \cdot (k\nabla f) + g\nabla \cdot (k\nabla f) = \left(\int_{\Omega} k(\nabla f) \cdot (\nabla g) \right) + \left(\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot (k\nabla f))g \right)$$

immediately implying:

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot (k\nabla f))g = - \int_{\Omega} k(\nabla f) \cdot (\nabla g)$$

and hence:

$$\langle \nabla \cdot (k\nabla f), g \rangle_{L^2} = \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot (k\nabla f))g = - \int_{\Omega} k(\nabla f) \cdot (\nabla g) = -\langle \nabla f, \nabla g \rangle_k$$

as stated. \square

Now this result relies on Neumann boundary conditions on f , so we'll conclude our quick look at partial integration by giving some good criteria for when composite functions have Neumann boundary conditions.

Obviously, Neumann boundary conditions are linear, so stable under sums and scalar multiplication, however, they are actually even stable under function multiplication, and under additional conditions, even under function inversion:

Lemma 17. (*Stability of Neumann boundary conditions*)

Homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions are stable under product, that is, if $f_1, f_2 \in C_N^j(\bar{\Omega})$ with $j \geq 1$, so they especially have homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, $f_1 f_2 \in C_N^j(\bar{\Omega})$ too, so the product especially has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions too.

Furthermore, if $f \in C_N^j(\bar{\Omega})$ with $j \geq 1$ is pointwise bounded below by some positive number y_{min} , then $f^{-1} \in C_N^j(\bar{\Omega})$ too.

Proof idea. The first claim for products follows from the product rules for higher order partial derivatives, which show that one has sufficiently well behaved partial derivatives of sufficiently high order, as well as from the product rule for gradients, which yields for \vec{n} the normal as usual that $\vec{n} \cdot \nabla(f_1 f_2) = (\vec{n} \cdot \nabla f_1) f_2 + (\vec{n} \cdot \nabla f_2) f_1 = 0$ if both functions have homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions.

The second claim follows by the chain rules for the gradient and higher order partial derivatives, noting that on $\mathbb{R}_{\geq y_{min}}$ for $y_{min} > 0$, $y \mapsto 1/y$ is a smooth diffeomorphism that is bounded and has all its derivatives bounded.

6.3. The toolkit for solving linear parabolic equations and bounding solutions. Now that we have presented the basics for working with the energy method, we continue with presenting the mathematical “tools” we will use to solve linear parabolic equations and bound their solutions. Even though the embedding theorems are more fundamental, we have a look at this toolkit first, simply because some of the corollaries of the embedding theorems are tailored to the parabolic Hölder spaces defined in this section. Concretely, we'll first have a look at parabolic Hölder spaces and the required Schauder theory, and then have a quick look at a key result from maximal regularity theory.

6.3.1. Hölder spaces and some Schauder theory. As we aim to work with strong solutions, we will use so called Schauder theory, which works with parabolic Hölder spaces, which intuitively are something like Hölder spaces where the “regularity”, for $a \in (0, 1)$ for example the Hölder exponent, is half as good for the time direction, accordingly we define, following [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3]:

Definition 18. (H_a for $a \in (0, 1)$ and $a \in (2, 3)$)

For $a \in (0, 1)$ we define:

$$|f|_{H_a} := \sup_{(x,t) \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} |f(x, t)| + \sup_{(x,t), (x',t') \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2), (x,t) \neq (x',t')} \frac{|f(x, t) - f(x', t')|}{\left(\|x - x'\|^2 + \|t - t'\|^2\right)^{a/2}} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \cup \{\infty\}$$

for any $f \in C^0(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, and accordingly:

$$H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) := \{f \in C^0(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) : |f|_{H_a} < \infty\}$$

Additionally, by abuse of notation, we define the regular Hölder spaces:

$$H_a(\Omega) := C^{0+a}(\Omega) := \{f \in C^0(\Omega) : |f|_{C^{0+a}} < \infty\}$$

where:

$$|f|_{C^{0+a}} := \sup_{x \in \Omega} |f(x)| + \sup_{x, x' \in \Omega} \frac{|f(x, t) - f(x', t')|}{|x - x'|^a}$$

and analogously to $C^{0+a}(\Omega)$, but with one spatial dimension more, we define the classical Hölder spaces $C^{0+a}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

For $a \in (2, 3)$ we define:

$$\begin{aligned} |f|_{H_a} := & \left(\sum_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}, i \leq j} |\partial_{x_i} \partial_{x_j} f|_{H_{a-2}} \right) + |\partial_t f|_{H_{a-2}} + \sum_{i \in \{1,2,3\}} \sup_{x \in \Omega, t, t' \in (T_1, T_2)} \frac{|\partial_{x_i} f(x, t) - \partial_{x_i} f(x, t')|}{|t - t'|^{(a-1)/2}} \\ & + \left(\sum_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}, i \leq j} |\partial_{x_i} \partial_{x_j} f|_{C^0} \right) + |\partial_t f|_{C^0} + \left(\sum_{i \in \{1,2,3\}} |\partial_{x_j} f|_{C^0} \right) + |f|_{C^0} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \cup \{\infty\} \end{aligned}$$

for any $f \in C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$, and accordingly:

$$H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) := \{f \in C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)}) : |f|_{H_a} < \infty\}$$

Additionally, by abuse of notation, we again define, also for $a \in (2, 3)$, the regular Hölder spaces:

$$H_a(\Omega) := C^{0+a}(\Omega) := \{f \in C^0(\Omega) : |f|_{C^{0+a}} < \infty\}$$

with:

$$|f|_{H_a} := \left(\sum_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}, i \leq j} |\partial_{x_i} \partial_{x_j} f|_{H_{a-2}} \right) + |\partial_t f|_{H_{a-2}} + \left(\sum_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}, i \leq j} |\partial_{x_i} \partial_{x_j} f|_{C^0} \right) + \left(\sum_{i \in \{1,2,3\}} |\partial_{x_j} f|_{C^0} \right) + |f|_{C^0} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \cup \{\infty\}$$

Remark. Though they are formally expressed a little different, these spaces are exactly the H_a from [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3] with the same norms, and as stated in [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3]2, they correspond to the $H^{a,a/2}$ spaces from [LSU]. Especially, $|f|_{H_a} < \infty$ for $a \in (0, 1)$ implies uniform continuity, because then $\frac{|f(x,t) - f(x',t')|}{\|x-x'\|^2 + |t-t'\|^{a/2}}$ is bounded by some $B \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\|x-x'\|^2 + |x-x'| + |t-t'|^2 + |t-t'\|^{a/2} = \|(x,t) - (x',t')\|^2 + \|(x,t) - (x',t')\|^{a/2}$ is a modulus of continuity for f , so all functions $f \in H_a$ for $a \in (0, 1)$ are automatically uniformly continuous as explicitly required in [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3], and obviously, since on bounded open sets uniform continuity is equivalent to continuous extendability to the closure, the formal additional requirement $f \in C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is equivalent to uniform continuity of all spatial partial derivatives up to second order and the time derivative of f and f itself, as assumed in the definition from [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3], so the formally missing uniform continuity requirement for $f \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $a \in (0, 1)$ is automatically fulfilled, and the formally different requirement $f \in C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ for $f \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $a \in (2, 3)$ is actually equivalent to the uniform continuity requirements for $f \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $a \in (2, 3)$ in [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3]. We chose to define H_a for $a \in (0, 1)$ formally weaker and H_a for $a \in (2, 3)$ essentially formally stronger (but in both cases actually equivalent to the definition in [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3], as explained) because we want to upgrade from H_a for $a \in (0, 1)$ to H_a for $a \in (2, 3)$, so with this definitions, we formally need less assumptions and get more results out, simplifying arguments.

Additionally to the parabolic Hölder spaces, we shall define the normal

Before we continue, we note three important fundamental properties that $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $a \in (2, 3)$ has by definition, which we will regularly explicitly and implicitly need throughout our proofs:

- (1) If $u \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $a \in (2, 3)$, then $u, \nabla u, \Delta u, u_t \in H_{a-2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.
- (2) If $u \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $a \in (2, 3)$, then it automatically is in our solution space $C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$.
- (3) By elementary computation, one can easily show that the C^{0+a} -norm is stronger than the H_a -norm for $a \in (0, 1)$, which we will also use.

Furthermore, since all functions in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $a \in (0, 1)$ are uniformly continuous, we have that all functions in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ can be continuously extended to $\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)}$, and therefore are in $C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$.

Now that we have defined the relevant H_a -spaces and norms from [Lieberman1], [Lieberman2], [Lieberman3], and noted their most important properties, we will state the main theorem, which is a standard result from Schauder theory, for solving heat equations:

Theorem 19. *(A standard result from Schauder theory)*

Given some constants $a \in (0, 1)$, $c \in \mathbb{R}$, some fixed domain $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ with $\overline{\Omega}$ having H_a -boundary, some initial data $u_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, some source term $f \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and some coefficient functions $k \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and $b_i \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $|k|_{H_a} \leq B_{|k|_{H_a}}$ and $|b_i|_{H_a} \leq B_{|b_i|_{H_a}}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $k \geq \lambda_{min}$ pointwise, for some bounds $B_{|k|_{H_a}}$, λ_{min} and $B_{|b_i|_{H_a}}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, there is a unique solution $u \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) \subseteq C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ that classically solves $u_t = k\Delta u + \vec{b} \cdot \nabla u + f$ on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ such that $u(T_1) = u_0$ and u has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, and:

$$|u|_{H_{a+2}} \leq C(|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}} + |f|_{H_a})$$

where C depends only on $\Omega, T_1, T_2, \lambda_{min}, B_{|k|_{H_a}}$ and the $B_{|b_i|_{H_a}}$.

Proof. The existence of an unique solution claimed in this theorem is Theorem 5.3 from chapter IV § 5 Basic results on solvability from [LSU], since the H_a spaces of [Lieberman1] and [Lieberman2] correspond to the $H^{a,a/2}$ -spaces from [LSU], as stated in [Lieberman2].

The boundedness result is almost a special case of [Lieberman1], which since $\overline{\Omega}$ is compact and C^3 so its normal vector field is even C^3 on the compact $\partial\Omega$, for our homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions yields such a boundedness result of the form:

$$|u|_{H_{a+2}} \leq C(|u|_{C^0} + |u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}} + |f|_{H_a})$$

with the constant depending on $\Omega, T_1, T_2, \lambda_{min}, B_{|k|_{H_a}}$ and the $B_{|b_i|_{H_a}}$ (the dependence on the maximum of k is accounted for via $B_{|k|_{H_a}}$)

Now because the $|u|_{C^0}$, this is not quite the required result yet, but bounding $|u|_{C^0}$ by:

$$|u|_{C^0} \leq \tilde{C}(|u_{T_1}|_{C^0} + |f|_{C^0})$$

with some constant \tilde{C} only depending on $T_2 - T_1$, which we will now show by a standard maximum principle argument. and plugging that in for $|u|_{C^0}$ and realizing that $|u_{T_1}|_{C^0} \leq |u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|f|_{C^0} \leq |f|_{H_a}$ by the definitions of these norms, we get the required bounding result.

So now we only have to show

$$|u|_{C^0} \leq \tilde{C}(|u_{T_1}|_{C^0} + |f|_{C^0})$$

by a standard maximum principle argument.

for that, we consider $v(x, t) := u(x, t) + |u_{T_1}|_{C^0} + (t - T_1)|f|_{C^0}$, this obviously fulfills:

$$v_t - \left(k\Delta v + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i \cdot (\nabla v)_i \right) = |f|_{C^0} + f \geq 0$$

Also, we obviously have:

$$v(T_1) = u_{T_1} + |u_{T_1}|_{C^0} \geq 0$$

Now we want to show that indeed $v \geq 0$, because then $u(x, t) \leq |u_{T_1}|_{C^0} + (t - T_1)|f|_{C^0}$, implying:

$$\max_{x \in \Omega, t \in (T_1, T_2)} u(x, t) \leq (T_2 - T_1)|f|_{C^0} + |u_{T_1}|_{C^0} \leq \max(T_2 - T_1, 1)(|f|_{C^0} + |u_{T_1}|_{C^0})$$

For this we do a standard perturbation argument. First we fix a function $d \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$ (“boundary distance”) with for the continuous extension ∇d of the classical gradient $\nabla d \cdot \vec{n} \leq -1$ on $\partial\Omega$, where \vec{n} is the outwards unit normal (it is well known that such functions exist for our compact $\bar{\Omega}$ with C^3 -boundary).

For $\epsilon, \delta > 0$ we then define the perturbed function:

$$v^{\epsilon, \delta}(x, t) := v(x, t) + \delta t + \delta - \epsilon d$$

We easily see that, because $d \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$:

$$v_t^{\epsilon, \delta} - \left(k\Delta v^{\epsilon, \delta} + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i \cdot (\nabla v^{\epsilon, \delta})_i \right) \geq \delta - c_1 \epsilon$$

for $c_1 = 3|k|_{C^0}|d|_{C^2}$ independent of ϵ, δ .

Furthermore, we easily see that, because $d \in C^0(\bar{\Omega})$:

$$v^{\epsilon, \delta}(T_1) \geq \delta - |d|_{C^0} \epsilon$$

Therefore, we can obviously find sequences $\epsilon_n, \delta_n \rightarrow 0$ with:

- $v_t^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n} - \left(k\Delta v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n} + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i \cdot (\nabla v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n})_i \right) \geq \delta_n - c_1 \epsilon_n > \delta_n/2 > 0$
- $v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n}(T_1) \geq \delta_n - |d|_{C^0} \epsilon_n > \delta_n/2 > 0$

Now for the perturbed v^{ϵ_n, δ_n} , we can indeed show that they have to be ≥ 0 , by contradiction:

Let us assume that any of them is < 0 somewhere, then, as function in $C^{2,1}(\bar{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$ (in which they are contained because u is even in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$), the unique continuous extension of that v^{ϵ_n, δ_n} to $\bar{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)$ must attain its negative finite minimum at some point (x^*, t^*) on $\bar{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)$.

Now because $v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n}(T_1) \geq \delta_n - |d|_{C^0} \epsilon_n \geq 0$, (x^*, t^*) , it cannot be in $\bar{\Omega} \times \{T_1\}$.

Furthermore, because of the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, for all $t \in (T_1, T_2)$:

$$\vec{n} \cdot \nabla v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n}(t) = -\epsilon_n \vec{n} \cdot \nabla d > 0$$

where ∇d is the continuous extension of the classical gradient, and \vec{n} is the outwards normal vector.

But this condition is well-known to, for bounded C^1 -domains, imply that the minimum of the continuous extension of the respective function, here $v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n}(t)$, cannot lie on $\partial\Omega$, and hence, the minimum of the continuous extension of v^{ϵ_n, δ_n} then cannot lie on $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ either.

But then we have that, even though:

$$v_t^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n} - \left(k\Delta v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n} + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i \cdot (\nabla v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n})_i \right) \geq \delta_n - c_1 \epsilon_n > \delta_n/2 > 0$$

the minimum of $v_t^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n}$ does not lie on the parabolic boundary, a contradiction to the weak maximum principle applied to $-v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n}$, found for example in [?] as theorem 8 in section 7.1.4.

So we now have that all v^{ϵ_n, δ_n} are ≥ 0 , but then also v , which obviously is their uniform limit since $\epsilon_n, \delta_n \rightarrow 0$, has to be ≥ 0 .

for $t := T_2$, which is well-known to imply that the maximum of the respective function, in this case $v^{\epsilon_n, \delta_n}(T_2)$, cannot be on $\partial\Omega$.

Arguing analogously for $-u$ by basically repeating the exactly same process for $\tilde{u} := -u$ which fulfills an analogous PDE with initial condition $-u_{T_1}$ and source term $-f$ then yields also:

$$\max_{x \in \Omega, t \in (T_1, T_2)} -u(x, t) \leq (T_2 - T_1)|f|_{C^0} + |u_{T_1}|_{C^0} \leq \max(T_2 - T_1, 1)(|f|_{C^0} + |u_{T_1}|_{C^0})$$

Yielding the desired bound:

$$|u|_{C^0} \leq \tilde{C}(|u_{T_1}|_{C^0} + |f|_{C^0})$$

for $\tilde{C} := \max(T_2 - T_1, 1)$ only depending on $T_2 - T_1$, concluding the proof, since this bound was the last element that remained to be shown.

Now this initially only yields bounds on the solution found, but not whether this solution continuously depends on the various functions involved.

If the solution operator was linear in all considered variables, we would automatically get that the boundedness result implies a continuity result, because of the fundamental result that linear maps that map all bounded sets to bounded sets are continuous.

Now the solution operator isn't simply a linear operator, because the coefficients are variable too, so applying this fundamental property is not possible.

However, via a clever computation, in spirit somewhat similar to the computations for showing that boundedness implies continuity for linear operators, we actually get a similar theorem for systems with "variable coefficients" as well, Kais free lunch theorem, which can be found with proof in the appendix.

And just like the theorem for linear functions, it requires very little structure of the system, for example it doesn't use completeness of the respective vectorspaces at all, and also allows for most of the involved operations being discontinuous.

Via this theorem, the boundedness results then yield the following continuity result:

Corollary 20. *The solution u from theorem 19 actually is always unique and depends continuously on u_0, k , the b_i , and f in the sense that if for some arbitrary fixed $a \in (0, 1)$:*

- u_0^n is a convergent sequence in $H_{a+2}(\Omega)$ with respect to the H_{a+2} -norm, with limit u_0^{lim} .
- k_n is a convergent sequence in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with respect to the H_a -norm, with limit k_{lim} .
- $b_{n,i}$ is a convergent sequence in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with respect to the H_a -norm, with limit $b_{lim,i}$, for each $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

one also has that, defining u_n to be the solution u from theorem 19 for $u_0 := u_0^n, k := k_n, b_i := b_{n,i}, f := f_n$, and u_{lim} to be the solution u from theorem 19 for $u_0 := u_0^{lim}, k := k_{lim}, b_i := b_{lim,i}, f := f_{lim}$:

$$u_n \rightarrow u_{lim}$$

in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

Proof sketch. We want to apply Kais free lunch theorem. For this, we fix everything but the coefficient and source functions, and firstly notice that the H_{a+2} -bound on the solution u automatically yields H_a -bounds on Δu and the $(\nabla u)_i = \partial_i u$ for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

But then, setting:

- $V := H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$
- $I := \{0\}, J_1 := \{0, 1, 2, 3\}, \tilde{I} := \{0\}$
- $L_{0,0} := \Delta, L_{0,1} := \partial_1, L_{0,2} := \partial_2, L_{0,3} := \partial_3$ as differential operators in the classical sense.
- $V_{0,0}, V_{0,1}, V_{0,2}, V_{0,3} := H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$
- $W_0 := H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$
- $W_{0,0}^c := \{k \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) : \exists k_{min} > 0 : k(x, t) > k_{min} \forall (x, t) \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)\}$
- $W_{0,1}^c, W_{0,2}^c, W_{0,3}^c := H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$
- $*_{0,0}, *_{0,1}, *_{0,2}, *_{0,3} :=$ pointwise multiplication, which we know is continuous and hence as continuous bilinear form bounded on $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) \times H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$

- $\tilde{V}_0 := \{f \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) : f(T_1) \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)\}$ (which actually is $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, but we don't even need that, a priori it could be any proper subspace)
- $\tilde{W}_0 := H_{a+2}(\Omega)$
- $\tilde{L}_0 := (\tilde{V}_1 \rightarrow \tilde{W}_1; f \mapsto f(T_1))$

and taking the respective bounds from the theorem with a “global” bound B_{data} plugged in for every bounding variable (except the fixed ones of course) to be the bound functions b and $b_{i,j}$, we can then apply the free lunch theorem to obtain, among other results, the uniqueness and the continuity result stated.

Now as we'll see later, we'll need a second boundedness result too for the bounding, concretely, we'll need the following smoothing result, that will allow us to obtain solutions in parabolic Hölder spaces for source terms in L^p for sufficiently large p :

Theorem 21. *(A smoothing result for sufficiently regular coefficients)*

Given some constants $a, b \in (0, 1)$, $c \in \mathbb{R}$, some fixed domain $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ with $\bar{\Omega}$ having H_{a+2} -boundary, some initial data $u_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, some source term $f \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and some coefficient functions $k \in C^1(\bar{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)) \subseteq H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and $b_i \in H_a(\bar{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$ for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $\forall(x, t) \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) : k(x, t) \geq k_{min} > 0$ pointwise, and $u \in C^{2,1}(\bar{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$ a classical solution to:

$$u_t = \nabla \cdot (k(x, t)\nabla u) + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i \cdot (\nabla u)_i + f$$

with initial data $u_0 \in C_a(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$, that is, $u(T_1) = 0$, and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, that is $u(t) \in C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$, for all $t \in [T_1, T_2]$, then there is a function $p_0(a, \Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ so that for $p \geq p_0(a, \Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ (so p_0 depends only on a and $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$), especially p large enough so $(n+2)/q - (n+2a) > 0$ for q the Hölder conjugate (that is, the q with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$), one can bound $|u|_{H_b}$ by some bound $B \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ depending only on $\Omega, T_1, T_2, a, p, k_{min}$ and upper bounds on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}, |k|_{H_a}$ the $|b_i|_{H_a}$ and $|f|_{L^p}$.

This result can be derived from theorem 1.1 from [Lieberman4], in conjunction with the generalization sketched by Lieberman on page 95 (page 19 if one only counts the pages of Liebermans article).

Similarly to the proof of theorem 19, we will need to bound the maximum of the solution, and indeed this can be done, however, the proof for this, unlike in the case of theorem 19, is far too long for the scope of this thesis, so it will only be sketched, so we can only provide a proof sketch for the theorem:

Proof sketch. Without loss of generality, we can assume $T_1 = 0$, since we can always translate the whole system. We essentially applies theorem 1.1 in conjunction with the generalization sketched by Lieberman on page 95 (page 19 if one only counts the pages of Liebermans article) from [Lieberman4], setting (almost in Liebermans notation, using x, t instead of $X := (x, t)$):

- $\beta := a$
- $A(x, t, u, Du) := k(x, t)Du$
- $B(x, t, u, Du) := \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i \cdot (\nabla u)_i + f$
- $\gamma := \bar{n}$ the normal vectorfield of the mantle
- $\psi := 0$

One then quickly sees that the system considered in Liebermann then becomes exactly a weak form (in the sense that he bounds even weak solutions) of the system considered, especially the conormal boundary conditions then become (considering as always continuous extensions) $k(x, t)\nabla u \cdot \bar{n} = 0$, which is obviously, because $\forall(x, t) \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) : k(x, t) \geq k_{min} > 0$, so the continuous extension of k cannot vanish on the boundary, equivalent to our Neumann boundary conditions.

So in order to apply theorem 1.1, we only have to show that the various bound variables assumed in theorem 1.1 in terms of which the resulting bound is given can be bounded in terms of the bounds we have given (and that the bounding variable independent precondition (1.6) is fulfilled).

We easily see that (again almost in Liebermans notation, again using x, t instead of $X := (x, t)$, and u_0 instead of φ for the initial data):

- $|A(x, t, z, 0)| = |k(x, z)0| = 0$, so we can choose $\mu_1 := 0$ for (1.2a).
- $|A(x, t, z, p) - A(y, t, w, p)| = |(k(x, t) - k(y, t))p| \leq |k|_{H_a} |x - y|^a |p| \leq |k|_{H_a} (1 + |p|) |x - y|^a$ so for (1.2b), $\mu_2 := |k|_{H_a}$ works.
- We obviously cannot work with (1.3c), but this condition can be replaced using that generalization Lieberman sketches later on, as we'll see.
- $|A(x, t, z, p) - A(x, s, w, p)| = |(k(x, t) - k(x, s))p| \leq |k|_{H_a} |t - s|^{a/2} |p| \leq |k|_{H_a} (1 + |p|) |x - y|^{a/2}$ so for (1.3), $\mu_2 := |k|_{H_a}$ works.
- (1.4) is trivially fulfilled, since $\psi = 0$.
- The matrix a_{ij} from (1.5) is obviously $k(x, t) \cdot Id$, so that $\forall (x, t) \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) : k(x, t) \geq k_{min} > 0$ and $|k|_{C^0} \leq |k|_{H_a}$ directly implies that (1.5) can be fulfilled with $\lambda := k_{min}$, $\Lambda := |k|_{H_a}$.
- $A(x, 0, u_0(x), Du_0(x)) \cdot \gamma + \psi(x, 0, u_0(x)) = k(x, 0) \nabla u_0(x) \cdot \vec{n}(x) + 0 = 0$ because of the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions of u_0 , so (1.6) holds

Moreover, we have that, by that generalization of the theorem Lieberman sketches on page 95 (19 if one only counts pages from his article), for our B , we can replace (1.3c) by (again in Liebermans notation, except for writing the domain as $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$):

- $|B(x, t, z, p)| \leq b(x, t) + \mu_3 p^2$
- $\int_{Q_R \cap \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} b(x, t)^2 \leq R^{n+2a}$ for all those cylinders Q_R from the paper

which holds for $b(x, t) := |f(x, t)| + 10 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right)$ and some μ_3 depending only on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, p and bounds on $\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0}$, $|f|_{L^p(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$, provided as assumed in the theorem, $(n + 2)/q - (n + 2a) > 0$ for q the conjugated index to $p/2$ (that is $\frac{1}{p/2} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$), as we'll see now by essentially constructing such a bound μ_3 :

For the first inequality, we simply ensure $\mu_3 \geq 10 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right)$ which we can do since μ_3 is allowed to depend on a bound on $\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0}$, so we can bound:

$$\begin{aligned} |B(x, t, z, p)| &= \left| \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i(x, t) \cdot p_i + f(x, t) \right| \leq 10 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right) |p| + |f(x, t)| \\ &\leq 10 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right) |p| \left(|p| + \frac{1}{|p|} \right) + |f(x, t)| \end{aligned}$$

since $|p| + \frac{1}{|p|} \geq 1$,

$$\leq 10 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right) |p|^2 + 10 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right) + |f(x, t)| \leq \mu_3 |p|^2 + b(x, t)$$

so the first inequality then holds.

For showing that by choosing the μ_3 suitably (but of course still only dependent on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, p and bounds on $\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0}$, $|f|_{L^p(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$) we can also ensure that the second inequality holds, for all the cylinders Q_R , we notice that it is equivalent to:

$$R^{-(n+2a)} \int_{Q_R \cap \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} b(x, t)^2 \leq \mu_3$$

so we start by bounding:

$$\begin{aligned}
R^{-(n+2a)} \int_{Q_R \cap \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} b(x, t)^2 &= \int_{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r} b(x, t)^2 = \langle R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r}, b(x, t)^2 \rangle_{L^2(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))} \\
&\leq |R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r}|_{L^q(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))} |b(x, t)^2|_{L^{p/2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}
\end{aligned}$$

via the Hölder inequality, where q is Hölder conjugated to $p/2$.

Now we want to show that $|R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r}|_{L^q(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$ can be bounded independently of R .

We have that, since $\int_{Q_r} 1 = cR^{n+2}$ for some constant c (since the cylinder radius is proportional to R and the length is proportional to R^2):

$$\begin{aligned}
|R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r}|_{L^q} &= R^{-(n+2a)} \int_{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r} \\
&\leq R^{-(n+2a)} \int_{Q_r} 1 \leq R^{-(n+2a)} (cR^{n+2})^{1/q} = c^{1/q} R^{(n+2)/q - (n+2a)}
\end{aligned}$$

And also obviously for $R \geq 1$, $|R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r}|_{L^q}$ can be bounded by $\int_{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} 1$.

Thus we see that since $(n+2)/q - (n+2a) > 0$ for q the Hölder conjugate to $p/2$, as we assumed in the theorem, the quantity $|R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r}|_{L^q}$ (with q still the Hölder conjugate of p , so determined by p) can be bounded independently of R , only dependent on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ and p , by the bound $\max\left(\int_{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} 1, c^q\right)$, because it can be bounded by $\int_{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} 1$ for $R \geq 1$, and by $c^q \geq c^q R^{(n+2)/q - (n+2a)}$ for $R \in [0, 1]$ (because $(n+2)/q - (n+2a) > 0$).

But since also:

$$\begin{aligned}
|b(x, t)^2|_{L^p} &\leq c_2 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right)^2 + 20 \left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right) |f|_{L^{p/2}} + |f|_{L^p}^2 \\
&\leq c_3 \left(\left(\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0} \right) + |f|_{L^p} \right)^2
\end{aligned}$$

for some constants c_2, c_3 depending only on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, we then have that the whole expression on the right hand side of:

$$R^{-(n+2a)} \int_{Q_R \cap \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} b(x, t)^2 \leq |R^{-(n+2a)} 1_{(x,t) \in Q_r}|_{L^q(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))} |b(x, t)^2|_{L^{p/2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$$

can be bounded by some bound that only depends on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, p and bounds on $\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0}$, $|f|_{L^p(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$, but not on R , and we can simply ensure that μ_3 is larger than that bound too, because μ_3 was allowed to depend on all these quantities.

But then we now also have that the more general replacement condition for condition (1.2c) can be fulfilled, with the bounding variable μ_3 depending only on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, p and bounds on $\max_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} |b_i|_{C^0}$, $|f|_{L^p(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$.

But then we now can apply the theorem with the selected values for the μ_i , which only depend on $\Omega, T_1, T_2, a, p, k_{min}$ and upper bounds on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$, $|k|_{H_a}$ the $|b_i|_{H_a}$ and $|f|_{L^p}$, obtaining a bound:

$$|u|_{H_{1+\delta}} \leq \tilde{B}(\lambda, \Lambda, |u|_{C^0}, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, |u_0|_{H_{1+\delta}}, \Omega, T_1, T_2)$$

for some $\delta \in (0, 1)$ and therefore, as one can compute from the definitions that $|u_0|_{1+\delta} \leq c_4 |u_0|_{a+2}$ for some constant c_4 that depends on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, but not on δ :

$$|u|_{H_{1+\delta}} \leq \tilde{B}(\lambda, \Lambda, |u|_{C^0}, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, |u_0|_{H_{2+a}}, \Omega, T_1, T_2)$$

but then also, via choosing $\lambda, \Lambda, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3$ in terms of $\Omega, T_1, T_2, a, p, k_{min}$ and B_{data} some upper bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}, |k|_{H_a}$ the $|b_i|_{H_a}$ and $|f|_{L^p}$, which is possible as we have seen:

$$|u|_{H_{1+\delta}} \leq \tilde{B}_2(|u|_{C^0}, |u_0|_{H_{2+a}}, \Omega, T_1, T_2, a, p, k_{min}, B_{data})$$

Now two issues remain. Firstly, the bound depends on $|u_0|_{2+a}, |u_0|_0$, not only on a bound on it, which is problematic since there is no way to, in general, transform a bound that depends on a quantity to a bound that depends on a bound on that quantity.

However, going through the proofs, especially also through the proof in [Lieberman4] (which cannot be avoided at this point), one has that one can basically reason the same way working with bounds on these norms instead of the norms themselves, obtaining that one has a bound:

$$|u|_{H_{1+\delta}} \leq \tilde{B}_2(B_{|u|_{C^0}}, \Omega, T_1, T_2, a, p, k_{min}, B_{data})$$

where $B_{|u|_{C^0}}$ is a bound on $|u|_{C^0}$, which leads us to the second issue, that we still have that dependence on $B_{|u|_{C^0}}$.

Now if we can bound $B_{|u|_{C^0}}$ in terms of the other quantities, that completes the proof ($C|u|_{H_{1+\delta}}$ for a suitable constant C can be checked to bound $|u_0|_{H_a}$ for a suitable constant C depending possibly on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ and a , but not on δ , by considering the definition from [Lieberman4]), and indeed one can bound $B_{|u|_{C^0}}$ in terms of the other quantities here, the proof is however, even though it works via a quite intuitive standard argument, if done properly, very long and technical, so we can only very roughly sketch the core idea here:

The idea is to take theorems that bound $|u|$ at a positive distance to the boundary, like theorem 8.1 from §8 local estimates of $\max |u|$ in chapter III linear equations with discontinuous coefficients of [LSU], use them to bound some compactly contained interior set of $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, and then use them in conjunction with a boundary flattening argument and mirroring argument to bound $\max |u|$ on cylinders intersecting with the boundary.

The idea of the boundary flattening and mirroring argument, which is standard, see for example [Lieberman1] is to, for sufficiently small cylinders intersecting with the boundary that are small enough so that the boundary is already quite flat on that scale, flatten the boundary with a diffeomorphism, perturbing the solutions slightly, and to then mirror the solution along the flattened boundary, “gluing” the solution and the mirrored version together along the flattened boundary, obtaining a solution for the joint system.

This then lets a portion of the flattened boundary become interior, so that the “local” bound on $|u|$ can be applied there, bounding $\max |u|$ on an even smaller cylinder that intersects with the boundary.

Now if one chooses those cylinders and the interior set cleverly, one can make sure that $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ is completely covered by those smaller boundary intersecting cylinders and the interior set, so that the bounds on those sets yield bounds on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$.

Basically this way one can then obtain a suitable bound on $B_{|u|_{C^0}}$, which then concludes the proof.

Applying the previous theorem to the standard heat equation (using that C^0 -norms bound L^p -norms on domains of finite volume), we get:

Corollary 22. (*Hölder bounds for heat equation solutions with bounded source term*)

If $u \in C_N^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a classical solution to $u_t = \lambda \Delta u + f$ for some $f \in C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ with initial data $u_0 \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$ for $a \in (0, 1)$, and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, then for every $b \in (0, 1)$, one can bound $|u|_{H_b}$ by some bound B depending only on $\Omega, T_2 - T_1, \lambda, a, b$ and bounds on $|f|_{C^0}$ and $|u_0|_{H_a}$.

Finally, for the sake of completeness, we have a look at a more basic result concerning parabolic Hölder spaces that we need.

For obtaining H_a -regularity for compositions like $g(u, \varphi, x)$, we have the following result:

Lemma 23. *If for $a \in (0, 1)$ we have that $f_1, \dots, f_m \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and $g : \mathbb{R}^n \times \Omega$ is Lipschitz on bounded subsets of its domain, which we'll also refer to as Lipschitz on bounded subset, then $g(f_1, \dots, f_m, x) : \Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}; (x, t) \mapsto g(f_1(x, t), \dots, f_m(x, t), x)$ is in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with:*

$$|g(f_1, \dots, f_m, x)|_{H_a} \leq B$$

for some B depending on $a, \Omega, T_2 - T_1, |f_1|_{H_a}, \dots, |f_m|_{H_a}$

furthermore, if f_1^n, \dots, f_m^n are convergent sequences in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with limits $f_1^{lim}, \dots, f_m^{lim}$, then:

$$g(f_1^n, \dots, f_m^n, x) \rightarrow g(f_1^{lim}, \dots, f_m^{lim}, x)$$

in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

If additionally g is globally Lipschitz with a Lipschitz constant bounded by some upper bound $B_g^{(1)} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, we have that:

$$|g(f_1, \dots, f_m, x)|_{H_a} \leq C(|f_1|_{H_a} + \dots + |f_m|_{H_a}) + B_0$$

for some $C, B_0 \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ depending on $\Omega, T_2 - T_1, B_{c_g}, n$ but not on the f_i or any of their norms.

Remark. An important example of a function g we will very often apply this lemma to is multiplication, which obviously is Lipschitz on bounded subsets of \mathbb{R}^2 .

Proof idea. For Lipschitz functions this is simply proven by verifying the required Hölder bounds computationally using the Lipschitz bounds. For functions that are Lipschitz on bounded subsets one uses that the H_a -norm is stronger than the C^0 -norm, so one gets the results by using the Lipschitzness on the relevant bounded sets, which are determined by the bounds on the input functions that arise from their H_a -norms.

6.3.2. *Some maximal regularity theory.* Additionally to the results from Schauder theory, we will need at least L^p -bounds on φ_t , “before” we have Hölder bounds on $g(u, \varphi, x)$. For this, we will use a result from so-called maximal regularity theory.

First, we define the L^p -norm, which will be needed in order to state the maximal regularity result used:

Definition 24. (L^p -norm)

Generalizing the L^2 -norm, for $p \in [1, \infty)$ one can define the L^p -norm of a function f in $C^0(\overline{D})$ or $C^0(D)^m$ for some bounded domain $D \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ as:

$$|f|_{L^p} := \left(\int_D |f|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

where the modulus is either the absolute value or the euclidean norm on \mathbb{R}^m .

Theorem 25. (*maximal regularity for $\lambda\Delta$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions*)

If $u \in C_N^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a classical solution to $u_t = \lambda\Delta u + f$ for some $f \in C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ with initial data 0, that is, $u(T_1) = 0$, and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, then for every $p \in [1, \infty)$, one can bound $|u_t|_{L^p}$ by some bound B depending only on $\Omega, T_2 - T_1$ and a bound on $|f|_{C^0}$.

Source. This is a well-known result from maximal regularity that is for example found, albeit formulated somewhat differently in a much more general setting, in [?], as theorem 1.11 in conjunction with example 1.13(c).

Corollary 26. *(maximal regularity with initial data)*

If $u \in C_N^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a classical solution to $u_t = \lambda \Delta u + f$ for some $f \in C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ with initial data $u_0 \in C_a(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$ for $a \in (2, 3)$, and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions then for every $p \in [1, \infty)$, one can bound $|u_t|_{L^p}$ by some bound B depending only on $\Omega, T_1, T_2, \lambda, a, p$ and upper bounds on $|u_0|_{H_a}$ and $|f|_{C^0}$.

Proof. This essentially follows by writing u as the sum of a solution u_{u_0} with zero source term and the given initial data and a solution u_f with 0 initial data and the given source term, and applying the theorem theorem 19 to the solution with zero source term, while applying theorem 25 to the solution with zero initial data.

Concretely we have that if $u \in C_N^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a classical solution to $u_t = \lambda \Delta u + f$ for some $f \in C^{0,0}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ with initial data $u_0 \in C_a(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$ and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, subtracting the solution $u_{u_0} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ to $u_t = \lambda \Delta u$ with initial data $u_0 \in C_a(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$ and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions from u , which we know exists by theorem 19 yields a function:

$$u_f := u - u_{u_0} \in C_N^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$$

which solves $u_t = \lambda \Delta u + f$ with initial data 0 and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions.

But we have that $|u_{u_0}|_{H_{a+2}}$ so especially also $|(u_{u_0})_t|_{C^0}$ can be bounded in terms of $\Omega, T_1, T_2, \lambda, a, p$ and an upper bound on $|u_0|_{H_a}$ via theorem 19 .

Also, we have that $|(u_f)_t|_{L^p}$ can be bounded in terms of $\Omega, T_1, T_2, \lambda, a, p$ and an upper bound on $|f|_{C^0}$ via theorem 25 . \square

6.4. Embedding theorems and norm interpolation theorems. Now that we have seen Hölder spaces and parabolic Hölder spaces, we have a look at the embedding and norm interpolation theorems, which essentially allow to bound some norms in terms of other norms. These will, among other things, allow us to formulate a corollary that will allow us to essentially upgrade a very weak well-posedness result to a well-posedness result in parabolic Hölder spaces, which we will then further upgrade, essentially via corollary 20 , obtaining an even stronger well-posedness result.

First we have a look at the norm interpolation theorem which will essentially be the core of our theorem for upgrading the well-posedness:

Theorem 27. *(Brezis-Mironescu)*

Let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded Lipschitz domain. Let $p, p_1 \in [1, \infty]$, $p_2 \in (1, \infty]$, $s, s_1, s_2 \in [0, \infty)$ and $\theta \in (0, 1)$ such that:

- (1) $s_1 \leq s_2$
- (2) $s = \theta s_1 + (1 - \theta) s_2$
- (3) $\frac{1}{p} = \frac{\theta}{p_1} + \frac{1-\theta}{p_2}$

Then for all $u \in W^{s_1, p_1}(U) \cap W^{s_2, p_2}(U)$ one has $u \in W^{s, p}(U)$ with:

$$|u|_{W^{s, p}(U)} = c |u|_{W^{s_1, p_1}(U)}^\theta \cdot |u|_{W^{s_2, p_2}(U)}^{1-\theta}$$

for some constant c independent of u .

Now since this theorem yields bounds in $W^{s, p}$ -norms, we cannot directly use it to upgrade our well-posedness to a well-posedness in Hölder spaces. However, the following embedding theorem will allow us to convert the $W^{s, p}$ -bounds into Hölder bounds which then can easily be converted to parabolic Hölder bounds for weaker parabolic hölder norms:

Theorem 28. *($W^{s, p}(\Omega)$ -to- $H^{0+\alpha}(\Omega)$ -Sobolev-embedding, relevant case) (<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1104.4345>, Thm. 8.2)*

Let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded Lipschitz domain. If f is a continuous function with $u \in W^{s,p}(\Omega)$ for $s \in (0, 1)$, $p \in [1, \infty)$, with $sp > n$, then for $\alpha \leq (sp - n)/p$ one has that $f \in C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ with:

$$|u|_{C^{0+\alpha}(\Omega)} \leq c_\alpha |u|_{W^{s,p}(\Omega)}$$

for some constant c_α dependent on among other things α but independent of u .

Remark. The result from the literature is actually somewhat stronger, even if u is discontinuous, it guarantees the existence of a continuous \tilde{u} that is equal to u Lebesgue almost everywhere such that $|\tilde{u}|_{C^{0+\alpha}(\Omega)} \leq c|\tilde{u}|_{W^{s,p}(\Omega)}$. However, we are working with continuous functions, so we opt for the simpler and less powerful formulation because it fits smoother into our arguments.

Another detail is that we formally strengthened the result from the literature here, in order to make it fit smoother into our arguments again. Formally, this result is somewhat stronger than the result from the literature, since it requires only $\alpha \leq (sp - n)/p$, not $\alpha = (sp - n)/p$, but this formal extension trivially follows by noting that for $\alpha_1 \leq \alpha_2$, $C^{0+\alpha_1}(U) \subseteq C^{0+\alpha_2}(U)$ with $\forall f \in C^{0+\alpha_2}(U) : |f|_{C^{0+\alpha_1}} \leq |f|_{C^{0+\alpha_2}}$.

Now that we have seen the norm interpolation result and the embedding theorem required we continue to formulate and prove the corollary for upgrading a very weak well-posedness result to a well-posedness result in parabolic Hölder spaces:

Corollary 29. (*upgrading L^1 convergence for Lipschitz functions*)

Let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded Lipschitz domain, and $f_n : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ be Lipschitz continuous functions, with their Lipschitz constants bounded by some bound B . Then convergence of the f_n to some continuous function f with respect to the L^1 -norm implies convergence of the f_n , which are easily seen to be in $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$, to the same f (which then especially is in $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$) with respect to the C^α -norm, for every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, and hence the f_n are also in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and converge to f (which then especially is also in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$) with respect to the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ -norm for every $a \in (0, 1)$ if $U = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$.

Proof. The core of the argument is theorem 27 .

We note that because the f_n converge in L^1 , they actually have bounded L^1 -norms. But then their Lipschitz constants and L^1 -norms are bounded, which immediately implies that their $W^{1,\infty}$ -norms are bounded by some $B \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, and so the $W^{1,\infty}$ -norms of their differences are bounded by $2B$ too.

Now via theorem 27 we get that for functions g bounded with respect to the $W^{1,\infty}$ -norm, if their L^1 -norms go to zero, other $W^{s,p}$ -norms go to zero as well, essentially via the inequality: \square

$$|f|_{W^{s,p}(U)} = c|f|_{W^{s_1,p_1}(U)}^\theta \cdot |f|_{W^{s_2,p_2}(U)}^{1-\theta}$$

More concretely, we obviously choose $s_1 := 0, p_1 := 1, s_2 := 1, p_2 := \infty$, and further choose, for given $\theta \in (0, 1)$:

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \quad & s = \theta s_1 + (1 - \theta) s_2 = 1 - \theta \\ (2) \quad & \frac{1}{p} = \frac{\theta}{p_1} + \frac{1-\theta}{p_2} = \theta, \text{ so } p = \frac{1}{\theta} \end{aligned}$$

apply Brezis Mironescu, and get that $g \in W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)$ with:

$$|g|_{W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)} = C|g|_{W^{0,1}(U)}^\theta \cdot |g|_{W^{1,\infty}(U)}^{1-\theta}$$

where C is independent of the g in question, so especially $C|g|_{W^{0,1}(U)}^\theta \cdot |g|_{W^{1,\infty}(U)}^{1-\theta}$ and therefore also $|g|_{W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)}$ go to zero if we consider functions g such that $|g|_{W^{0,1}(U)}$ and hence also $|g|_{W^{0,1}(U)}$ goes to zero and $|g|_{W^{1,\infty}(U)}$ and hence also $|g|_{W^{1,\infty}(U)}$ stays bounded.

This can be immediately applied to show that, for any $\theta \in (0, 1)$, the f_n are a Cauchy sequence with respect to the $W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}$ -norm, because they are a Cauchy sequence with respect to the L^1 norm:

That they are a Cauchy sequence with respect to the L^1 -norm simply means that:

$$h(n) := \sup_{n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq n}} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{L^1} \rightarrow 0$$

for $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Now we define, for $\theta \in (0, 1)$:

$$\tilde{h}_\theta(n) := \sup_{n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq n}} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}}$$

Applying Brezis Mironescu to each f_n and the differences between the f_n as above, we get that for all $n, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$f_n, f_{n_1} - f_{n_2} \in W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)} &= C |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{W^{0,1}(U)}^\theta \cdot |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{W^{1,\infty}(U)}^{1-\theta} \\ &\leq C(2B)^{1-\theta} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{W^{0,1}(U)}^\theta = C(2B)^{1-\theta} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{L^1(U)}^\theta \end{aligned}$$

for some constant C independent of the functions in question, so that not only all the $|f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}}$ -terms are well-defined, but also:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{h}_\theta(n) &= \sup_{n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq n}} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}} \leq \sup_{n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq n}} C(2B)^{1-\theta} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{L^1(U)}^\theta \\ &= C(2B)^{1-\theta} \left(\sup_{n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq n}} |f_{n_1} - f_{n_2}|_{L^1(U)} \right)^\theta = C(2B)^{1-\theta} h(n)^\theta \end{aligned}$$

because x^θ is monotonically increasing on $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$,

which is $< \infty$, since as mentioned already, because the f_n converge with respect to the L^1 -norm, they are bounded with respect to it, so that their differences are of course bounded with respect to the L^1 -norm as well, so that $h(n) < \infty$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and both supremums are even well-defined on the normal real number line.

So both $h(n)$ and $\tilde{h}_\theta(n)$ are well-defined real valued functions, and we have $\tilde{h}_\theta(n) \leq C(2B)^{1-\theta} h(n)^\theta$, so that because $h(n) \rightarrow 0$ and hence also $C(2B)^{1-\theta} h(n)^\theta \rightarrow 0$ for $n \rightarrow \infty$, and $\tilde{h}_\theta(n) \geq 0$, also $\tilde{h}_\theta(n) \rightarrow 0$ via the Sandwich lemma.

Now that we have that the f_n are all in $W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)$ and form a Cauchy sequence with respect to the $W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}$ -norm for all θ , we would like to use that to get that they are also all in $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$, forming a Cauchy sequence with respect to the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm, for all $\alpha \in (0, 1)$.

That they are also all in $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ simply follows because they are Lipschitz and the domain is bounded, so we only have to show that they form a Cauchy sequence in $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$:

We essentially do that via theorem 28. Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ be arbitrary. If one of our $W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)$ spaces for $\theta \in (0, 1)$ fulfills the conditions of theorem 28 for our α , that is, $(1-\theta)\theta^{-1} > n$ and $\alpha = ((1-\theta)\theta^{-1} - n)/(\theta^{-1})$, we get via theorem 28 that for that θ :

$$\forall g \in C^0(U) : |g|_{C^{0+\alpha}(U)} \leq c |g|_{W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)}$$

for some constant c .

So for that θ , the $W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}$ -norm is then at least as strong as the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm, on the continuous functions on U , to which our f_n belong.

But that then implies that because the f_n are a Cauchy sequence with respect to the $W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}$ -norm, as we have already shown, they are also a cauchy sequence with respect to the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm.

So for showing that the f_n are a Cauchy sequence with respect to the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm for our arbitrary α , it only remains to be shown that we can always find a $\theta \in (0, 1)$ such that $W^{1-\theta, \theta^{-1}}(U)$ fulfills the conditions of theorem 28 for our α , that is, $(1 - \theta)\theta^{-1} > n$ and $\alpha = ((1 - \theta)\theta^{-1} - n)/(\theta^{-1})$.

We note:

$$(1 - \theta)\theta^{-1} > n \Leftrightarrow \theta^{-1} > n + 1$$

and

$$\alpha \leq ((1 - \theta)\theta^{-1} - n)/(\theta^{-1}) \Leftrightarrow \alpha \leq (\theta^{-1} - (n + 1))/(\theta^{-1}) \Leftrightarrow \alpha \leq 1 - \theta(n + 1)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \theta(n + 1) \leq 1 - \alpha \Leftrightarrow \theta \leq \frac{1 - \alpha}{n + 1} \Leftrightarrow \theta^{-1} \geq \frac{n + 1}{1 - \alpha}$$

Which are obviously both fulfilled if:

$$\theta^{-1} = \max\left(n + 2, \frac{n + 1}{1 - \alpha}, 2\right) \Leftrightarrow \theta = \max\left(n + 2, \frac{n + 1}{1 - \alpha}, 2\right)^{-1} \in (0, 0.5] \subseteq (0, 1)$$

so we always find such a $\theta \in (0, 1)$ by setting:

$$\theta := \max\left(n + 2, \frac{n + 1}{1 - \alpha}, 2\right)^{-1}$$

and hence, as we have shown already assuming such a θ can be found, the f_n are indeed a cauchy sequence with respect to the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm for arbitrary and hence every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$.

So overall, we now have that because they are Lipschitz and U is bounded, the f_n are all in every $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ for $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, and that they are a Cauchy sequence with respect to the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm for arbitrary and hence every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$.

But then, since $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ is a Banach space when equipped with its canonical $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm, they also have a unique limit \tilde{f}_α in each of the $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ with respect to its respective norm.

But since the L^1 -norm, considered on functions in $C^0(U)$, else it would be a seminorm without considering equivalence classes, is not stronger (actually much weaker) than the C^0 -norm on functions in $C^0(U)$, and the C^0 -norm is not stronger (actually much weaker) than the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm on functions in $C^{0+\alpha}(U) \subseteq C^0(U)$, the convergence of the f_n to \tilde{f}_α in the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm implies the convergence of the f_n to \tilde{f}_α in the L^1 -norm on $C^0(U)$, so that, since limits on metric and hence also normed spaces are unique, each \tilde{f}_α actually has to be a L^1 -limit of the f_n in $C^0(U)$, so each of them has to be f , since f is a L^1 -limit of the f_n in $C^0(U)$. Especially, $f = \tilde{f}_\alpha$ therefore has to be in $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ for each $\alpha \in (0, 1)$.

But then we have that the f_n are all in $C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ and converge to $f = \tilde{f}_\alpha \in C^{0+\alpha}(U)$ with respect to the $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm for every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, so the core of the Corrolary is proven, and we only have to prove the triviality that therefore we also have that the f_n are also in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and converge to f with respect to the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ -norm for every $a \in (0, 1)$ if $U = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$.

In order to see this, we simply note that, as is easily shown, for every $a \in (0, 1)$, $C^{0+a}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) \subseteq H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, and that on $C^{0+a}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, where both norms are defined, the H_a -norm is not stronger (actually weaker) than the C^{0+a} -norm.

Hence in case $U = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, the f_n and f are all in $C^{0+a}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, and therefore they are also all in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, and because the f_n converge to f on $C^{0+a}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with respect to the not weaker (actually stronger) $C^{0+\alpha}$ -norm, they also converge to f with respect to the not stronger (actually weaker) H_a -norm.

Therefore, also the second statement about $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ in case $U = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ easily follows from the first, concluding the proof.

6.5. Schaefer's fixed point theorem and the direct sum of Banachspaces. Now we'll have a look at Schaefer's fixed point theorem and some foundations regarding the direct sum of Banachspaces that we will need to apply it to our case.

Due to the nature of the arguments, unlike in the rest of this work, where we consider multiple norms on the same vectorspace, we consider each of the spaces to be equipped with its own norm, and consider convergence, Cauchy sequences etc. in each space with respect to its norm, in order to streamline the presentation.

First we shall define the notion of precompactness, as it occurs in the statement of Schaefer's fixed point theorem:

Definition 30. For V a Banachspace we define a subset $U \subseteq V$ to be precompact if and only if every sequence in U has a Cauchy subsequence.

Remark. This common definition for Banachspaces, which explicitly shows the main reason why precompact spaces are useful in PDE, is actually well-known to be equivalent to the more generally applicable more common definition that $U \subseteq V$ is precompact if \bar{U} , considered as a metric subspace of V , is compact.

Example 31. A good example of precompact sets in Banachspaces which we will actually need later are, for $a \in (0, 1)$, $U \subseteq H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ such that even $U \subseteq H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and U is bounded in the H_{a+2} -norm.

Such sets U are precompact since because there is a bound on the H_{a+2} -norms of all functions in U , there is also a bound on all their Lipschitz constants and supremum norms, so that equivalently U is bounded in the in the boundary Hölder space of bounded Lipschitz functions $C^{0+1}(\Omega)$ (with respect to its norm), which automatically, because the embeddings $C^{0+1}(\Omega) \rightarrow C^{0+a}(\Omega)$ for $a \in (0, 1)$ are well known to be compact, that is, to map sets of functions in $C^{0+1}(\Omega)$ that are bounded with respect to the C^{0+1} -norm to sets of functions that are precompact in the Banachspace $C^{0+a}(\Omega)$, implies that U is precompact in the $C^{0+a}(\Omega)$ -spaces for all $a \in (0, 1)$. But then U is also precompact in all H_a -spaces for $a \in (0, 1)$, because a sequence being Cauchy in the C^{0+a} -norm implies it being Cauchy in the H_a -norm, since $|u|_{H_a} \leq c|u|_{C^{0+a}}$ for some constant c , since $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ is bounded, so precompactness in C^{0+a} obviously implies precompactness in H_a .

Now that we have seen what precompactness is, we take a look at Schaefer's fixed point theorem:

Theorem 32. (*Schaefer's fixed point theorem*)

Let V be a Banachspace, and $\mathcal{F} : V \rightarrow V$ be a continuous mapping that is compact in the usual sense that it maps bounded sets in V to precompact sets, and further assume that the escape set:

$$\mathcal{E} := \{v \in V : \exists \lambda \in [0, 1] : v = \lambda \mathcal{F}(v)\}$$

is bounded.

Then \mathcal{F} has a fixed point.

Now we cannot directly apply this to our problem, because we have two separate functions u, φ , each within a function space. However, the direct sum of Banachspaces allows us to, in a very natural way, understand tuples of vectors in Banachspaces as elements of a direct sum Banachspace, it can be defined as follows:

Definition 33. (The direct sum of Banachspaces)

Let V, W be two Banachspaces with norms $|\cdot|_V, |\cdot|_W$. Then we define $V \oplus W$ as the direct sum of the Vectorspaces V, W , that is the vectorspace of tuples (v, w) with $v \in V, w \in W$, with component wise addition and scalar multiplication, equipped with the norm:

$$|(v, w)|_{V \oplus W} := \max(|v|_V, |w|_W)$$

Additionally, we define the linear projections p_1, p_2 as for vectorspaces via:

$$p_1 : V \oplus W \rightarrow V; (v, w) \mapsto v$$

and

$$p_2 : V \oplus W \rightarrow W; (v, w) \mapsto w$$

Furthermore, for V any banachspace except those defined in definition 2, for which we defined V^n differently in definition 2, we define V^2 to be the space $V \oplus V$.

Remark. The norm $|(v, w)|_{V \oplus W}$ could also be defined via $|(v, w)|_{V \oplus W} := |v|_V + |w|_W = ||v|_V + |w|_W|$ or $|(v, w)|_{V \oplus W} := \sqrt{|v|_V^2 + |w|_W^2}$, or more generally via $|(v, w)|_{V \oplus W} := (|v|_V, |w|_W)_N$ for any norm $|\cdot|_N$ on the \mathbb{R}^2 , but these definitions actually all yield equivalent norms, as can be easily shown by a simple calculation using the fact that all norms on \mathbb{R}^2 are equivalent. Therefore, these definitions actually all yield the same notions of convergence, Cauchy sequences, precompactness, etc., even though the norms are different. Also, we could define $V_1 \oplus V_2 \oplus \dots \oplus V_n$ the obvious way, but sums of two spaces suffice for our purposes.

Now as one would expect, the projections are quite well-behaved:

Lemma 34. *(trivial properties of the projections)*

One trivially has:

$$\forall (v, w) \in V \oplus W : |p_1((v, w))|_V \leq |(v, w)|_{V \oplus W}$$

and

$$\forall (v, w) \in V \oplus W : |p_2((v, w))|_W \leq |(v, w)|_{V \oplus W}$$

so that p_1, p_2 are bounded linear functions, and hence continuous.

Proof. One has, for arbitrary $v \in V, w \in W$ that $|p_1((v, w))|_V = |v|_V \leq \max(|v|_V, |w|_V) = |(v, w)|_{V \oplus W}$ and $|p_2((v, w))|_W = |w|_W \leq \max(|v|_V, |w|_V) = |(v, w)|_{V \oplus W}$.

And moreover, boundedness, cauchyiness, convergence and precompactness on $V \oplus W$ can be characterized in a very natural way, as is easily shown by mostly writing out the definitions: \square

Lemma 35. *(boundedness, cauchyiness, convergence, precompactness on $V \oplus W$)*

Boundedness, cauchyiness, convergence and precompactness on $V \oplus W$ can be characterized as follows:

- A subset $U \subseteq V \oplus W$ is bounded if and only if both the images $p_1(U), p_2(W)$ are bounded.
- A sequence (v_n, w_n) in $V \oplus W$ is Cauchy if and only if v_n, w_n are.
- A sequence (v_n, w_n) in $V \oplus W$ converges to (v, w) if and only if v_n converges to v and w_n converges to w .
- A subset $U \subseteq V \oplus W$ is precompact in $V \oplus W$ if and only if both the images $p_1(U), p_2(W)$ are precompact.

7. EXISTENCE

Now that we have the necessary preliminaries, we first prove the existence of solutions, as is often done in PDE, via a fixed point argument. Concretely we prove:

Theorem 36. (*existence of strong solutions*)

Under the assumptions from section 5 and for arbitrary initial conditions $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C_N^1(\overline{\Omega})$ for some $a \in (0, 1)$, there always exists a strong solution with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial conditions u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} to the system equation (5.1), equation (5.2) in the sense of definition 9 such that u, φ of that solution are even in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for the same a .

Proof. In order to show the existence of solutions to our system, we consider arbitrary $a \in (0, 1)$ and $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C_N^1(\overline{\Omega})$ and define a functional \mathcal{F} whose fixed points are solutions to the system, and show that it is well-defined, as well as, via the Schäfer fixed point theorem, that it indeed has a fixed point, which then is the desired solution, and is even in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for the same a , concluding the proof.

For the rest of this proof, we assume $a \in (0, 1)$ as well as $\Omega, T_1, T_2, g, W', c_u, c_\varphi, k$ and the initial conditions $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)$ to be fixed, so they don't have to be mentioned every time a constant appears.

7.0.1. *Defining the functional \mathcal{F} .* Now we proceed to define the functional \mathcal{F} “component wise”. For $(u, \varphi) \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ we define:

- (1) $\tilde{\varphi} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) \subseteq C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ as the unique classical solution to $\tilde{\varphi}_t = \lambda \Delta \tilde{\varphi} - W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions in the sense of definition 6 and initial condition φ_{T_1} , that is $\tilde{\varphi}(T_1) = \varphi_{T_1}$,
- (2) building upon the definition of $\tilde{\varphi}$, we define $\tilde{u} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) \subseteq C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ as the unique classical solution to $c_u(x)\tilde{u}_t + c_\varphi(x)\tilde{\varphi}_t = \nabla \cdot (k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla \tilde{u})$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions in the sense of definition 6 and initial condition u_{T_1} , that is $\tilde{u}(T_1) = u_{T_1}$.

Based on these definitions we define the map $\mathcal{F} : H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2 \rightarrow H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2; (u, \varphi) \mapsto (\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi})$. This map actually, by the definition of $\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}$, even maps to $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$, but since we are about to look for fixed points, we will consider it as map from $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ to itself.

Now obviously, any fixed point (u, φ) of this functional \mathcal{F} will fulfill:

- (1) $\varphi \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) \subseteq C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a classical solution to $\varphi_t = \lambda \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions in the sense of definition 6 and initial condition φ_{T_1} , that is $\varphi(T_1) = \varphi_{T_1}$,
- (2) $u \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)) \subseteq C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a classical solution to $c_u(x)u_t + c_\varphi(x)\varphi_t = \nabla \cdot (k(\varphi, x)\nabla u)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions in the sense of definition 6 and initial condition u_{T_1} , that is $u(T_1) = u_{T_1}$.

and hence obviously be a solution with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions to our system in the sense of definition 9 such that u, φ are even in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, so any fixed point of this functional is indeed the required solution, and if we can show that this functional is well-defined and has a fixed point, we have proven the theorem.

7.0.2. *Well-definedness of \mathcal{F} .* Firstly, let us quickly check that the functional \mathcal{F} is actually well defined. Due to lemma 23 $-W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x) \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, because W', g are Lipschitz, and $u, \varphi \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$. But then, $\tilde{\varphi}$ is obviously well-defined and in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, by theorem 19.

But for such regular $\tilde{\varphi}$, since k is totally differentiable, one obviously can rewrite:

$$c_u(x)\tilde{u}_t + c_\varphi(x)\tilde{\varphi}_t = \nabla \cdot (k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla \tilde{u})$$

to the equivalent equation:

$$c_u(x)\tilde{u}_t = k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\Delta\tilde{u} + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k\right)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\tilde{\varphi} + (\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - c_\varphi(x)\tilde{\varphi}_t$$

which again is equivalent to, by dividing by $c_u(x)$, which we can do, since we assumed $c_u(x) \in [c_{min}, c_{max}] \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}$:

$$\tilde{u}_t = \tilde{k}(x, t)\Delta\tilde{u} + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i(x, t) \cdot (\nabla\tilde{u})_i + f$$

for:

- $\tilde{k}(x, t) := \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}$
- $b_i(x, t) := \left(\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)} \nabla\tilde{\varphi} + \frac{1}{c_u(x)} (\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x) \right)_i$ for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$
- $f(x, t) := -\frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)} \tilde{\varphi}_t$

From now on, we will mostly use this equivalent form of the PDE fulfilled by \tilde{u} instead of the original PDE from the definition of \mathcal{F} .

Looking at the $\tilde{k}(x, t)$, $b_i(x, t)$ and $f(x, t)$, we quickly note that $\tilde{k} \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, $b_i \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and $f \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, essentially by lemma 23 , because:

- k and the total derivative of k were assumed to be Lipschitz, so $k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)$, $(\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)$, $(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)$ are all in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ via lemma 23 , since $\tilde{\varphi}$ is in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.
- Because $c_u(x) \in [c_{min}, c_{max}] \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and c_u in $C^1(\bar{\Omega})$ also $\frac{1}{c_u(x)}$ is in $C^1(\bar{\Omega})$ and hence Lipschitz, because Ω is bounded with a C^3 -boundary, so especially Lipschitz, and functions with bounded total derivatives on Lipschitz domains are known to be Lipschitz.
- Further $(\nabla\tilde{\varphi})_i, \tilde{\varphi}_t \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, because $\tilde{\varphi} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.
- Furthermore, since multiplication is Lipschitz on bounded subsets of its domain and addition is globally Lipschitz continuous, lemma 23 further yields that $\tilde{k}(x, t)$, the $b_i(x, t)$, and $f(x, t)$ are in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

But then one can again apply theorem 19 , this time to:

$$\tilde{u}_t = \tilde{k}(x, t)\Delta\tilde{u} + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i(x, t) \cdot (\nabla\tilde{u})_i + f$$

with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, and obtain that there is a unique classical solution $\tilde{u} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition u_{T_1} , so \tilde{u} is well-defined as well, so \mathcal{F} is well-defined.

7.0.3. Compactness of \mathcal{F} . Now that we have that \mathcal{F} is well-defined, we proceed by showing that it is a compact map, in the sense that it maps sets in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ that are bounded with respect to its norm to sets that are precompact in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ with respect to its Banach space structure. In order to do this, we simply use that theorem 19 yields H_{a+2} -bounds, and that bounded subsets of $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ are precompact in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, as we have seen in example 31 , to basically show that for any bounded set U , the two projections of $p_1(\mathcal{F}(U))$, $p_2(\mathcal{F}(U))$ in the sense of definition 33 are precompact, and hence, via lemma 35 , $\mathcal{F}(U)$ is precompact in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$.

With this in mind, we now aim to bound $|p_1(\mathcal{F}((u, \varphi)))|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|p_2(\mathcal{F}((u, \varphi)))|_{H_{a+2}}$, that is $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$, by some bound $B_{H_{a+2}}(B_{H_a})$ in terms of a bound B_{H_a} on $|(u, \varphi)|_{H_a}$, that is a bound on $\max(|u|_{H_a}, |\varphi|_{H_a})$, so on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$.

We essentially do that by going through the argument that the various terms are in H_a again, using the estimate from lemma 23 every time that lemma is used, and the estimate from theorem 19 every time that theorem is used.

Concretely we see that, for B_{H_a} a bound on $|(u, \varphi)|_{H_a}$, so on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$:

- Due to lemma 23 $-W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x) \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with $|-W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x)|_{H_a}$ bounded by some bound depending only on B_{H_a} (and fixed objects like $\Omega, T_1, T_2, W', g, \dots$), because W', g are Lipschitz, and $u, \varphi \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.
- But then, $\tilde{\varphi}$ is obviously well-defined and in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$ bounded by some bound depending only on B_{H_a} (and fixed objects) by theorem 19 .
- By the definition of $|\ast|_{H_{a+2}}$, we then also have $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_a}, |(\nabla \tilde{\varphi})_i|_{H_a}$ and $|\tilde{\varphi}_t|_{H_a}$ bounded by some bound depending only on B_{H_a} (and fixed objects).
- But then we get that, by repeatedly applying lemma 23 , $\tilde{k}(x, t) = \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}$, the $b_i(x, t) = \left(\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)} \nabla \tilde{\varphi} + \frac{1}{c_u(x)} (\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x) \right)_i$ for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $f(x, t) = -\frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)} \tilde{\varphi}_t$ have H_a -norms bounded by some bound depending only on B_{H_a} (and fixed objects) too.
- But then we can apply theorem 19 again to obtain that \tilde{u} , which we know is the unique function in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ that solves $\tilde{u}_t = \tilde{k}(x, t) \Delta \tilde{u} + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i(x, t) \cdot (\nabla \tilde{u})_i + f$ classically with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and the fixed initial condition u_{T_1} , has $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ bounded by some bound depending only on B_{H_a} (and fixed objects) as well.

So that we get that we then have both $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ bounded by some bound depending only on B_{H_a} (and fixed objects).

But this obviously implies that for U any bounded subset of $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$, $p_1(\mathcal{F}(U)), p_2(\mathcal{F}(U))$ are in the H_{a+2} -norm bounded subsets of $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, and hence precompact as subsets of the Banachspace $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

But then we get that, via lemma 35 , $\mathcal{F}(U)$ is actually precompact in the Banachspace $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$, for any bounded subset $U \subseteq H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$, so that we have that \mathcal{F} is compact, in the sense that it maps all bounded subsets of the Banachspace $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ to precompact subsets of the same, as required.

7.0.4. *Continuity of \mathcal{F} .* Now, we only need to show continuity of \mathcal{F} , with respect to the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm, besides the escape set criterion, to be able to apply the Schäfer fixed point theorem to obtain a fixed point of \mathcal{F} , concluding our existence proof.

Due to lemma 35 we obviously have that \mathcal{F} is continuous with respect to the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm if and only if, for any sequences u_n, φ_n in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with $u_n \rightarrow u_{lim}, \varphi_n \rightarrow \varphi_{lim}$ with respect to the H_a -norm, also $\tilde{u}_n \rightarrow \tilde{u}_{lim}, \tilde{\varphi}_n \rightarrow \tilde{\varphi}_{lim}$ with respect to the H_a -norm, where $(\tilde{u}_n, \tilde{\varphi}_n) := \mathcal{F}((u_n, \varphi_n))$ and $(\tilde{u}_{lim}, \tilde{\varphi}_{lim}) := \mathcal{F}((u_{lim}, \varphi_{lim}))$ are simply the $\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}$ tuples corresponding to the respective u, φ tuples.

Therefore, we now show continuity of \mathcal{F} with respect to the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm by considering arbitrary sequences u_n, φ_n in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with $u_n \rightarrow u_{lim}, \varphi_n \rightarrow \varphi_{lim}$ with respect to the H_a -norm, and showing that for $(\tilde{u}_n, \tilde{\varphi}_n) := \mathcal{F}((u_n, \varphi_n))$ and $(\tilde{u}_{lim}, \tilde{\varphi}_{lim}) := \mathcal{F}((u_{lim}, \varphi_{lim}))$ we indeed get $\tilde{u}_n \rightarrow \tilde{u}_{lim}, \tilde{\varphi}_n \rightarrow \tilde{\varphi}_{lim}$, even in the H_{a+2} -norm, which will be useful later, so especially also in the H_a -norm, as required for the continuity.

Now because $u_n \rightarrow u_{lim}, \varphi_n \rightarrow \varphi_{lim}$ in the H_a -norm, and g and W' are Lipschitz, lemma 23 yields that $-W'(\varphi_n) + g(u_n, \varphi_n, x) \rightarrow -W'(\varphi_{lim}) + g(u_{lim}, \varphi_{lim}, x)$ in the H_a -norm.

But then we get, because $\tilde{\varphi}_n$ is the unique solution in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ to $(\tilde{\varphi}_n)_t = \lambda \Delta \tilde{\varphi}_n - W'(\varphi_n) + g(u, \varphi_n, x)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition φ_{T_1} , and $\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}$ is the unique solution in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ to $(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim})_t = \lambda \Delta \tilde{\varphi}_{lim} - W'(\varphi_{lim}) + g(u, \varphi_{lim}, x)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition φ_{T_1} , via corollary 20 , that $\tilde{\varphi}_n \rightarrow \tilde{\varphi}_{lim}$ in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, as we wanted to show for the $\tilde{\varphi}_n$.

This especially implies, via the definition of $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, that $(\nabla \tilde{\varphi}_n)_i \rightarrow (\nabla \tilde{\varphi}_{lim})_i$ for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $(\tilde{\varphi}_n)_t \rightarrow (\tilde{\varphi}_{lim})_t$ with respect to the H_a -norm.

But then also, because $k, \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k, \nabla_x k$ were assumed to be Lipschitz, we have that $k(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x) \rightarrow k(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)$, $(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x) \rightarrow (\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)$ and $(\nabla_x k)_i(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x) \rightarrow (\nabla_x k)_i(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)$ with respect to the H_a -norm via lemma 23 .

But then, because $k(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x) \rightarrow k(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)$, $(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x) \rightarrow (\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)$, $(\nabla_x k)_i(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x) \rightarrow (\nabla_x k)_i(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)$ and $(\nabla \tilde{\varphi}_n)_i \rightarrow (\nabla \tilde{\varphi}_{lim})_i$ for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, and $(\tilde{\varphi}_n)_t \rightarrow (\tilde{\varphi}_{lim})_t$, with respect to the H_a -norm, and $\frac{1}{c_u(x)} \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$ is Lipschitz, and multiplication is Lipschitz on bounded subsets of \mathbb{R}^2 , and addition is Lipschitz, we have that, via applying lemma 23 repeatedly:

- $\tilde{k}_n(x, t) := \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x)}{c_u(x)} \rightarrow \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)}{c_u(x)} =: \tilde{k}_{lim}(x, t)$
- $b_{n,i}(x, t) := \left(\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x)}{c_u(x)} \nabla \varphi + \frac{(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}_n, x)}{c_u(x)} \right)_i \rightarrow \left(\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)}{c_u(x)} \nabla \varphi + \frac{(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)}{c_u(x)} \right)_i =: b_{lim,i}(x, t)$
- $f_n(x, t) := -\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} E)(u_n, \tilde{\varphi}_n, x)}{c_u(x)} (\tilde{\varphi}_n)_t \rightarrow -\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} E)(u_{lim}, \tilde{\varphi}_{lim}, x)}{c_u(x)} (\tilde{\varphi}_{lim})_t =: f_{lim}(x, t)$

in the H_a -norm, so that, because \tilde{u}_n is the unique classical solution in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ to $(\tilde{u}_n)_t = \tilde{k}_n(x, t) \Delta \tilde{u}_n + \sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_{n,i}(x, t) \cdot \nabla \tilde{u}_n + f_n$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition u_{T_1} , and \tilde{u}_{lim} is the unique classical solution in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ to $(\tilde{u}_{lim})_t = \tilde{k}_{lim}(x, t) \Delta \tilde{u}_{lim} + b_{lim,i}(x, t) \cdot \nabla \tilde{u}_{lim} + f_{lim}$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition u_{T_1} , again via corollary 20 , we have that $\tilde{u}_n \rightarrow \tilde{u}_{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm, so that we now have $\tilde{u}_n \rightarrow \tilde{u}_{lim}, \tilde{\varphi}_n \rightarrow \tilde{\varphi}_{lim}$ with respect to the H_{a+2} -norm, so especially with respect to the H_a -norm, concluding the continuity proof.

7.0.5. *Bounding the escape set \mathcal{E} .* Now that we know that \mathcal{F} maps bounded sets to precompact sets and is continuous, in order to show that it has a fixed point, via the Schaefer fixed point theorem, concluding the existence proof, we only need to show that the escape set:

$$\mathcal{E} := \{(u, \varphi) \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2 : (u, \varphi) = \lambda \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi)), \lambda \in [0, 1]\}$$

is bounded in the H_a -norm.

For this, we let (u, φ) be an arbitrary element of \mathcal{E} , and show that it is bounded by a constant that of course doesn't depend on it. By the definition of \mathcal{E} , $(u, \varphi) \in \mathcal{E}$ means that there is a $\Lambda \in [0, 1]$ so that $(u, \varphi) = \Lambda(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi})$ for $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$, let Λ be such a Λ .

Now writing $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$, by the definition of \mathcal{F} , $(u, \varphi) = \Lambda(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi})$ for $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$ obviously means that $u = \Lambda \tilde{u}, \varphi = \Lambda \tilde{\varphi} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with:

- (1) $\tilde{\varphi}_t = \Lambda \Delta \tilde{\varphi} - W'(\varphi) + g(u, \varphi, x)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition φ_{T_1} ,
- (2) $c_u(x) \tilde{u}_t + c_\varphi(x) \tilde{\varphi}_t = \nabla \cdot (k(\tilde{\varphi}, x) \nabla \tilde{u})$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition u_{T_1} .

Or equivalently, expressing everything in $\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}$:

- (1) $\tilde{\varphi}_t = \Lambda \Delta \tilde{\varphi} - W'(\Lambda \tilde{\varphi}) + g(\Lambda \tilde{u}, \Lambda \tilde{\varphi}, x)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition φ_{T_1} ,
- (2) $c_u(x) \tilde{u}_t + c_\varphi(x) \tilde{\varphi}_t = \nabla \cdot (k(\tilde{\varphi}, x) \nabla \tilde{u})$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial condition u_{T_1} .

Now since W' and g were assumed to be bounded, there is a bound B_{f_φ} on $|-W'(\Lambda \tilde{\varphi}) + g(\Lambda \tilde{u}, \Lambda \tilde{\varphi}, x)|$ that does not depend on $\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}$ or even the initial data. Additionally, the initial data φ_{T_1} is in $H_{a+2}(\Omega)$. All in all, we have that \tilde{u} is a solution to a heat equation with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, initial data bounded in the H_{a+2} -norm and a source term that is pointwise bounded, so corollary 26 is applicable, and yields that for any fixed $p \geq 1, a \in (0, 1)$, so especially letting $p := p_0(a, \Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ with the p_0 from theorem 21 ,

the norm $|\tilde{\varphi}_t|_{L^p(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$ is bounded as well, independently of u, φ . Additionally, the other corollary corollary 22 of theorem 25 is of course applicable too, and yields that $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_a}$ is bounded too, also independently of u, φ .

Now we have that $\tilde{u} \in C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)})$ is a solution to:

$$c_u(x)\tilde{u}_t = k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\Delta\tilde{u} + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k\right)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + (\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - c_\varphi(x)\tilde{\varphi}_t$$

which we now want to bring in divergence form, so we can apply theorem 21 .

Dividing by $c_u(x)$ we get:

$$\tilde{u}_t = \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\Delta\tilde{u} + \left(\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k}{c_u(x)}(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + \frac{1}{c_u(x)}(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t$$

Now we would like to make this:

$$\tilde{u}_t = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right) + (\dots) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t$$

In order to do this, we first note that, via the quotient rule:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\Delta\tilde{u} - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right) = - \left(\nabla \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} \\ & = - \left(\frac{1}{c_u(x)} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k\right)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + (\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x) - \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)^2}\nabla c_u(x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} \end{aligned}$$

So that we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{u}_t &= \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\Delta\tilde{u} + \left(\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k}{c_u(x)}(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + \frac{1}{c_u(x)}(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t \\ \Leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_t &= \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\Delta\tilde{u} - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right)\right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right) + \left(\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k}{c_u(x)}(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + \frac{1}{c_u(x)}(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t \\ &\Leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_t = - \left(\frac{1}{c_u(x)} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k\right)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + (\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x) - \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)^2}\nabla c_u(x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} \\ &+ \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right) + \left(\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k}{c_u(x)}(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + \frac{1}{c_u(x)}(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t \\ \Leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_t &= - \left(\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k}{c_u(x)}(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + \frac{1}{c_u(x)}(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} + \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)^2}\nabla c_u(x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} \\ &+ \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right) + \left(\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial\varphi}k}{c_u(x)}(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\nabla\varphi + \frac{1}{c_u(x)}(\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}, x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t \end{aligned}$$

And we immediately see that the terms containing $\nabla\varphi$ cancel so we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_t &= \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)^2}\nabla c_u(x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right) - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t \\ \Leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_t &= \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}\nabla\tilde{u}\right) + \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)^2}\nabla c_u(x)\right) \cdot \nabla\tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}\tilde{\varphi}_t \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_t &= \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)} \nabla \tilde{u} \right) + \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)^2} \nabla c_u(x) \right) \cdot \nabla \tilde{u} - \frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)} \tilde{\varphi}_t \\ \Leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_t &= \nabla \cdot \left(\tilde{k}(x, t) \nabla \tilde{u} \right) + \left(\sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i^{div}(x, t) \cdot (\nabla \tilde{u})_i \right) + f(x, t) \end{aligned}$$

for

- $\tilde{k}(x, t) := \frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)}$ as usual
- $b_i^{div}(x, t) := \left(\frac{k(\tilde{\varphi}, x)}{c_u(x)^2} \nabla c_u(x) \right)_i$ for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$
- $f(x, t) := -\frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)} \tilde{\varphi}_t$ as usual

But we already have that $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_a}$ is bounded independently of u, φ , and $\nabla c_u \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})^3$, $\frac{1}{c_u}, c_\varphi \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$, with $\frac{1}{c_u(x)} \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$ because $c_u \in C^1(\bar{\Omega}), \forall x \in \Omega : c_u(x) \geq c_{min} > 0$, so $\nabla c_u, \frac{1}{c_u}, c_\varphi$ are Lipschitz, because $\bar{\Omega}$ is a Lipschitz domain.

Thus we can, as usual, repeatedly apply lemma 23, and obtain that \tilde{k} and the b_i^{div} are bounded in the H_a -norm, independently of u, φ .

Furthermore, because $-\frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)}$ is bounded since $\frac{1}{c_u}, c_\varphi \in C^1(\bar{\Omega})$, and we know that $|\tilde{\varphi}_t|_{L^p(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$ is bounded independently of u, φ for our fixed $p = 1000$, we obviously have that, essentially via the definition of the L^p -norm, $|f|_{L^p(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))}$ is bounded independently of u, φ as well.

But then \tilde{u} is a classical solution to $\tilde{u}_t = \nabla \cdot \left(\tilde{k}(x, t) \nabla \tilde{u} \right) + \left(\sum_{i \in \{1, 2, 3\}} b_i^{div}(x, t) \cdot (\nabla \tilde{u})_i \right) + f(x, t)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and our fixed initial condition u_{T_1} , with \tilde{k} and the b_i^{div} bounded in the H_a -norm, and f bounded in the L^p -norm for our fixed $p = 1000$, so we can apply theorem 21 and obtain that also \tilde{u} is bounded in the H_a -norm, independently of u, φ .

But then we now have that \tilde{u} and $\tilde{\varphi}$ are bounded in the H_a -norm, independently of u, φ , so we especially get that $u, \varphi = \Lambda \tilde{u}, \Lambda \tilde{\varphi}$ are bounded in the H_a norm too, again with a bound independent of u, φ , so we have that (u, φ) is bounded in the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm with a bound independent of (u, φ) , and, because (u, φ) was an arbitrary element of the escape set \mathcal{E} , that the escape set is bounded with some fixed bound, too.

7.0.6. Concluding the existence proof. Thus, all prerequisites to applying the Schaefer fixed point theorem to \mathcal{F} have been shown, \mathcal{F} is continuous and compact and the escape set \mathcal{E} is bounded, so the Schaefer fixed point theorem yields that \mathcal{F} has a fixed point (u, φ) , which by definition of \mathcal{F} is, as we have already seen, the solution with $u, \varphi \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ we needed to find, concluding the proof.

8. BOUNDEDNESS OF SOLUTIONS

During the existence proof, we already bounded the escape set \mathcal{E} in the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm. Furthermore, for showing the compactness of \mathcal{F} , we also, for arbitrary $(u, \varphi) \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$, have shown that $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}, |\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ for $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$, can be bounded by some bound $B_{H_{a+2}}(B_{H_a})$ in terms of a bound B_{H_a} on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$.

Now these results were derived for fixed u_{T_1} , however, u_0 affects these bounding arguments only at a few select places via a dependency on a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$, so that we will see that the line of reasoning from the existence proof works for variable u_0 too, yielding bounds that then depend on u_0 only via a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$.

Chaining these results, we will obtain the following boundedness result in this section:

Theorem 37. *(A H_{a+2} -bound on solutions)*

For fixed $a \in (0, 1)$, fixed Ω and interval length $T_2 - T_1$, and a fixed system, that is fixed g, W', c_u, c_φ, k , there is a function $B_{H_{a+2}} : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ so that:

- for arbitrary initial data $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C^1(\bar{\Omega})$,
- an arbitrary bound $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ such that $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}} \leq B_{data}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}} \leq B_{data}$,
- and any solution u, φ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions to the system equation (5.1), equation (5.2) in the sense of definition 9 such that u, φ of that solution are even in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$,

also $|u|_{H_{a+2}} \leq B_{H_{a+2}}(B_{data})$ and $|\varphi|_{H_{a+2}} \leq B_{H_{a+2}}(B_{data})$.

That is, for fixed Ω and interval length $T_2 - T_1$, and a fixed system, that is fixed g, W', c_u, c_φ, k , one can bound $|u|_{H_{a+2}}, |\varphi|_{H_{a+2}}$ for solutions u, φ with $u, \varphi \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ by some bound depending only on a bound on the H_{a+2} -norms of the initial data u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} .

Proof. First we notice that if the claim holds when we fix T_1 and T_2 instead of only fixing the interval length $T_2 - T_1$, it also holds if we only fix $T_2 - T_1$, essentially because solutions to the system are translation invariant:

If u, φ solve the system with some initial data on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, then for every offset $d \in \mathbb{R}$, the translated functions $\tilde{u} : \Omega \times (T_1 + d, T_2 + d); (x, t) \mapsto u(x, t - d)$ and $\tilde{\varphi} : \Omega \times (T_1 + d, T_2 + d); (x, t) \mapsto \varphi(x, t - d)$ solve it for the same initial data too.

But then, one can always translate the domain $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ to $\Omega \times (\tilde{T}_1 := 0, \tilde{T}_2 := T_2 - T_1)$, and translate the solution to be bounded accordingly, too, bound it on the translated domain with the theorem for fixed T_1 and T_2 , with $\tilde{T}_1 := 0, \tilde{T}_2 := T_2 - T_1$ however only depending on $T_2 - T_1$, and translate the solution back, without changing the bounds because H_{a+2} -norms are translation invariant too.

Therefore, without loss of generality, it suffices to show the theorem for fixed T_1 and T_2 , so we now proceed to show it for fixed T_1 and T_2 as sketched in the beginning of this section:

8.0.1. *Bounding the H_a -norm.* We start by noticing that the line of reasoning we used for bounding the escape set actually yields bounds on all solutions to the system in the sense of definition 9 such that u, φ additionally are in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, too, because each of them obviously has to be a fixed point of \mathcal{F} , by the definition of \mathcal{F} , and therefore has to be contained in the escape set \mathcal{E} , which we bounded.

Now when we bounded the escape set, we assumed u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} to be fixed, so the argument isn't directly applicable, however, going through the argument again, we quickly notice that u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} only affects the bounds via the estimates from corollary 26, corollary 22 and theorem 21, and in each of those, it only affects the bounds via a dependence on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

Therefore we have that also for variable u_0 , the escape set \mathcal{E} is still bounded in the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm, with a bound depending only on a bound B_{data} on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$.

Now by the definition of the escape set \mathcal{E} , we obviously have that any solution u, φ to the system in the sense of definition 9 with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial data u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} that additionally is in $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ is contained in the escape set \mathcal{E} of \mathcal{F} for that initial data. Therefore, the bound on the escape set in the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm that only depends on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ also is a bound on all such solutions (u, φ) with the respective initial data in the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))^2$ -norm that only depends on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

So we now have that for such solutions, u and φ can be bounded in the $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ -norm by a bound that only depends on a bound B_{data} on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$.

8.0.2. *Upgrading to a H_{a+2} -bound.* Now that we have a $H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ -bound that only depends on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$, we only need to upgrade it to a H_{a+2} -bound.

We will do that by using that any such solution is a fixed point of \mathcal{F} again, in conjunction with another bounding argument we essentially already did for the existence proof:

When we showed that \mathcal{F} is compact for the existence proof, we also showed that for arbitrary $u, \varphi \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, setting $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$ as usual, $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$ can be bounded by a bound that only depends on a bound B_{H_a} on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$.

Now just like with the escape set argument, we cannot directly defer to this argument because we assumed the initial data to be fixed in the existence proof.

However, again very similarly to when we worked with the escape set argument, going through the argument again, we quickly notice that u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} only affects the bounds via the estimate from theorem 19 which we use twice, and in this estimate, it only affects the bound via a linear dependence on $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ in one instance and $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ in the other.

Therefore we can simply estimate by plugging in any bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ for $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_a}$ and $|u_{T_1}|_{H_a}$ at these places, possibly increasing the bounds we get out, but still obtaining valid bounds, and otherwise argue effectively exactly as in the existence proof, obtaining for the case of variable initial data a bound $B_{H_{a+2}}$ on $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$ for $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$ that depends only on a bound B_{H_a} on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$ and a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

So we now have that for the case of variable initial data, for any $u, \varphi \in H_a(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, there is a bound $B_{H_{a+2}}$ on $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$ for $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$ that depends only on a bound B_{H_a} on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$ and a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

But we already have shown that for solutions (u, φ) to our system with variable initial data $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)$ and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions such that u, φ are additionally in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, there is a bound $B_{H_a}(B_{data})$ on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$ that itself only depends on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

So considering such a solution (u, φ) for some variable initial data u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} , and considering \mathcal{F} for the same variable initial data, we can use this bound $B_{H_a}(B_{data})$ as bound B_{H_a} on $|u|_{H_a}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_a}$, obtaining that there is a bound $B_{H_{a+2}}(B_{data})$ on $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$ for $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$ that depends only on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

But since such solutions (u, φ) with some initial data are fixed points of the \mathcal{F} for the same initial data, we have that in this case, actually $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi)) = (u, \varphi)$, so the bound $B_{H_{a+2}}$ on $|\tilde{u}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\tilde{\varphi}|_{H_{a+2}}$ for $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{\varphi}) := \mathcal{F}((u, \varphi))$ that depends only on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ we have found actually is a bound $B_{H_{a+2}}(B_{data})$ on $|u|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_{a+2}}$ that depends only on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

So with this bound, we now have, for arbitrary solutions to our system with variable initial data $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)$ and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions such that u, φ are additionally in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, and independent of the solution considered, a bound $B_{H_{a+2}}(B_{data})$ on $|u|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi|_{H_{a+2}}$ that depends (besides the fixed quantities, including T_1 and T_2 , which we have seen we can fix without loss of generality) only on a bound B_{data} on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$ and $|\varphi_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$, as claimed in the theorem, concluding the proof.

9. UNIQUENESS AND WELL POSEDNESS

Now that we have solution existence and boundedness results, it is time to show solution uniqueness and solution well-posedness, that is, that the solution continuously depends on the initial data.

So we now consider a fixed system, fixed domain and fixed interval (T_1, T_2) , and show that solutions are unique, and in a sense continuously depend on the initial data. Concretely we show:

Theorem 38. *(Uniqueness & Well posedness)*

Let $\Omega, T_1, T_2, g, W', c_u, c_\varphi, k$ be arbitrary but fixed so that the assumptions from section 5 hold, and let $a \in (0, 1)$ be arbitrary but fixed.

Then, for arbitrary initial conditions $u_{T_1}, \varphi_{T_1} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C_N^1(\bar{\Omega})$, there exists exactly one strong solution with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial conditions u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} to the system equation (5.1), equation (5.2) in the sense of definition 9, and furthermore, u, φ of that solution always are in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ for the same a .

Additionally, the unique solution depends continuously on the initial data in the sense that if $u_{T_1}^n, \varphi_{T_1}^n \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$ are arbitrary sequences of initial datums that converge to $u_{T_1}^{lim}, \varphi_{T_1}^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm, $u^{(n)}, \varphi^{(n)}$ is the unique solution to the system for initial data $u_{T_1}^n, \varphi_{T_1}^n$, and u^{lim}, φ^{lim} is the unique solution to the system for initial data $u_{T_1}^{lim}, \varphi_{T_1}^{lim}$, we have that $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ and $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm.

Proof. Firstly we let, as in the theorem, $\Omega, T_1, T_2, g, W', c_u, c_\varphi, k$ be arbitrary but fixed so that the assumptions from section 5 hold, and $a \in (0, 1)$ be arbitrary but fixed.

Now in order to prove the theorem by showing that the uniqueness and the well-posedness part both hold, we first derive a quite weak well posedness result by applying the energy method to the difference between two solutions, and then conclude the uniqueness part of the theorem and upgrade it to show the well posedness part of the theorem.

9.1. A first weak well posedness result via the energy method. Concretely, we'll now show the following weak well posedness result:

Let $u_{T_1}^{(1)}, \varphi_{T_1}^{(1)} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)$ and $u_{T_1}^{(2)}, \varphi_{T_1}^{(2)} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega)$, all with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, be two arbitrary potentially different sets of initial data, and consider two solutions $u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}$ and $u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}$ of the system in the sense of definition 9, so with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, $u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}$ being an arbitrary solution with initial data $u_{T_1}^{(1)}, \varphi_{T_1}^{(1)}$, and $u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}$ being an arbitrary solution with initial data $u_{T_1}^{(2)}, \varphi_{T_1}^{(2)}$, and define $u_d := u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}, \varphi_d := \varphi^{(1)} - \varphi^{(2)}$. Then we have that that:

$$\forall t \in (T_1, T_2) : \max(|u_d(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) \leq C \max(|u_0^{(1)} - u_0^{(2)}|_{L^2}, |\varphi_0^{(1)} - \varphi_0^{(2)}|_{L^2})$$

with some constant C that only depends on (besides the fixed objects) a bound B_{data} on the H_{a+2} -norms of the initial datums, that is $|u_{T_1}^{(1)}|_{H_{a+2}}, |\varphi_{T_1}^{(1)}|_{H_{a+2}}, |u_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{H_{a+2}}, |\varphi_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{H_{a+2}}$.

In order to show this, we let $u_0^{(1)}, \varphi_0^{(1)}$ and $u_0^{(2)}, \varphi_0^{(2)}$ as well as $u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}$ and $u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}$ be as in the weak well posedness result we want to show, and proceed to apply the energy method to $u_d := u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}$ and $\varphi_d := \varphi^{(1)} - \varphi^{(2)}$ defined as in the weak well posedness result.

As usual when applying the energy method, we start by computing bounds on $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ and $\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$:

9.1.1. *An expression for $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ and $\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ via the Feynman trick.* Since we have $u_d, \varphi_d \in C^{2,1}(\overline{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$, we can apply theorem 14 to get that $|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ and $|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ are differentiable on (T_1, T_2) in the classical sense, with derivatives

$$\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 = 2\langle u_d(t), (u_d)_t(t) \rangle_{L^2} = 2\langle u_d(t), (u_t^{(1)} - u_t^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

and

$$\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 = 2\langle \varphi_d(t), (\varphi_d)_t(t) \rangle_{L^2} = 2\langle \varphi_d(t), (\varphi_t^{(1)} - \varphi_t^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

Now plugging in the expressions for $u_t^{(1)}, u_t^{(2)}, \varphi_t^{(1)}, \varphi_t^{(2)}$ we get because they are solutions to our system, we obtain, setting for brevity $k^{(1)} := k(\varphi^{(1)}, x), k^{(2)} := k(\varphi^{(2)}, x)$ and $c_u := c_u(x), c_\varphi := c_\varphi(x)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 &= 2\langle u_d(t), c_u^{-1} \left((\nabla \cdot (k^{(1)} \nabla u^{(1)}) - \nabla \cdot (k^{(2)} \nabla u^{(2)})) - c_\varphi (\varphi_t^{(1)} - \varphi_t^{(2)}) \right) (t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &= 2\langle c_u^{-1} u_d(t), \left(\nabla \cdot (k^{(1)} \nabla (u^{(1)} - u^{(2)})) + \nabla \cdot \left((k^{(1)} - k^{(2)}) \nabla u^{(2)} \right) - c_\varphi (\varphi_t^{(1)} - \varphi_t^{(2)}) \right) (t) \rangle_{L^2} = q_1 + q_2 + q_3 \end{aligned}$$

for the quantities:

- $q_1 := 2\langle c_u^{-1}u_d(t), \nabla \cdot (k^{(1)}\nabla(u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}))(t) \rangle_{L^2}$
- $q_2 := 2\langle c_u^{-1}u_d(t), \nabla \cdot ((k^{(1)} - k^{(2)})\nabla u^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2}$
- $q_3 := -2\langle c_u^{-1}u_d(t), c_\varphi(\varphi_t^{(1)} - \varphi_t^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2}$

9.1.2. *Bounding with partial integration I - bounding $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$.* Now we conceptually bound $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ by bounding the quantities above individually, in order to avoid overly long equations.

For q_1 we have:

$$\begin{aligned} q_1 &= 2\langle c_u^{-1}u_d(t), \nabla \cdot (k^{(1)}\nabla(u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}))(t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &= -2\langle u_d(t)\nabla(c_u^{-1}) + c_u^{-1}\nabla u_d(t), (k^{(1)}\nabla(u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}))(t) \rangle_{L^2} \end{aligned}$$

by corollary 16, which we can do because $c_u^{-1}u_d(t) \in C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$ via applying lemma 17 twice,

$$\begin{aligned} &= -2\langle c_u^{-1}\nabla u_d(t), k^{(1)}(t)\nabla u_d(t) \rangle_{L^2} - 2\langle u_d(t)\nabla(c_u^{-1}), k^{(1)}(t)\nabla u_d(t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &= -2\langle \nabla u_d(t), \nabla u_d(t) \rangle_{c_u^{-1}k^{(1)}(t)} - 2\langle u_d(t)\nabla(c_u^{-1}), k^{(1)}(t)\nabla u_d(t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &\leq -2\langle \nabla u_d(t), \nabla u_d(t) \rangle_{c_{max}^{-1}k_{min}} + 2|u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla(c_u^{-1})|_{C^0k_{max}}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2} \end{aligned}$$

via the fundamentals of working with L^2 -norms and scalar products and $\langle *, * \rangle_k$ -scalar products, using that we assumed $c_u(x) \in [c_{min}, c_{max}] \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ so especially $c_u^{-1} \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$ and $k(\varphi, x) \in [k_{min}, k_{max}] \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}$

$$\begin{aligned} &= -2c_{max}^{-1}k_{min}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 2|u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla(c_u^{-1})|_{C^0k_{max}}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2} \\ &= -2c_{max}^{-1}k_{min}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + c_1|u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2} \end{aligned}$$

for $c_1 := 2|\nabla c_u^{-1}|_{C^0}k_{max}$ a constant.

Similarly, we get for q_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} q_2 &= 2\langle c_u^{-1}u_d(t), \nabla \cdot ((k^{(1)} - k^{(2)})\nabla u^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &= -2\langle u_d(t)\nabla(c_u^{-1}) + c_u^{-1}\nabla u_d(t), ((k^{(1)} - k^{(2)})\nabla u^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2} \end{aligned}$$

by corollary 16 which we can again do because $c_u^{-1}u_d(t) \in C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$,

$$\begin{aligned} &= -2\langle u_d(t)\nabla(c_u^{-1}), ((k^{(1)} - k^{(2)})\nabla u^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2} - 2\langle c_u^{-1}\nabla u_d(t), ((k^{(1)} - k^{(2)})\nabla u^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &\leq 2|u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla(c_u^{-1})|_{C^0}|k^{(1)}(t) - k^{(2)}(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla u^{(2)}(t)|_{C^0} + 2|c_u^{-1}|_{C^0}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|k^{(1)}(t) - k^{(2)}(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla u^{(2)}(t)|_{C^0} \end{aligned}$$

This looks more difficult, but because k is Lipschitz, we pointwise have that:

$$|k^{(1)}(t)(x) - k^{(2)}(t)(x)| = |k(\varphi^{(1)}(x, t), x, t) - k(\varphi^{(2)}(x, t), x, t)| \leq c_2|\varphi^{(1)}(x, t) - \varphi^{(2)}(x, t)| = c_2|\varphi_d(x, t)|$$

for some constant c_2 , which implies that:

$$|k^{(1)}(t) - k^{(2)}(t)|_{L^2} \leq c_2|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}$$

Estimating further by plugging this into the difficult looking estimate we obtain:

$$q_2 \leq 2|u_d(t)|_{L^2} |\nabla(c_u^{-1})|_{C^0} c_2 |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2} |\nabla u^{(2)}(t)|_{C^0} + 2|c_u^{-1}|_{C^0} |\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2} c_2 |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2} |\nabla u^{(2)}(t)|_{C^0}$$

so that because $|\nabla u^{(2)}(t)|_{C^0}$ is bounded in terms of a bound on the H_{a+2} -norms of the initial datums, as seen in the section on bounding solutions, and $|\nabla c_u|_{C^0}$ is just a constant, we get that:

$$q_2 \leq c_3 |u_d(t)|_{L^2} |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2} + c_4 |\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2} |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}$$

for some constants c_3, c_4 that depend on a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$.

For q_3 , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} q_3 &= -2 \langle c_u^{-1} u_d(t), c_\varphi (\varphi_t^{(1)} - \varphi_t^{(2)}) (t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &= -2 \langle c_u^{-1} u_d(t), c_\varphi (\lambda \Delta \varphi^{(1)} - W'(\varphi^{(1)}) + g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x)) (t) - (\lambda \Delta \varphi^{(2)} - W'(\varphi^{(2)}) + g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x)) (t) \rangle_{L^2} \end{aligned}$$

via plugging in the expressions for $\varphi_t^{(1)}, \varphi_t^{(2)}$ because we are considering solutions to our system

$$= -2 \langle c_u^{-1} c_\varphi u_d(t), (\lambda \Delta \varphi_d - (W'(\varphi^{(1)}) - W'(\varphi^{(2)})) + (g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) - g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x))) (t) \rangle_{L^2} = q'_3 + q''_3$$

for

$$q'_3 := -2 \langle c_u^{-1} c_\varphi u_d(t), \lambda \Delta \varphi_d(t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

and

$$q''_3 := -2 \langle c_u^{-1} c_\varphi u_d(t), - (W'(\varphi^{(1)}) - W'(\varphi^{(2)})) (t) + (g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) - g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x)) (t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

Now we first bound q''_3 , because it can be bounded very similarly to other terms we have bounded already. We have that:

$$q''_3 \leq 2|c_u^{-1} c_\varphi|_{C^0} |u_d(t)|_{L^2} | (W'(\varphi^{(1)}) - W'(\varphi^{(2)})) (t) + (g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) - g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x)) (t) |_{L^2}$$

Because W' and g are Lipschitz, like when bounding q_2 , we have that pointwise:

$$| (W'(\varphi^{(1)}) - W'(\varphi^{(2)})) (t)(x) + (g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) - g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x)) (t)(x) | \leq c_5 (|\varphi_d(x, t)| + |u_d(x, t)|)$$

So that also:

$$| (W'(\varphi^{(1)}) - W'(\varphi^{(2)})) (t)(x) + (g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) - g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x)) (t)(x) |_{L^2} \leq c_5 (|\varphi_d(x, t)|_{L^2} + |u_d(x, t)|_{L^2})$$

which then yields:

$$\begin{aligned} q''_3 &\leq 2c_5 |c_u^{-1} c_\varphi|_{C^0} |u_d(t)|_{L^2} |\varphi_d(x, t)|_{L^2} + 2c_5 |c_u^{-1} c_\varphi|_{C^0} |u_d(t)|_{L^2} |u_d(x, t)|_{L^2} \\ &= c_6 |u_d(t)|_{L^2} |\varphi_d(x, t)|_{L^2} + c_6 |u_d(t)|_{L^2} |u_d(x, t)|_{L^2} \end{aligned}$$

for $c_6 := 2c_5 |c_u^{-1} c_\varphi|_{C^0}$.

Now we bound q'_3 , we have:

$$q'_3 = -2 \langle c_u^{-1} c_\varphi u_d(t), \lambda \Delta \varphi_d(t) \rangle_{L^2}$$

$$= -2\langle (\nabla(c_u^{-1}c_\varphi))u_d(t) + c_u^{-1}c_\varphi\nabla u_d(t), \lambda\nabla\varphi_d \rangle_{L^2}$$

via partial integration, which we can do because $c_u^{-1}c_\varphi u_d(t) \in C_N^2(\overline{\Omega})$ via applying lemma 17 thrice,

$$\begin{aligned} &= -2\langle (\nabla(c_u^{-1}c_\varphi))u_d(t), \lambda\nabla\varphi_d \rangle_{L^2} - 2\langle \nabla u_d(t), \nabla\varphi_d \rangle_{\lambda c_u^{-1}c_\varphi} \\ &\leq 2|(\nabla(c_u^{-1}c_\varphi))|_{C^0}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}\lambda|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2} + 2|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}\lambda c_{min}^{-1}|c_\varphi|_{C^0} \\ &= c_7|u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2} + 2|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}\lambda c_{min}^{-1}|c_\varphi|_{C^0} \end{aligned}$$

for the constant $c_7 := 2|(\nabla(c_u^{-1}c_\varphi))|_{C^0}\lambda$.

9.1.3. *Extracting a simple bound on $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$.* Looking at the bounds for $q_1, q_2, q_3 = q_3' + q_3''$, we notice that we have two special summands, $-2c_{max}^{-1}k_{min}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$, which is the only “negative” summand in the bounds, and $2|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}\lambda c_{min}^{-1}|c_\varphi|_{C^0}$, which is the only “positive” summand that is the product of two L^2 -norms of gradients. Additionally, we have several summands of the form constant times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$, and of the form constant times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ times $|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}$, with the constants sometimes depending on a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$.

Now we would like to collect the summands of the form constant times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$, and of the form constant times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ times $|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}$, in one summand respectively, and we can actually do that, because every summand of the form c times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ can obviously be bounded by $c(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2$, and every summand of the form c times $|u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ times $|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}$ or $|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}$ can obviously be bounded by $c(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})(|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2})$.

Doing this, we obtain a bound on $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 &\leq -2c_{max}^{-1}k_{min}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 2|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}\lambda c_{min}^{-1}|c_\varphi|_{C^0} + c_8(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 \\ &\quad + c_9(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})(|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2}) \end{aligned}$$

for some constants c_8, c_9 that depend on a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$.

9.1.4. *Bounding with partial integration II - bounding $\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$.* Now we estimate $\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi(t)|_{L^2}^2$ basically analogously to q_3 , we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 &= 2\langle \varphi_d(t), (\varphi_t^{(1)} - \varphi_t^{(2)})(t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &= 2\langle \varphi_d(t), c_\varphi \left(\lambda\Delta\varphi^{(1)} - W'(\varphi^{(1)}) + g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) \right) (t) - \left(\lambda\Delta\varphi^{(2)} - W'(\varphi^{(2)}) + g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x) \right) (t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &= -2\lambda\langle \nabla\varphi_d(t), \nabla\varphi_d(t) \rangle_{L^2} + \langle \varphi_d(t), \left(-W'(\varphi^{(1)}) + g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) \right) (t) - \left(-W'(\varphi^{(2)}) + g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x) \right) (t) \rangle_{L^2} \\ &\leq -2\lambda\langle \nabla\varphi_d(t), \nabla\varphi_d(t) \rangle_{L^2} + |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2} \left(-W'(\varphi^{(1)}) + g(u^{(1)}, \varphi^{(1)}, x) \right) (t) - \left(-W'(\varphi^{(2)}) + g(u^{(2)}, \varphi^{(2)}, x) \right) (t) |_{L^2} \\ &\leq -2\lambda\langle \nabla\varphi_d(t), \nabla\varphi_d(t) \rangle_{L^2} + c_{10}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}(|u_d(t)|_{L^2} + |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) \\ &= -2\lambda|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + c_{10}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}|u_d(t)|_{L^2} + c_9|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2} \end{aligned}$$

for some constant c_{10} , because W', g are Lipschitz.

Bounding $c_{10}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}|u_d(t)|_{L^2} + c_{10}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}$ by $2c_{10}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2$, we obtain:

$$\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq -2\lambda|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 2c_{10}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2$$

9.1.5. *Bounding a suitable linear combination of $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ and $\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$.* Now we would like to add the inequalities for $\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$ and $\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$, we “normalize” the first one, that is we divide it by the positive quantity $2c_{max}^{-1}k_{min}$ so that its negative term has -1 as constant in front of it, and we take the second one to be “normalized” the same way by dividing it by a positive constant so that its negative term has -1 as constant in front of it, but then times a positive parameter β to be chosen later so that we can remove the $c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\lambda c_{min}^{-1}|c_\varphi|_{C^0}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}$ -term from the first inequality using one half of the negative terms, we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + \beta\frac{1}{2}\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq -|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 - \beta|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}^2$$

$+c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\lambda c_{min}^{-1}|c_\varphi|_{C^0}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2} + c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 + c_{12}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})(|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2})$ with the $c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2$ -term collecting the $c_i(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2$ -terms of both equations, so c_{11} is a constant depending on a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$ and on β .

Defining the special obviously positive constant $\gamma := c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\lambda c_{min}^{-1} = \frac{\lambda c_{max}}{k_{min}c_{min}}$ we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + \beta\frac{1}{2}\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq -|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 - \beta|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}^2$$

$$+\gamma|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2} + c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 + c_{12}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})(|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2})$$

which can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + \beta\frac{1}{2}\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq -|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 - \beta|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2}^2$$

$$+\frac{1}{10}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) + c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 + c_{12}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})(|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2})$$

now we fix $\beta := (10\gamma)^2$ so β is now constant, and c_{11} is now just a constant depending on a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$, and obtain, applying the Young inequality for products:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq -|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 - (10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2$$

$$+\frac{1}{10}\left(\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2})^2\right) + c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 + c_{12}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})(|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2})$$

Now obviously, we have that:

$$\frac{1}{10}\left(\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2})^2\right) + \frac{1}{2}\left(-|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 - (10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2\right) \leq 0$$

so we can use half of $-|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 - (10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2$ to remove the $\frac{1}{10}\left(\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2})^2\right)$ -term, and obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq -\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 - \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2$$

$$+c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 + c_{12}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})(|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2})$$

for some constants c_{10}, c_{12} depending on a bound on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$.

Now essentially because all norms on \mathbb{R}^2 are equivalent, and $(y_1, y_2) \mapsto \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2}$ is a norm on \mathbb{R}^2 , and $(y_1, y_2) \mapsto |y_1| + |y_2|$ is a norm on \mathbb{R}^2 too, we can bound, for some positive constant c_{13} :

$$|\nabla u|_{L^2} + |\nabla\varphi|_{L^2} = \|\nabla u|_{L^2}\| + \|\nabla\varphi|_{L^2}\| \leq c_{13}\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2}$$

plugging this into our equation, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 &\leq -\left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2}\right)^2 \\ &+ c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 + c_{12}c_{13}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2} \end{aligned}$$

which we can further rewrite as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 &\leq c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 \\ &+ \left(c_{12}c_{13}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2}) - \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2}\right)\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}|\nabla u_d|_{L^2}^2 + \frac{1}{2}(10\gamma|\nabla\varphi_d|_{L^2})^2} \end{aligned}$$

now purely algebraically, the term in the second line has the form $(y - z)z$, which is a parabola that is opened downwards in z , with maximum at $z = \frac{y}{2}$, and maximal value $\frac{1}{4}y^2$. Applying this estimate to the term on the second line, we get the bound:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq c_{11}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2 + \frac{1}{4}(c_{12}c_{13}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2}))^2$$

which, setting $c_{14} := c_{11} + \frac{1}{4}c_{12}^2c_{13}^2$ a constant that depends on $|u_0|_{H_{a+2}}$ can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq c_{14}(|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2})^2$$

Now again essentially because all norms on \mathbb{R}^2 are equivalent, we have:

$$|u|_{L^2} + |\varphi|_{L^2} = \||u|_{L^2}\| + \||\varphi|_{L^2}\| \leq c_{15}\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2}$$

plugging this into our previous estimate, we get that:

$$\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}\frac{d}{dt}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 \leq c_{14}\left(c_{15}\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2}\right)^2$$

which we can, setting $c_{16} := c_{14}c_{15}^2$ and using the linearity of $\frac{d}{dt}$, rewrite as:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2\right) \leq c_{16}\left(\frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2\right)$$

But this means that for $y := \frac{1}{2}c_{max}k_{min}^{-1}|u_d(t)|_{L^2}^2 + 5\gamma\lambda^{-1}|\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}^2$, we get the differential inequality:

$$\frac{d}{dt}y \leq c_{16}y$$

on (T_1, T_2) , so that by Gronwalls lemma, we obtain that:

$$y(t) \leq e^{c_{16}t} y(T_1) \leq c_{17} y(T_1)$$

for $c_{17} := \max_{t \in [T_1, T_2]} e^{c_{16}t}$, so that because $y(t)$ is nonnegative also:

$$\sqrt{y(t)} \leq c_{17} \sqrt{y(T_1)}$$

for all $t \in (T_1, T_2)$.

But looking at the definition of $y(t)$ we easily see that again essentially by the equivalence of norms on \mathbb{R}^2 , we have that there are positive constants such that:

$$\max(|u_d(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) \leq c_{18} \sqrt{y(t)}$$

and

$$\max(|u_d(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) \geq c_{19} \sqrt{y(t)}$$

so that we get, for all $t \in (T_1, T_2)$:

$$\max(|u_d(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) \leq c_{18} \sqrt{y(t)} \leq c_{17} c_{18} \sqrt{y(T_1)} \leq c_{17} c_{18} c_{19} \max(|u_d(T_1)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(T_1)|_{L^2})$$

which is, introducing a new constant $c_{20} := c_{17} c_{18} c_{19}$ that depends on a bound on $|u_{T_1}|_{H_{a+2}}$, and recognizing that $u_d(T_1) = u_{T_1}^{(1)} - u_{T_1}^{(2)}$ and $\varphi_d(T_1) = \varphi_{T_1}^{(1)} - \varphi_{T_1}^{(2)}$:

$$\forall t \in (T_1, T_2) : \max(|u_d(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) \leq c_{20} \max(|u_{T_1}^{(1)} - u_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{L^2}, |\varphi_{T_1}^{(1)} - \varphi_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{L^2})$$

which is our foundational well-posedness result we wanted to show, which we will now use to get uniqueness and well-posedness for higher regularity norms.

9.2. Showing the uniqueness claim of the theorem. Firstly, we notice that, if $u_{T_1}^{(1)} = u_{T_1}^{(2)}$ and $\varphi_{T_1}^{(1)} = \varphi_{T_1}^{(2)}$, we have $\max(|u_{T_1}^{(1)} - u_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{L^2}, |\varphi_{T_1}^{(1)} - \varphi_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{L^2}) = 0$, so our foundational well-posedness result yields that:

$$\forall t \in (T_1, T_2) : \max(|u_d(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}) \leq 0$$

implying that $|u_d(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi_d(t)|_{L^2}$ are 0 on (T_1, T_2) , which, because they are continuous functions, implies $u_d(t), \varphi_d(t) = 0$ on (T_1, T_2) , which in turn implies $u_d = 0, \varphi_d = 0$ on their whole domain $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ which implies $u^{(1)} = u^{(2)}$ and $\varphi^{(1)} = \varphi^{(2)}$.

So we firstly get uniqueness, if we have two solutions to the same initial data, they are the same, and consequently, since we already have existence, there always is a unique solution to our system.

Notice that we didn't need to assume that the solutions were additionally in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, so as in the uniqueness claim we want to show, there is a unique strong solution with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial conditions u_{T_1}, φ_{T_1} to the system equation (5.1), equation (5.2) in the sense of definition 9, even when one includes solutions that are not in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

So to complete our proof of the uniqueness claim, we only have to show that the unique solution furthermore has $u, \varphi \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, but this is obviously the case, because our existence result guaranteed us the existence of a solution with $u, \varphi \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

9.3. Showing the well posedness claim of the theorem. Now that we have shown the uniqueness claim, and hence especially have uniqueness of solutions, it is time to show the well-posedness claim, concluding the proof of the theorem.

Concretely, we will show that, as claimed in the theorem, if $u_{T_1}^n, \varphi_{T_1}^n \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$ are sequences of initial datums that converge to $u_{T_1}^{lim}, \varphi_{T_1}^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm, $u^{(n)}, \varphi^{(n)}$ is the unique solution to the system for initial data $u_{T_1}^n, \varphi_{T_1}^n$, and u^{lim}, φ^{lim} is the unique solution to the system for initial data $u_{T_1}^{lim}, \varphi_{T_1}^{lim}$, we have that $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ and $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm.

In order to prove this, we consider, as in the well posedness claim, arbitrary sequences $u_{T_1}^n, \varphi_{T_1}^n \in H_{a+2}(\Omega) \cap C_N^2(\bar{\Omega})$ of initial datums that converge to $u_{T_1}^{lim}, \varphi_{T_1}^{lim}$, and show that for the $u^{(n)}, \varphi^{(n)}$ and u^{lim}, φ^{lim} we indeed have $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ and $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm.

9.3.1. Getting L^1 -convergence from the weak well posedness result. Immediately showing $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ and $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm would be at least very difficult, so we first show $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ and $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ in the L^1 -norm, then upgrade this via corollary 29 to convergence in H_a , which we then, via theorem 19, upgrade to convergence in H_{a+2}

Now because the H_{a+2} -norm is obviously at least as strong as the C^0 -norm which is at least as strong as (actually much stronger than) the L^2 -norm as we already know, we of course have that since $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ and $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm, also $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ and $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ in the L^2 -norm, so especially:

$$\max \left(|u_{T_1}^{(n)} - u_{T_1}^{lim}|_{L^2}, |\varphi_{T_1}^{(n)} - \varphi_{T_1}^{lim}|_{L^2} \right) \rightarrow 0$$

and then also, via our foundational well-posedness result:

$$\forall t \in (T_1, T_2) : \max(|u^{(n)}(t) - u^{lim}(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi^{(n)}(t) - \varphi^{lim}(t)|_{L^2}) \leq c_{20} \max \left(|u_{T_1}^{(1)} - u_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{L^2}, |\varphi_{T_1}^{(1)} - \varphi_{T_1}^{(2)}|_{L^2} \right) \rightarrow 0$$

so via the Sandwichlemma, we have that:

$$\max(|u^{(n)}(t) - u^{lim}(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi^{(n)}(t) - \varphi^{lim}(t)|_{L^2}) \rightarrow 0$$

But then also:

$$\begin{aligned} |u^{(n)} - u^{lim}|_{L^1} &= \int_{\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)} |u^{(n)} - u^{lim}| = \int_{(T_1, T_2)} \left(\int_{\Omega} |u^{(n)}(t) - u^{lim}(t)| \right) dt = \int_{(T_1, T_2)} |u^{(n)}(t) - u^{lim}(t)|_{L^1} dt \\ &\leq \int_{(T_1, T_2)} c_{21} |u^{(n)}(t) - u^{lim}(t)|_{L^2} dt \end{aligned}$$

for some positive constant c_{21} via the well-known fact that the L^2 -norm is at least as strong as (actually stronger than) the L^1 -norm

$$\leq c_{21}(T_2 - T_1) \max_{t \in (T_1, T_2)} |u^{(n)}(t) - u^{lim}(t)|_{L^2}$$

which goes to zero since $\forall t \in (T_1, T_2) : \max(|u^{(n)}(t) - u^{lim}(t)|_{L^2}, |\varphi^{(n)}(t) - \varphi^{lim}(t)|_{L^2})$ goes to zero, so $|u^{(n)} - u^{lim}|_{L^1} \rightarrow 0$, we have that:

$$u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$$

in the L^1 -norm.

Completely analogously, we get that:

$$|\varphi^{(n)} - \varphi^{lim}|_{L^1} \leq c_{21}(T_2 - T_1) \max_{t \in (T_1, T_2)} |\varphi^{(n)}(t) - \varphi^{lim}(t)|_{L^2} \rightarrow 0$$

and hence:

$$\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$$

in the L^1 -norm.

9.3.2. *Upgrading to H_a well posedness.* Furthermore, we have that because $u_0^{(n)}$ and $\varphi_n^{(n)}$ are convergent sequences in the H_{a+2} -norm, the $u_0^{(n)}$ and $\varphi_n^{(n)}$ are bounded (independently of n) in the H_{a+2} -norm. Via theorem 37 this automatically yields that the $u^{(n)}$ and $\varphi^{(n)}$ are bounded (independently of n) in the H_{a+2} -norm as well, so especially, $\partial_t u^{(n)}$, $\partial_t \varphi^{(n)}$, $\nabla u^{(n)}$, $\nabla \varphi^{(n)}$ are bounded pointwise independently of n , so the total derivatives of the $u^{(n)}$ and $\varphi^{(n)}$ are bounded pointwise independently of n as well, so that, because $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ is Lipschitz, the $u^{(n)}$ and $\varphi^{(n)}$ are Lipschitz with bounded Lipschitz constants as well.

But then, we have that:

$$u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}, \varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$$

and that the $u^{(n)}$ and $\varphi^{(n)}$ have bounded Lipschitz constants, so corollary 29 is applicable and yields that:

$$u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}, \varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$$

in the H_a -norm.

9.3.3. *Upgrading to H_{a+2} well posedness.* Now that we have solution convergence in the H_a -norm, we can upgrade via lemma 23 and corollary 20. Firstly we have that, via lemma 23 :

$$-W'(\varphi^{(n)}) + g(u^{(n)}, \varphi^{(n)}, x) \rightarrow -W'(\varphi^{lim}) + g(u^{lim}, \varphi^{lim}, x)$$

in H_a , and therefore, because $\varphi^{(n)}$ solves:

$$\varphi_t^{(n)} = \lambda \Delta \varphi - W'(\varphi^{(n)}) + g(u^{(n)}, \varphi^{(n)}, x)$$

with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial conditions $\varphi_0^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi_0^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm, via corollary 20, that also:

$$\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$$

where we know that the $\varphi^{(n)}$ and φ^{lim} are actually the unique solutions with $\varphi^{(n)} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and $\varphi^{lim} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ considered in corollary 20, and not for example hypothetical other solutions that are not in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, because we have already shown that the unique solution to our system always has $u, \varphi \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ as part of the already proven uniqueness claim, so the $\varphi^{(n)}$ and φ^{lim} are all in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

in H_{a+2} , so we especially now have the required convergence for $\varphi^{(n)}$.

But then especially also:

$$\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}, \nabla \varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \nabla \varphi^{lim}, \varphi_t^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi_t^{lim}$$

in the H_a -norm, so that $u^{(n)}$ is a solution to that equivalent formulation for the PDE for u from the existence section:

$$u_t^{(n)} = \tilde{k}_n(x, t) \Delta u + b_{n,i}(x, t) \cdot \nabla u^{(n)} + f_n$$

with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, initial data $u_0^{(n)}$ that converges to u_0^{lim} in H_{a+2} , and:

- $\tilde{k}_n(x, t) = \frac{k(\varphi^{(n)}, x)}{c_u(x)} \rightarrow \frac{k(\varphi^{lim}, x)}{c_u(x)} = \tilde{k}^{lim}(x, t)$

- $b_{n,i}(x, t) = \left(\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\varphi^{(n)}, x)}{c_u(x)} \nabla \varphi^{(n)} + \frac{1}{c_u(x)} (\nabla_x k)(\varphi^{(n)}, x) \right)_i \rightarrow \left(\frac{(\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} k)(\varphi^{lim}, x)}{c_u(x)} \nabla \varphi^{lim} + \frac{1}{c_u(x)} (\nabla_x k)(\tilde{\varphi}^{lim}, x) \right)_i = b_{lim,i}(x, t)$ for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$
- $f_n(x, t) = -\frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)} \varphi_t^{(n)} \rightarrow -\frac{c_\varphi(x)}{c_u(x)} \varphi_t^{lim} = f_{lim}(x, t)$

in the H_a -norm via repeated application of lemma 23 building upon

$$\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}, \nabla \varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \nabla \varphi^{lim}, \varphi_t^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi_t^{lim}$$

in the H_a -norm.

But then we can apply corollary 20 again, and obtain that also:

$$u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$$

in the H_{a+2} -norm, as claimed, knowing again that the $u^{(n)}$ and u^{lim} are actually the unique solutions with $u^{(n)} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ and $u^{lim} \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ considered in corollary 20, and not for example hypothetical other solutions that are not in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$, because we have already shown that the unique solution to our system always has $u, \varphi \in H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ as part of the already proven uniqueness claim, so the $u^{(n)}$ and u^{lim} are all in $H_{a+2}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$.

But now we have $\varphi^{(n)} \rightarrow \varphi^{lim}$ and $u^{(n)} \rightarrow u^{lim}$ in the H_{a+2} -norm, so we have proven the conclusion of the well posedness claim under the preconditions from the claim, proving the well posedness claim, and concluding the proof of the theorem.

10. DISCUSSION

In this treatise our main aim was to do two things, show strong existence and well posedness results for a novel system that is especially suitable to model inhomogeneous materials with thermal properties that change with phase, which we did, and to do that in a way that is systematic, rigorous and works with strong solutions, which we partially achieved, rigorously proving most important parts of the argument and working basically only with strong solutions, and presenting some selected techniques for working with parabolic PDEs systematically.

However, for the smoothing result, we required a standard yet quite advanced and very technical argument that we, due to the limited scope of this treatise, could only sketch. In general, it seems like some fundamental results, which for Dirichlet boundary conditions can be found in some form in [LSU], are hard to find, even for homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, suggesting that there is a noticeable gap in the toolkit for solving parabolic PDEs with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, unless one is fine with proof sketches.

Therefore, it seems like thoroughly proving the pendants to the fundamental results for Dirichlet boundary conditions might actually be an overlooked yet possibly very impactful research direction in the field of parabolic PDEs.

Lastly, the unexpected bounds to continuity result, Kais free lunch theorem, suggests that very generally applicable metaresults like the characterization of continuous linear functions on normed spaces as bounded linear functions might be another promising research direction.

11. APPENDIX

11.1. The boundedness to continuity theorem. Working on the existence proof for a quasilinear parabolic PDE via Schaefer's fixed point theorem, I found myself essentially using a solution operator for semilinear parabolic PDEs with variable coefficient functions.

Now I had found a paper yielding existence and uniqueness of solutions, and bounds on the same, but for applying the Schaefer fixed point theorem, I needed continuity in the coefficient functions in a certain sense as well.

Indeed, when solving quasilinear PDEs with fixed point theorems, employing solution operators for linear PDEs with variable coefficient functions, one basically always needs continuity of the solution in the coefficient functions in a certain sense.

Furthermore, also from a physical standpoint, the continuity of solutions in the coefficient functions is quite important, because when modelling physical systems, the coefficient functions are basically always approximations of some physical quantities, and hence it would be bad if arbitrarily small approximation errors in the coefficient functions would potentially yield big changes in the model predictions.

Now after a while, and some attempts to show continuity in the parameters differently, I figured out that it actually essentially follows from the boundedness results via a quite trivial trick which we'll now illustrate on a simple example, we will purposefully omit stating the necessary technical assumptions, identifying the considered norms etc., in this quick sketch, in order to focus on the core idea, the rigorous argument follows later:

Lets say we have a PDE $a_1 \partial^{\alpha_1} u + \dots + a_m \partial^{\alpha_m} u = f$ on some suitable function space possibly encoding some homogeneous boundary conditions.

Lets further say we know that for suitable coefficient and source functions, this PDE always has at least one solution, and all solutions and their relevant partial derivatives are bounded in a suitable sense, in terms of bounds, in a suitable sense, on the coefficient functions and the source function.

One easily sees that firstly, this implies that solutions have to be unique, because for fixed coefficients and source terms, the solution space is an affine space, and bounded by our assumption, and every bounded affine space contains exactly one point.

But actually we even get a quite strong continuity result. Given convergent sequences a_1^n, \dots, a_m^n of coefficient functions with limits $a_1^{lim}, \dots, a_m^{lim}$, and a convergent sequence f_n of source terms with limit f_{lim} we can show that the corresponding unique solutions converge as well:

Crucially, we note that, denoting by u_n the solution to $a_1^n \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots + a_m^n \partial^{\alpha_m} u_n = f_n$, and by u_{lim} the solution to $a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} u_{lim} + \dots + a_m^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_m} u_{lim} = f_{lim}$, we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} & (a_1^n \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots + a_m^n \partial^{\alpha_m} u_n) - (a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} u_{lim} + \dots + a_m^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_m} u_{lim}) = f_n - f_{lim} \\ \Leftrightarrow & (a_1^n \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots) - (a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots) + (a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots) - (a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} u_{lim} + \dots) = f_n - f_{lim} \\ \Leftrightarrow & (a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} (u_n - u_{lim}) + \dots) = f_n - f_{lim} - ((a_1^n - a_1^{lim}) \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots) \end{aligned}$$

So that $d_n := u_n - u_{lim}$ fulfills our PDE for the fixed coefficient functions $a_1^{lim}, \dots, a_m^{lim}$, with:

$$h_n := f_n - f_{lim} - ((a_1^n - a_1^{lim}) \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots)$$

that is we have with this h_n :

$$a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} d_n + \dots + a_m^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_m} d_n = h_n$$

this is the very trivial trick, it's really just a simple algebraic rearrangement, however one with huge consequences, because it fixes the coefficient functions, so one only has to deal with a variable source term.

Now for the then fixed coefficients, the solution d_n to:

$$a_1^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_1} d_n + \dots + a_m^{lim} \partial^{\alpha_m} d_n = h_n$$

has to depend linearly on the h_n , and via our assumed bounds, we also get that, fixing the coefficients, the solution operator is a bounded linear functional in the source term, and hence continuous.

But then we have that $d_n \rightarrow 0$ if $h_n \rightarrow 0$, and indeed, if multiplication is suitably well behaved with respect to the considered norms, we have that $h_n \rightarrow 0$, because:

$$h_n = f_n - f_{lim} - ((a_1^n - a_1^{lim}) \partial^{\alpha_1} u_n + \dots)$$

and:

- $f_n - f_{lim} \rightarrow 0$
- $a_1^n - a_1^{lim} \rightarrow 0$
- $\partial^{\alpha_1} u_n$ is a bounded sequence because the a_i^n , and the f_n are convergent sequences and hence bounded, and we have assumed that the relevant partial derivatives of our solutions are bounded in terms of bounds on the coefficients and source terms.

So we get that $d_n = u_n - u_{lim} \rightarrow 0$, and hence that the solutions u_n converge to the solution u_{lim} , so that the solution operator is continuous in the usual sense that if one plugs in convergent coefficient and source term sequences, one gets convergent solution sequences with the right limit out.

11.1.1. *The generality of this approach - old trick, new application.* One very interesting thing about this calculation is that it doesn't depend on the "type" of the considered PDE at all, but simply immediately works for all PDEs of the form $a_1 \partial^{\alpha_1} u + \dots + a_m \partial^{\alpha_m} u = f$, regardless of whether they are elliptic, hyperbolic, parabolic or neither, so it especially works for linear heat equations, scalar wave equations, Schrödinger equations, and electrostatic equations like Poisson's equation and Laplace's equation.

Furthermore, this calculation can obviously also be carried out pretty much analogously for systems of multiple equations of the form $a_1 \partial^{\alpha_1} u_{i_1} + \dots + a_m \partial^{\alpha_m} u_{i_m} = f$, where u is now vector-valued, so for example for the Maxwell equations.

All in all, one could say that the calculation is basically applicable to all the core linear PDEs from mathematical physics.

Furthermore, one finds that the concrete structure of function multiplication, beyond bilinearity and boundedness as bilinear operator, and the structure of the partial derivatives was not used at all, one can replace the classical partial derivatives by any linear operators, for example weak derivatives or more exotic linear operators like convolutions with fixed kernels, and the multiplications with any bilinear form that is bounded with respect to the considered norms, for example convolution, and the calculation still works.

Also, one finds that one didn't use metric completeness at all, so one can work on normed vectorspaces instead of Banachspaces.

Additionally, as we'll see in the following, one can easily incorporate affine linear boundary conditions, like Dirichlet boundary conditions $u|_{\partial\Omega} = f_{\partial\Omega}$ or Neumann boundary conditions $\partial_n u = f_{\partial\Omega}$, with given "boundary functions" $f_{\partial\Omega}$, into the calculation.

Lastly, one finds that instead of considering sequences directly, one can basically use the same calculation on two solutions u_1, u_2 for different data to get local Lipschitz continuity of the solution operator in a specific sense, which is easily seen to imply the continuity result, and is valuable if one wants to use the solution operator in conjunction with the Banach fixed point theorem, because one needs contractions in order to apply it.

Now of course, as expected, the core trick has been "rediscovered" multiple times as it is a quite trivial trick with such broad applicability, if one can even consider such a trivial transformation a "discovery". For example, this technique has been used to deal with elliptic operators with varying coefficients in scientific computing and to deal with resolvents in functional analysis.

However, quite unexpectedly, it seems to always be used in some topic specific proof, rather than being recognized as the very broadly applicable technique that it is and accordingly being cast into a super broadly applicable metatheorem.

To remedy this issue, I propose a very general version of this "bounds to local Lipschitz continuity of the solution operator" argument, encapsulated as a very general "metatheorem":

11.1.2. *The general theorem.* Considering:

- instead of normed function spaces on the domain and the boundary arbitrary normed vectorspaces $V, V_{i,j}, W_{i,j}, W_{i,j}^c, W_i, \tilde{V}_i, \tilde{W}_i$ (not even necessarily Banach), where the $V_{i,j}, \tilde{V}_i \subseteq V$ and $W_{i,j}, W_{i,j}^c, W_i$ model function spaces, for example $C^{k+\alpha}$ or $W^{k,p}$ -spaces, on the domain, and the \tilde{W}_i model function spaces on the boundary,
- instead of partial derivatives or other differential operators arbitrary linear operators (not even necessarily bounded with respect to the norms) $L_{i,j} : V_{i,j} \rightarrow W_{i,j}$, defined on the respective subspaces $V_{i,j} \subseteq V$ modelling function spaces providing sufficient differentiability,
- instead of affine linear boundary conditions, like inhomogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions $u|_{\partial\Omega} = f_{\partial\Omega}$ or inhomogeneous Neumann boundary conditions $\partial_n u = f_{\partial\Omega}$ (homogeneous boundary conditions can be modelled by restricting V to the functions where the boundary conditions hold), arbitrary linear equations $\tilde{L}_i u = \tilde{f}_i$, with $\tilde{L}_i : \tilde{V}_i \rightarrow \tilde{W}_i$ modelling the “boundary operator” (which could for example be mapping the function to its restriction to the boundary, or to its normal derivative on the boundary, etc.), \tilde{V}_i modelling the space of functions where the “boundary operator” is well-defined, and \tilde{W}_i modelling the space of admissible “boundary functions” (that is admissible values of $u|_{\partial\Omega}$ at the boundary or admissible values of $\partial_n u$ at the boundary etc.),

we get the following very general theorem for, given a very general class of existence and boundedness results for a priori not even unique solutions to parametrized linear PDEs like $\sum_{i \in I} a_i(x, t) \partial^{\alpha_i} u(x, t) = f_1$ with affine linear boundary conditions, obtaining:

- a uniqueness result,
- a certain kind of local Lipschitz continuity of solutions in all parameters, that is in all coefficient functions, source terms and boundary functions,
- directly following from that local Lipschitz continuity result, of course also a certain kind of global continuity of the solution operator in all parameters,

essentially showing that for basically any linear PDE with variable coefficient functions, it is sufficient to bound solutions sufficiently well, as uniqueness of solutions and good continuity properties of the solution operator, even in the coefficient functions, automatically follow:

Theorem 39. (*Kais free lunch theorem*)

Let $\mathbb{K} \in \{\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}\}$ and in the following, write vector space for \mathbb{K} vector space.

Let V be a normed vector space with norm $|\cdot|_V$ and I, \tilde{I} be some finite index sets.

For each $i \in I$ let:

- W_i be a normed vector space with norm $|\cdot|_{W_i}$,
- J_i be a finite index set.

For each (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$ let:

- $V_{i,j} \subseteq V$ be a subvectorspace of V ,
- $W_{i,j}$ be a normed vectorspace with norm $|\cdot|_{W_{i,j}}$,
- $W_{i,j}^c$ be a normed vectorspace with norm $|\cdot|_{W_{i,j}^c}$,
- $L_{i,j} : V_{i,j} \rightarrow W_{i,j}$ be a linear function,
- $*_{i,j} : W_{i,j}^c \times W_{i,j} \rightarrow W_i$ be a bounded bilinear form, that is a bilinear form with $\forall w_1 \in W_{i,j}^c, w_2 \in W_{i,j} : |w_1 *_{i,j} w_2|_{W_i} \leq c_{i,j} |w_1|_{W_{i,j}^c} |w_2|_{W_{i,j}}$ for some $c_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, and $c_{i,j}$ be such a $c_{i,j}$,
- $D_{i,j} \subseteq W_{i,j}^c$ be an arbitrary subset of $W_{i,j}^c$.

For each $i \in \tilde{I}$ let:

- $\tilde{V}_i \subseteq V$ be a subvectorspace of V ,
- \tilde{W}_i be a normed vector space with norm $|\cdot|_{\tilde{W}_i}$,

- $\tilde{L}_i : \tilde{V}_i \rightarrow \tilde{W}_i$ be a linear function.

Assuming that given:

- some arbitrary $f_i \in W_i$ for each $i \in I$,
- some arbitrary $a_{i,j} \in D_{i,j} \subseteq W_{i,j}^c$ for each (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$,
- some arbitrary $\tilde{f}_i \in \tilde{W}_i$ for each $i \in \tilde{I}$,

there always are one or more vectors $u \in V$ such that:

$$u \in \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \bigcap_{j \in J_i} V_{i,j} \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i \in \tilde{I}} \tilde{V}_i \right)$$

that satisfy:

$$\forall i \in I : \sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j} *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u = f_i$$

and

$$\forall i \in \tilde{I} : \tilde{L}_i u = \tilde{f}_i$$

and that there are a function $b_V : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and for each (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$ functions $b_{i,j} : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, with the b_V and the $b_{i,j}$ all independent of the $a_{i,j}$, the f_i , the \tilde{f}_i and u of course, such that such vectors u always fulfill:

$$|u|_V \leq b_V(B_{data})$$

and

$$\forall i \in I : \forall j \in J_i : |L_{i,j} u|_{W_i} \leq b_{i,j}(B_{data})$$

for any bound $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ on the data, that is any $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ with:

$$B_{data} \geq \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}|_{W_{i,j}^c})$$

then for any given selection of the $f_i \in W_i$, $a_{i,j} \in D_{i,j}$ and $\tilde{f}_i \in \tilde{W}_i$, the vector $u \in V$ fulfilling:

$$u \in \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \bigcap_{j \in J_i} V_{i,j} \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i \in \tilde{I}} \tilde{V}_i \right)$$

and

$$\forall i \in I : \sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j} *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u = f_i$$

and

$$\forall i \in \tilde{I} : \tilde{L}_i u = \tilde{f}_i$$

which obviously exists by our assumptions, is unique, so we can define $Sol(\{a_{i,j}\}, \{f_i\}, \{\tilde{f}_i\})$ as this unique u for the respective indexed collections $\{a_{i,j}\}, \{f_i\}, \{\tilde{f}_i\}$ of the $a_{i,j}$, the f_i and the \tilde{f}_i considered. Furthermore, this vector $Sol(\{a_{i,j}\}, \{f_i\}, \{\tilde{f}_i\})$ depends locally Lipschitz continuously on the $a_{i,j}$, the f_i and the \tilde{f}_i , that is $Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{f_i^1\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^1\})$ is locally Lipschitz continuous, in the sense that if we consider:

- some arbitrary $f_i^1, f_i^2 \in W_i$ for each $i \in I$,
- some arbitrary $a_{i,j}^1, a_{i,j}^2 \in D_{i,j} \subseteq W_{i,j}^c$ for each (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$,
- some arbitrary $\tilde{f}_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^2 \in \tilde{W}_i$ for each $i \in \tilde{I}$,

and let $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ be some bound on the data in the usual sense, that is, some $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ with:

$$B_{data} \geq \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i^1|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i^1|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^1|_{W_{i,j}^c})$$

and

$$B_{data} \geq \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i^2|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i^2|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^2|_{W_{i,j}^c})$$

we always have, for $u_1 := Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{f_i^1\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^1\})$, $u_2 := Sol(\{a_{i,j}^2\}, \{f_i^2\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^2\})$, that:

$$|u_1 - u_2|_V \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$$

and

$$|L_{i,j}u|_{W_{i,j}} \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$$

for

$$d_{max} := \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i^1 - f_i^2|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i^1 - \tilde{f}_i^2|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2|_{W_{i,j}^c})$$

with some constant $C(B_{data}) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ depending on B_{data} but otherwise independent of $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and of course also of u_1 and u_2 .

Additionally, if $b_V(B_{data})$ and the $b_{i,j}(B_{data})$ are, as functions of B_{data} , polynomial with degree at most d , $C(B_{data})$ can be chosen polynomial as well, with degree at most d^2 .

Furthermore, one especially also gets that $Sol(\{a_{i,j}\}, \{f_i\}, \{\tilde{f}_i\})$ is continuous in all its parameters in a very standard and useful sense, concretely, if we pick:

- for each $i \in I$ an arbitrary convergent sequence $(f_i^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in W_i , with convergence understood in the $|\cdot|_{W_i}$ -norm,
- for each (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$ an arbitrary convergent sequence $(a_{i,j}^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $D_{i,j} \subseteq W_{i,j}^c$ with limit in $D_{i,j}$, with convergence understood in the $|\cdot|_{W_{i,j}^c}$ -norm,
- for each $i \in \tilde{I}$ an arbitrary convergent sequence $(\tilde{f}_i^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in \tilde{W}_i , with convergence understood in the $|\cdot|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ -norm,

and define, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $u_n := Sol(\{a_{i,j}^n\}, \{f_i^n\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^n\})$, we have that:

$$u_n \rightarrow u_{lim}$$

with respect to the $|\cdot|_V$ -norm, and for all (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$:

$$L_{i,j}u_n \rightarrow L_{i,j}u_{lim}$$

with respect to the respective $|\cdot|_{W_i}$ -norm, for $u_{lim} := Sol(\{a_{i,j}^{lim}\}, \{f_i^{lim}\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^{lim}\})$, with the $a_{i,j}^{lim}, f_i^{lim}$ and \tilde{f}_i^{lim} defined via:

- $a_{i,j}^{lim} := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{i,j}^n$ with respect to the $|\cdot|_{W_{i,j}^c}$ -norm for all i, j such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$,
- $f_i^{lim} := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_i^n$ with respect to the $|\cdot|_{W_i}$ -norm for all $i \in I$,
- $\tilde{f}_i^{lim} := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{f}_i^n$ with respect to the $|\cdot|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ -norm for all $i \in \tilde{I}$.

Proof. First we prove the uniqueness property claimed especially justifying the $Sol(\{a_{i,j}\}, \{f_i\}, \{\tilde{f}_i\})$ -notation, then we prove the Lipschitz continuity property claimed, then the addition that if $b_V(B_{data})$ and the $b_{i,j}(B_{data})$ are polynomial with degree at most d , $C(B_{data})$ can be chosen polynomial as well, with degree at most d^2 , and then we use the then proven Lipschitz continuity property to prove the continuity property claimed, concluding the proof.

In order to prove the uniqueness property, we simply note that if $u_1, u_2 \in V$ are different solutions to:

$$u \in \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \bigcap_{j \in J_i} V_{i,j} \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i \in \tilde{I}} \tilde{V}_i \right)$$

and

$$\forall i \in I : \sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j} *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u = f_i$$

and

$$\forall i \in \tilde{I} : \tilde{L}_i u = \tilde{f}_i$$

then $d := u_1 - u_2 \neq 0$ obviously fulfills:

$$d \in \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \bigcap_{j \in J_i} V_{i,j} \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i \in \tilde{I}} \tilde{V}_i \right)$$

and

$$\forall i \in I : \sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j} *_{i,j} L_{i,j} d = 0$$

and

$$\forall i \in \tilde{I} : \tilde{L}_i d = 0$$

so that for any $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}$, we have that $v_\lambda := u_1 + \lambda d$ still fulfills:

$$v_\lambda \in \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \bigcap_{j \in J_i} V_{i,j} \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i \in \tilde{I}} \tilde{V}_i \right)$$

and

$$\forall i \in I : \sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j} *_{i,j} L_{i,j} v_\lambda = f_i$$

and

$$\forall i \in \tilde{I} : \tilde{L}_i v_\lambda = \tilde{f}_i$$

but the set $\{v_\lambda = u_1 + \lambda d : \lambda \in \mathbb{K}\}$ with $d \neq 0$ is obviously a nontrivial affine subspace of V , and hence unbounded, a contradiction to the assumption that for any vector $u \in V$ that fulfills that system, so especially all v_λ :

$$|v_\lambda|_V \leq b_V(B_{data})$$

for any bound $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ on the data, that is any $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ with:

$$B_{data} \geq \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}|_{W_{i,j}})$$

because we can obviously pick

$$B_{data} := \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}|_{W_{i,j}})$$

and would get that all the v_λ are bounded by a constant.

Therefore, our solution u actually has to be unique, essentially by the well-known fact that any affine space that is bounded contains exactly one point. Especially, the $Sol(\{a_{i,j}\}, \{f_i\}, \{\tilde{f}_i\})$ -notation is justified.

In order to prove the Lipschitz continuity property claimed, we now consider arbitrary $u_1 := Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{f_i^1\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^1\})$, $u_2 := Sol(\{a_{i,j}^2\}, \{f_i^2\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^2\})$ and an arbitrary bound $B_{data} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ with:

$$B_{data} \geq \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i^1|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i^1|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^1|_{W_{i,j}^c})$$

and

$$B_{data} \geq \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i^2|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i^2|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^2|_{W_{i,j}^c})$$

as in the theorem, and prove that there is a constant $C(B_{data}) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ dependent on B_{data} but otherwise independent of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and of course also of u_1 and u_2 such that:

$$|u_1 - u_2|_V \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$$

and

$$|L_{i,j}u|_{W_{i,j}} \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$$

for

$$d_{max} = \max(\max_{i \in I} |f_i^1 - f_i^2|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} |\tilde{f}_i^1 - \tilde{f}_i^2|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2|_{W_{i,j}^c})$$

as in the theorem.

For this we note, that because $u_1 = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{f_i^1\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^1\})$, $u_2 = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^2\}, \{f_i^2\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^2\})$, we have that:

$$u_1 - u_2 \in \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \bigcap_{j \in J_i} V_{i,j} \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i \in \tilde{I}} \tilde{V}_i \right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i \in I : \left(\sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j}^1 *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u_1 \right) - \left(\sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j}^2 *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u_2 \right) &= f_i^1 - f_i^2 \\ \Leftrightarrow \forall i \in I : \left(\sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j}^1 *_{i,j} L_{i,j} (u_1 - u_2) \right) + \left(\sum_{j \in J_i} (a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2) *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u_2 \right) &= f_i^1 - f_i^2 \\ \Leftrightarrow \forall i \in I : \sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j}^1 *_{i,j} L_{i,j} (u_1 - u_2) &= h_i \end{aligned}$$

and of course:

$$\forall i \in \tilde{I} : \tilde{L}_i(u_1 - u_2) = \tilde{h}_i$$

for

$$h_i := f_i^1 - f_i^2 - \left(\sum_{j \in J_i} (a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2) *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u_2 \right)$$

and $\tilde{h}_i := \tilde{f}_i^1 - \tilde{f}_i^2$ so that, by the definition of $Sol(\{a_{i,j}\}, \{f_i\}, \{\tilde{f}_i\})$, we have that, for $d := u_1 - u_2$:

$$d = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{h_i\}, \{\tilde{h}_i\})$$

so that we obviously also get for every $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}$:

$$\lambda d \in \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \bigcap_{j \in J_i} V_{i,j} \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i \in \tilde{I}} \tilde{V}_i \right)$$

and

$$\forall i \in I : \sum_{j \in J_i} a_{i,j}^1 *_{i,j} L_{i,j} \lambda d = \lambda h_i$$

and of course:

$$\forall i \in \tilde{I} : \tilde{L}_i \lambda d = \lambda \tilde{h}_i$$

so in shorter notation:

$$\lambda d = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{\lambda h_i\}, \{\lambda \tilde{h}_i\})$$

Now if $d_{max} = 0$, the parameter collections $\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{f_i^1\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^1\}$ and $\{a_{i,j}^2\}, \{f_i^2\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^2\}$ are simply identical, and so one has, as the Sol -notation already supposes, and our uniqueness argument has shown, $Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{f_i^1\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^1\}) = u_1 = u_2 = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^2\}, \{f_i^2\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^2\})$, so that in this case $|u_1 - u_2|_V \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$ and $|L_{i,j}u|_{W_i} \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$ hold trivially for any $C \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.

So now, in order to prove the claimed Lipschitz continuity property, we just have to find a constant $C(B_{data})$ dependent on B_{data} but otherwise independent of the data and the solutions, that is of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$, and of the u_1 and u_2 , such that:

$$|u_1 - u_2|_V \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$$

and

$$|L_{i,j}u|_{W_i} \leq C(B_{data})d_{max}$$

whenever $d_{max} \neq 0$ and hence obviously also $d_{max} > 0$.

So now we restrict ourselves to the remaining relevant case $d_{max} > 0$, and again consider the formula:

$$\lambda d = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^1\}, \{\lambda h_i\}, \{\lambda \tilde{f}_i^1\})$$

and simply choose $\lambda := \frac{1}{d_{max}} > 0$, obtaining via the assumed bounds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} d \right|_V \leq b_V(B_{d^0})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow |d|_V \leq d_{max} b_V(B_{d^0})$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i \in I : \forall j \in J_i : |L_{i,j} \frac{1}{d_{max}} d|_{W_i} &\leq b_{i,j}(B_{d^0}) \\ \Leftrightarrow \forall i \in I : \forall j \in J_i : |L_{i,j} d|_{W_i} &\leq d_{max} b_{i,j}(B_{d^0}) \end{aligned}$$

for any $B_{d^0} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ with:

$$B_{d^0} \geq \max\left(\max_{i \in I} \left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} h_i \right|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} \left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} \tilde{h}_i \right|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}|_{W_{i,j}^c} \right) =: B_{d^0, min}$$

but as we will see now, $B_{d^0, min}$ is bounded by some $B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})$ dependent on B_{data} but otherwise independent of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and the solutions u_1 and u_2 so we can simply choose $C(B_{data}) := \max(b_V(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})), \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} b_{i,j}(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})))$, so that our bounds:

$$|d|_V \leq d_{max} b_V(B_{d^0})$$

and

$$\forall i \in I : \forall j \in J_i : |L_{i,j} d|_{W_i} \leq d_{max} b_{i,j}(B_{d^0})$$

for $B_{d^0} := B_{d^0, max}(B_{data}) \geq B_{d^0, min}$, as required for these bounds to hold, obviously imply:

$$|u_1 - u_2|_V \leq C(B_{data}) d_{max}$$

and

$$|L_{i,j} u|_{W_i} \leq C(B_{data}) d_{max}$$

as required, with

$$C(B_{data}) = \max\left(b_V(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})), \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} b_{i,j}(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data}))\right)$$

obviously dependent on B_{data} but otherwise independent of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and the solutions u_1 and u_2 concluding the proof of the claimed Lipschitz property.

So now we conclude the proof of the claimed Lipschitz property by showing that indeed there is some $B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})$ dependent on B_{data} but otherwise independent of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and the solutions u_1 and u_2 such that $B_{d^0, min} \leq B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})$.

Since $B_{d^0, min} = \max(\max_{i \in I} \left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} h_i \right|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in \tilde{I}} \left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} \tilde{h}_i \right|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}|_{W_i})$, it suffices to bound:

- (1) $\left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} h_i \right|_{W_i}$ for all $i \in I$
- (2) $\left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} \tilde{h}_i \right|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ for all $i \in \tilde{I}$
- (3) $|a_{i,j}^1|_{W_{i,j}^c}$ for all (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$

individually by some bounds dependent on B_{data} but otherwise independent of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and the solutions u_1 and u_2 , because since I, \tilde{I} and all J_i are finite, the maximum of those finitely many bounds then obviously yields a bound $B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})$ on $B_{d^0, min}$ that depends on B_{data} but is otherwise independent of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and the solutions u_1 and u_2 .

Firstly, we note that $|a_{i,j}^1|_{W_{i,j}^c}$ is directly bounded by B_{data} since $B_{data} \geq \max(\dots, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^1|_{W_{i,j}^c})$, so we immediately get such a bound for case 3.

We bound $\left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} h_i \right|_{W_i}$ for arbitrary i via:

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} h_i \right|_{W_i} &= \frac{1}{d_{max}} |f_1 - f_2 - \left(\sum_{j \in J_i} (a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2) *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u_2 \right)|_{W_i} \\
&\leq \frac{|f_1 - f_2|_{W_1}}{d_{max}} + \sum_{j \in J_i} \frac{|(a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2) *_{i,j} L_{i,j} u_2|_{W_i}}{d_{max}} \\
&\leq \frac{|f_1 - f_2|_{W_1}}{d_{max}} + \sum_{j \in J_i} c_{i,j} \frac{|a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2|_{W_{i,j}^c}}{d_{max}} |L_{i,j} u_2|_{W_{i,j}} \\
&= \frac{|f_i^1 - f_i^2|_{W_1}}{\max(\dots, |f_i^1 - f_i^2|_{W_1})} + \sum_{j \in J_i} c_{i,j} \frac{|a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2|_{W_{i,j}^c}}{\max(\dots, |a_{i,j}^1 - a_{i,j}^2|_{W_{i,j}^c})} |L_{i,j} u_2|_{W_{i,j}} \\
&\leq 1 + \sum_{j \in J_i} c_{i,j} |L_{i,j} u_2|_{W_{i,j}} \leq 1 + \sum_{j \in J_i} c_{i,j} b_{i,j}(B_{data})
\end{aligned}$$

with the last inequality due to the bounds assumed in the theorem.

So the $|\frac{1}{d_{max}} h_i|_{W_i}$, can be bounded by a bound depending only on B_{data} but otherwise independent of the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and u_1, u_2 , concluding case 1.

We bound $|\frac{1}{d_{max}} \tilde{h}_i|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ for arbitrary i via:

$$\left| \frac{1}{d_{max}} \tilde{h}_i \right|_{\tilde{W}_i} = \frac{|f_i^1 - \tilde{f}_i^2|_{\tilde{W}_i}}{\max(\dots, |f_i^1 - \tilde{f}_i^2|_{\tilde{W}_i})} \leq 1$$

so the $|\frac{1}{d_{max}} \tilde{h}_i|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ can be bounded by a bound depending on B_{data} but not on the $a_{i,j}^1, f_i^1, \tilde{f}_i^1, a_{i,j}^2, f_i^2, \tilde{f}_i^2$ and u_1, u_2 , concluding case 2.

Thus the necessary bounds for the $|\frac{1}{d_{max}} h_i|_{W_i}$, the $|\frac{1}{d_{max}} \tilde{h}_i|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ and the $|a_{i,j}^1|_{W_{i,j}^c}$ in terms of B_{data} exist, so that as explained earlier, we can bound $B_{d^0, min}$ by some bound $B_{d^0, max}$ on the maximum of these bounds, and then set:

$$C(B_{data}) = \max \left(b_V(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})), \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} b_{i,j}(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})) \right)$$

so that the claimed Lipschitz property holds.

Additionally, we see that if $b_V(B_{data}), b_{i,j}(B_{data})$ are all polynomial with degree d all the finitely many bounds for the $|d_{max} h_i|_{W_i}$, the $|d_{max} \tilde{h}_i|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ and the $|a_{i,j}^1|_{W_{i,j}^c}$ derived can obviously be, as functions of B_{data} , bounded by a polynomial of degree $\max(d, 1)$, so that $B_{d^0, max}$ which simply has to bound their maximum, can also be bounded by a polynomial of degree $\max(d, 1)$, so that

$$C(B_{data}) = \max \left(b_V(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})), \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} b_{i,j}(B_{d^0, max}(B_{data})) \right)$$

can then be bounded by a polynomial of degree d^2 , as claimed, as is easily seen by considering the cases $d = 0$ and $d > 0$ separately, so the additional claim on the growth of $C(B_{data})$ if $b_V(B_{data}), b_{i,j}(B_{data})$ are all polynomial with degree d also holds.

Finally we use the now proven Lipschitz property to prove the continuity property claimed, concluding the proof.

In order to prove the continuity property claimed, we consider, as in the statement of the theorem:

- for each $i \in I$ an arbitrary convergent sequence $(f_i^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in W_i , with convergence understood in the $|\cdot|_{W_i}$ -norm,

- for each (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$ an arbitrary convergent sequence $(a_{i,j}^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $W_{i,j}^c$, with convergence understood in the $|\ast|_{W_{i,j}^c}$ -norm,
- for each $i \in I$ an arbitrary convergent sequence $(\tilde{f}_i^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in \tilde{W}_i , with convergence understood in the $|\ast|_{\tilde{W}_i}$ -norm,

and define the u_n and u_{lim} as well as all the $a_{i,j}^{lim}$, f_i^{lim} and \tilde{f}_i^{lim} as in the theorem.

Now because convergent sequences with respect to a norm are bounded in that norm, we have that:

$$B_{seq} := \max \left(\max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |a_{i,j}^n|_{W_{i,j}^c}, \max_{i \in I} \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |f_i^n|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in I} \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |\tilde{f}_i^n|_{\tilde{W}_i} \right)$$

is finite, and obviously fulfills

$$B_{seq} \geq \max \left(\max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^n|_{W_{i,j}^c}, \max_{i \in I} |f_i^n|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in I} |\tilde{f}_i^n|_{\tilde{W}_i} \right)$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, so that the following bound B (which actually is just B_{seq} , but this way, the argument is simpler):

$$B := \max \left(B_{seq}, \max \left(\max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^{lim}|_{W_{i,j}^c}, \max_{i \in I} |f_i^{lim}|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in I} |\tilde{f}_i^{lim}|_{\tilde{W}_i} \right) \right)$$

still fulfills $B \geq \max \left(\max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^n|_{W_{i,j}^c}, \max_{i \in I} |f_i^n|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in I} |\tilde{f}_i^n|_{\tilde{W}_i} \right)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ but also fulfills:

$$B \geq \max \left(\max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^{lim}|_{W_{i,j}^c}, \max_{i \in I} |f_i^{lim}|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in I} |\tilde{f}_i^{lim}|_{\tilde{W}_i} \right)$$

But then we can apply the Lipschitz property to $u_n = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^n\}, \{f_i^n\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^n\})$ and $u_{lim} = Sol(\{a_{i,j}^{lim}\}, \{f_i^{lim}\}, \{\tilde{f}_i^{lim}\})$, with bound $B_{data} := B$ independent of n , obtaining

$$|u_n - u_{lim}|_V \leq C(B)d_{max}^n$$

and

$$|L_{i,j}u_n - L_{i,j}u_{lim}|_{W_{i,j}} \leq C(B)d_{max}^n$$

for

$$d_{max}^n := \max \left(\max_{i \in I} |f_i^n - f_i^{lim}|_{W_i}, \max_{i \in I} |\tilde{f}_i^n - \tilde{f}_i^{lim}|_{\tilde{W}_i}, \max_{i \in I} \max_{j \in J_i} |a_{i,j}^n - a_{i,j}^{lim}|_{W_{i,j}^c} \right)$$

but since the f_i^n converge to the f_i^{lim} in $|\ast|_{W_i}$, the \tilde{f}_i^n converge to the \tilde{f}_i^{lim} in $|\ast|_{\tilde{W}_i}$, and the $a_{i,j}^n$ converge to the $a_{i,j}^{lim}$ in $|\ast|_{W_{i,j}^c}$, we obviously have that $d_{max}^n \rightarrow 0$, as maximum of finitely many sequences that converge to 0, so that via the sandwichlemma also $|u_1 - u_2|_V \rightarrow 0$ and $|L_{i,j}u|_{W_{i,j}} \rightarrow 0$, which immediately implies that we have that:

$$u_n \rightarrow u_{lim}$$

with respect to the $|\ast|_V$ -norm, and for all (i, j) such that $i \in I$ and $j \in J_i$:

$$L_{i,j}u_n \rightarrow L_{i,j}u_{lim}$$

with respect to the respective $|\ast|_{W_{i,j}}$ -norm, so that also the claimed continuity property holds, concluding the proof.

11.2. A more thorough sketch of the mirroring argument. While the core idea of boundary flattening and mirroring arguments (which are standard, see for example [Lieberman1]) to, for sufficiently small cylinders intersecting with the boundary, flatten the boundary with a diffeomorphism, perturbing the system and the solutions slightly, and to then mirror the solution along the flattened boundary, “gluing” the solution and the mirrored version together along the flattened boundary, locally obtaining a solution for the glued system where a part of the boundary becomes interior, is very natural and intuitive, doing them rigorously is often quite involved. Accordingly, we present a more detailed sketch of how the C^0 -bound from the proof sketch of theorem 21 can be obtained, with the help of a mirroring argument, as very briefly outlined in theorem 21, and then passing to the limit.

Concretely we consider, on an open and bounded cylinder $Z = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, with $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ having at least C^3 -boundary, the parabolic PDE in divergence form $u_t = \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla u) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla u + f$, with A having continuous partial derivatives in all spacial (non-time) directions, and the components of A as well as the components of the $\partial_{x_i} A$, and the components of b and the function f each in some parabolic Hölder space $H_a(Z)$ for some $a \in (0, 1)$, or more simply, each in some Hölder space $C^{0+a}(Z)$ (which implies they are in some $H_a(Z)$ too). We assume the PDE to be uniformly parabolic, that is we assume $0 < \lambda \leq v^T A(x, t)v \leq \Lambda$ for all $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $|v| = 1$ and all $(x, t) \in Z$. We consider the PDE in a strong sense, looking for solutions in the parabolic space $C^{2,1}(\overline{Z})$. We consider it with a given initial datum $u_{T_1} \in C^{2+a}(\Omega)$ with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, that is with $\forall x \in \Omega : \overline{u}(x, T_1) = u_{T_1}(x)$ for that initial datum, and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, that is $\overline{\nabla u} \cdot n = 0$ on $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, where $\overline{u}, \overline{\nabla u}$ are the continuous extensions of the respective functions to \overline{Z} , and n is the normal vector field on $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$. Schauder theory quickly yields in this case that there is a strong solution u to the PDE, which we, using local bounds and a standard mirroring argument, show to be bounded in absolute value with a bound that depends only on λ, Λ , a bound the initial datum, a on the b_i , and an L^p bound on f for sufficiently large p .

11.2.1. *The setting.* Firstly, we describe the setting, that is essentially the system, we work with.

We fix an arbitrary dimension $n \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 2}$, for the rest of this sketch. That is, we consider n a fixed constant, so that dependencies on n are dependencies on a constant and thus no proper dependencies (so especially, all our constructed bounds only work for the respective arbitrary n chosen, and accordingly “change with n ”).

We consider, in a strong sense, the parabolic PDE:

$$u_t = \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla u) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla u + f$$

on a cylinder $Z = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$, for some open and bounded $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ with C^{2+a} boundary for some $a \in (0, 1)$, where ∇ and the divergence are as usual to be understood as gradient and divergence with respect to the space coordinates only.

We consider strong solutions in $C^{2,1}(\overline{Z})$, that is strong solutions in the space of continuous functions u on Z which are continuously extendable to \overline{Z} and for which, denoting, as we shall do from now on, the first n coordinates as x_1, \dots, x_n , and the $n + 1$ -th coordinate as t , all the partial derivatives:

$$\partial_{x_i} \partial_{x_j} u, \partial_{x_i} u, i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \partial_t u$$

exist in the classical sense, and are continuous and continuously extendable to \overline{Z} .

We consider strong solutions for some arbitrary given initial data in a higher order Hölder space, $u_{T_1} \in C^{2+a}(\Omega)$, for some $a \in (0, 1)$, with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions, that is with:

$$\forall x \in \partial\Omega : \overline{\nabla u_{T_1}}(x) \cdot n = 0$$

where $\overline{\nabla u_{T_1}}$ is the continuous extension of the gradient to $\overline{\Omega}$ (in general, we will use overlines over functions to denote unique continuous extensions to some closure or some subset of a closure, from now on), which exists because u_{T_1} is in C^{2+a} so ∇u_{T_1} is uniformly continuous and thus continuously extendable to the closure, as the boundary is C^{2+a} (and hence also has no self-intersections).

We require solutions to have that initial data in the sense that:

$$\forall x \in \Omega : \bar{u}(x, T_1) = u_{T_1}(x)$$

where as usual \bar{u} is the continuous extension of u to \bar{Z} .

We further require the solutions to have homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions in the sense that:

$$\forall (x, t) \in \partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2) : \overline{\nabla u}(x, t) \cdot n(x) = 0$$

where as usual $\overline{\nabla u}$ is the continuous extension of the classical gradient, and n is the normal vector field on $\partial\Omega$.

Additionally we assume that A has continuous partial derivatives in all spacial (non-time) directions, and the components of A as well as the components of the $\partial_{x_i} A$, and the components of b and the function f , are in (possibly distinct) Hölder spaces $C^{0+a}(Z)$ for some values $a \in (0, 1)$.

Notice that these assumptions are really qualitative, as neither any norm on a continuous partial derivative of A nor any Hölder norm on any of these functions will appear in the bound that will be derived. The main reason for these assumptions is to allow for the existence of strong solutions, which simplifies the argument. While this means these assumptions are key for the techniques of this proof to work, the fact that these higher regularity requirements don't enter the estimates quantitatively means that they can basically be dropped by approximating systems by smoothed systems, and passing to the limit, so they are key for this way of proving things, but could be shown in a second step, by taking the main result from this work and passing to the limit, to be mathematically superfluous.

Now that we have made the required structural assumptions and qualitative regularity assumptions, we continue to introduce the quantitative bounds that the estimate from the main result will actually depend on:

Concretely, we assume that we have uniform ellipticity (which is crucial for solution existence as well as for bounding solutions), that is that there are $\lambda, \Lambda \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ so that:

$$0 < \lambda \leq v^T A(x, t) v \leq \Lambda$$

for all $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $|v| = 1$ and all $(x, t) \in Z$ and we assume that we have some upper bound $B \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ so that:

$$\sup_{x \in \Omega} |u_{T_1}(x)| \leq B, |f|_{L^p} \leq B, \sup_{(x, t) \in Z} |b| \leq B$$

where p is some fixed positive value (it depends on n but n is fixed) that will be fixed in the next subsection.

11.2.2. Some foundational results. Of course we need some foundational results in order to derive the main result of this sketch.

Firstly, in such a setting, there always is a unique strong solution u as considered in the previous section in some higher order parabolic Hölder space which is a subspace of $C^{2,1}(\bar{Z})$, since in the higher order parabolic Hölder space, all the relevant partial derivatives are uniformly continuous. This solution is found essentially by noting that:

$$u_t = \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla u) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla u + f$$

is equivalent to a non divergence form PDE:

$$u_t = A(x, t) : H_u + \tilde{b}(x, t) \cdot \nabla u + f$$

with $:$ the Frobenius scalar product, H_u the Hessian, and \tilde{b} being b plus some vector valued function whose components are linear combinations of spatial partial derivatives of components of A .

Now because the components of b and the partial derivatives of the components of A were assumed to be Hölder, \tilde{b} is component wise Hölder too, and A was assumed to be component wise Hölder and f was assumed to be Hölder, we then have A, \tilde{b}, f höldercontinuous with possibly different Hölderexponents, and $u_{T_1} \in C^{2+a}(\Omega)$ with yet another $a \in (0, 1)$, so we can simply pick $\tilde{a} \in (0, 1)$ small enough so that $\tilde{a} < a$ and A, \tilde{b}, f are höldercontinuous with respect to the exponent \tilde{a} , and then apply standard existence results from Schauder theory, for example theorem 5.3 from chapter IV § 5 Basic results on solvability from [LSU], to get existence of a solution, and we can then get the uniqueness of such a solution from the so-called energy method.

Secondly, we can fix that p we still have to fix so that $p \geq 2$ (so B bounds an L^p norm of f at least as strong as the L^2 -norm) so that then by a standard application of the energy method the L^2 -norm of the solution can be bounded using a bound that only depends on λ, Λ, B, Z , via the energy method. One simply bounds the L^2 -norm of u_{T_1} and that of f by B and then applies the energy method.

Thirdly, it is well-known that mirroring-results like this hold:

Theorem 40. (*regularity of mirrored functions*)

Let H be a half ball, that is one half of a ball $B_r(x)$ divided equally by a hyperplane, and let ϕ_m be the uniquely determined “mirroring” map that maps H to the other half of $B_r(x)$, then, denoting continuous extensions with an overline as usual, for every $u \in C^2(\overline{H})$ with $\overline{\nabla} u \cdot n = 0$ on the intersection of $B_r(x)$ and the hyperplane, where n is the surface normal again, we have that the map u_m defined piecewise via:

- $u_m(x) := u(x)$ on H , $u_m(x) := \overline{u}(x)$ on $C := B_r(x) \setminus (H \cup \phi_m(H)) \subseteq \partial H$
- $u_m(x) := u(\phi_m(x))$ on $\phi_m(H)$

is in $C^2(\overline{B_r(x)})$.

This obviously implies that, letting $C^{2,0}(\overline{Z})$ be defined like $C^{2,1}(\overline{Z})$ without the requirement that u_t exists:

Corollary 41. (*regularity of mirrored functions I*)

Let Z_h be a finitely long cylinder with a half-disk crosssection, and let ϕ_m be the uniquely determined “mirroring” map that maps Z_h to the other half of the full cylinder Z , then for every $u \in C^{2,0}(\overline{Z})$ with $\overline{\nabla} u \cdot n = 0$ on the intersection of Z and the hyperplane, where n is the surface normal again, we have that the map u_m defined piecewise via:

- $u_m(x) := u(x)$ on Z_h , $u_m(x) := \overline{u}(x)$ on $C := Z \setminus (Z_h \cup \phi_m(Z_h)) \subseteq \partial Z_h$
- $u_m(x) := u(\phi_m(x))$ on $\phi_m(Z_h)$

is in $C^{2,0}(\overline{Z})$.

Using a simple argument, essentially representing $u(x, t)$ as $\int_{T_1}^t \overline{u}_t(x, t') dt'$, and using that $t \mapsto u_t(x, t)$ is uniformly continuous in x , since u_t is uniformly continuous, for u with u_t continuously extendable to \overline{Z} , one quickly realizes that also, defining $C^{0,1}(\overline{Z})$ as the space of continuously extendable (to \overline{Z} of course) functions with continuously extendable time derivatives (again continuously extendable to \overline{Z} of course), we get:

Proposition 42. (*regularity of mirrored functions II*)

Let Z_h be a finitely long cylinder with a half-disk crosssection, and let ϕ_m be the uniquely determined “mirroring” map that maps Z_h to the other half of the full cylinder Z , then for every $u \in C^{0,1}(\overline{Z})$ with $\overline{\nabla} u \cdot n = 0$ on the intersection of Z and the hyperplane, where n is the surface normal again, we have that the map u_m defined piecewise via:

- $u_m(x) := u(x)$ on Z_h , $u_m(x) := \overline{u}(x)$ on $C := Z \setminus (Z_h \cup \phi_m(Z_h)) \subseteq \partial Z_h$
- $u_m(x) := u(\phi_m(x))$ on $\phi_m(Z_h)$

is in $C^{0,1}(\bar{Z})$.

Now because for these particular spaces we have $C^{2,1}(\bar{Z}) = C^{2,0}(\bar{Z}) \cap C^{0,1}(\bar{Z})$, these two results can be combined yielding:

Theorem 43. (*regularity of mirrored functions III*)

Let Z_h be a finitely long cylinder with a half-disk crosssection, and let ϕ_m be the uniquely determined “mirroring” map that maps Z_h to the other half of the full cylinder Z , then for every $u \in C^{2,1}(\bar{Z})$ with $\bar{\nabla}u \cdot n = 0$ on the intersection of D and the hyperplane, where n is the surface normal again, we have that the map u_m defined piecewise via:

- $u_m(x) := u(x)$ on Z_h , $u_m(x) := \bar{u}(x)$ on $C := Z \setminus (Z_h \cup \phi_m(Z_h)) \subseteq \partial Z_h$
- $u_m(x) := u(\phi_m(x))$ on $\phi_m(Z_h)$

is in $C^{2,1}(\bar{Z})$.

Now of course, we can only attempt to mirror like this, if we can locally flatten the boundary with a suitable diffeomorphism, but the following variant local flattening proposition makes that possible:

Proposition 44. (*a boundary flattening result*)

Given some set $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ with C^k boundary, $k \geq 2$, and some $x \in \partial\Omega$ and $\epsilon > 0$, there always is a C^k -diffeomorphism $\psi_x : \Omega \rightarrow \tilde{\Omega} \in C^k(\bar{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ with $\psi_x^{-1} \in C^k(\bar{\tilde{\Omega}}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ so that:

- $|\psi_x|_{C^k}, |\psi_x^{-1}|_{C^k} < \infty, |\psi_x - Id|_{C^1} < \epsilon$
- The continuous extension $\overline{D\psi_x}$ (which just like $\overline{D\psi_x^{-1}}$ exists because $|\psi_x|_{C^2}, |\psi_x^{-1}|_{C^k} < \infty$) maps the normal vector field of Ω to the normal vector field of $\tilde{\Omega}$, so composing with the diffeo (or even its inverse) especially preserves homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions.
- $B_\delta(x) \cap \tilde{\Omega}$ is a half ball for some $\delta > 0$ (so ψ_x locally flattens the boundary around x).

Now for ease of notation, we from now on write $\overline{C^k}$ -diffeomorphism for diffeomorphisms $\phi : Z \rightarrow \tilde{Z} \in C^k(\bar{Z}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ or $\psi : \Omega \rightarrow \tilde{\Omega} \in C^k(\bar{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ with $\phi^{-1} \in C^k(\bar{\tilde{Z}}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ or respectively $\psi^{-1} \in C^k(\bar{\tilde{\Omega}}; \mathbb{R}^n)$, obviously, for such diffeos, Jacobi matrices and inverses of Jacobi matrices and determinants of Jacobi matrices and inverses of determinants of Jacobi matrices and so on are all well-defined and in $C^{k-1}(\bar{Z}; \mathbb{R}^n)$.

For any $\overline{C^3}$ -diffeo $\phi : (\Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow (\tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))); (x, t) \mapsto (\psi(x), t)$ with ψ some C^3 -diffeo $\psi : \Omega \rightarrow \tilde{\Omega}$, we have via the chain rule, that for $u \in C^{2,1}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ also $u \circ \phi^{-1} \in C^{2,1}(\tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$ with:

$$\nabla u(x, t) = \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t) = \nabla(u(*, t) \circ \psi^{-1} \circ \psi)(x) = (D\psi)(\psi^{-1}(y))^T \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t)$$

for $(y, t) := \phi(x, t)$.

Similarly, it is well known that:

$$\operatorname{div}(A(x)\nabla(u \circ \psi)(x)) = \det(D\psi^{-1}(y))^{-1} \operatorname{div}(A^\psi(y)(\nabla u)(y))$$

for $A^\psi(y) := \det(D\psi^{-1}(y))(D\psi^{-1}(y))^T A(\psi^{-1}(y))(D\psi^{-1}(y))$, $y := \psi(x)$.

This of course implies that for any $\overline{C^3}$ -diffeo $\phi : (\Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow (\tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))); (x, t) \mapsto (\psi(x), t)$ with ψ some C^3 -diffeo $\psi : \Omega \rightarrow \tilde{\Omega}$, we have that for $u \in C^{2,1}(\Omega \times (T_1, T_2))$ also $u \circ \phi^{-1} \in C^{2,1}(\tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2))$ due to the chain rule with, due to the aforementioned formula:

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t)) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t) \\ &= \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla(u(*, t) \circ \psi^{-1} \circ \psi)(x)) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla(u(*, t) \circ \psi^{-1} \circ \psi)(x) \\ &= \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1} \operatorname{div}(\tilde{A}^\psi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla(u(*, t) \circ \psi^{-1} \circ \psi)(x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1} \operatorname{div}(\tilde{A}^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + (b(x, t)^T (D\psi)(\psi^{-1}(y))^T)^T \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t) \\
&= \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1} \operatorname{div}(\tilde{A}^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + ((D\psi)(\psi^{-1}(y))b(x, t)) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t) \\
&= \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1} \operatorname{div}(\tilde{A}^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + \tilde{b}^\phi(x, t) \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t)
\end{aligned}$$

for:

$$\tilde{A}^\phi(y, t) := \det(D\psi^{-1}(y))(D\psi^{-1}(y))^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)(D\psi^{-1}(y))$$

$$\tilde{b}^\phi(x, t) := ((D\psi)(\psi^{-1}(y))b(x, t))$$

and $y := \psi(x)$.

Now that is a weighted divergence form, however, since $\det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1}$ is in $C^{k-1}(\bar{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^n)$ because ϕ is a C^3 -diffeo, not only a C^3 -diffeo, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\operatorname{div}(\det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1}(y)\tilde{A}^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) \\
&= \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1} \operatorname{div}(\tilde{A}^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + (((\nabla \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1})(y))^T \tilde{A}^\phi(y)) \cdot (\nabla u)(y, t)
\end{aligned}$$

so we can bring this into proper divergence form via:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1} \operatorname{div}(\tilde{A}^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + \tilde{b}^\phi(x, t) \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t) \\
&= \operatorname{div}(\det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1} \tilde{A}^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + \tilde{b}^\phi(x, t) \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t) - (((\nabla \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1})(y))^T \tilde{A}^\phi(y)) \cdot (\nabla u)(y, t) \\
&= \operatorname{div}(A^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + b^\phi(x, t) \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t)
\end{aligned}$$

for:

$$A^\phi(y, t) := (D\psi^{-1}(y))^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)(D\psi^{-1}(y))$$

$$b^\phi(y, t) := ((D\psi)(\psi^{-1}(y))b(x, t)) - (\nabla \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1})(y)^T \tilde{A}^\phi(y)$$

Now this formula actually has several important properties,

Furthermore, we then have, for the special case of a mirroring diffeomorphism $\phi_m : (\Omega \times (T_1, T_2) \rightarrow (\tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2)); (x, t) \mapsto (\psi_m(x), t)$, with simpler calculations by noting that for such a diffeo $\phi_m = \phi_m^{-1}$, $\psi_m = \psi_m^{-1}$ (mirrorings are self-inverse), and that it can be written as $(x, t) \mapsto (Q(x - b) + b, t)$ for some symmetric self inverse orthonormal mirroring matrix Q , so that it also has $\det(D\psi_m) = \det(D\psi_m^{-1}) = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\operatorname{div}(A(x, t) \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t)) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t) \\
&= \operatorname{div}(A(x, t) \nabla(u(*, t) \circ \psi^{-1} \circ \psi)(x)) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla(u(*, t) \circ \psi^{-1} \circ \psi)(x) \\
&= \operatorname{div}(A^{\phi_m}(y, t)(\nabla u)(y)) + (b(x, t)^T Q^T) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t) \\
&= \operatorname{div}(A^{\phi_m}(y, t)(\nabla u)(y)) + (Qb(x, t)) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t)
\end{aligned}$$

$$= \operatorname{div}(A^{\phi^m}(y, t)(\nabla u)(y)) + b^{\phi^m}(y, t) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t)$$

for $A^{\phi^m}(y, t) := Q^T A(\phi^m(y, t))Q$, $b^{\phi^m}(y, t) := Qb(\phi^m(y, t))$ and $y := \psi(x)$.

Furthermore, we will need the following finite subcover result:

Theorem 45. *(a subcover result)*

Let U be any open and bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^n , and let \mathcal{F} be a family of open sets of the form $U \cap B_{\epsilon_x}(x)$ with some positive ϵ_x , containing at least one such open set per $x \in \bar{U}$. Then \mathcal{F} contains a finite subcover covering U .

Proof.

Wlog we assume that \mathcal{F} contains exactly one set $U \cap B_{\epsilon_x}(x)$ per $x \in \bar{U}$, choosing one such set for each x . We now consider the family $\tilde{\mathcal{F}} := \{B_{\epsilon_x}(x) : x \in \bar{U}\}$. Now $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$ is clearly an open cover that covers \bar{U} , and \bar{U} is a closed bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^n , and hence compact, so there is a finite subcover, and hence a finite selection $X \subseteq \bar{U}$ of centerpoints so that $\bigcup_{x \in X} B_{\epsilon_x}(x) \supseteq \bar{U}$ and hence $\bigcup_{x \in X} U \cap B_{\epsilon_x}(x) \supseteq U$, so that $\{U \cap B_{\epsilon_x}(x) : x \in X\}$ is a finite subcover of \mathcal{F} covering U .

Finally, we of course need the local bounding result that we build upon, concretely, the following is essentially a special case of theorem 8.1 from section 8 Local estimates of $\max|u|$ of chapter III Linear equations with discontinuous coefficients from [LSU]:

Theorem 46. *(the local bound)*

Assume we have a strong solution from $C^{2,1}(\bar{Z})$ on some cylinder Z to a parabolic PDE of the form:

$$u_t = \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla u) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla u + f$$

with measurable (importantly not necessarily continuous) A, b, f and some $\lambda, \Lambda \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ so that:

$$0 < \lambda \leq v^T A(x, t)v \leq \Lambda$$

for all $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $|v| = 1$ and all $(x, t) \in Z$ and some $B \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ so that:

$$\sup_{x \in \Omega} |u_{T_1}(x)| \leq B, |f|_{L^p} \leq B, \sup_{(x, t) \in Z} |b| \leq B$$

where p is some constant (so we assume that we use this theorem with one fixed p , and therefore do not consider dependence on p) that is sufficiently large depending on n .

Then on any open set $U \subset Z$ that is compactly contained in Z , $|u|$ is pointwise bounded on U by some bound depending only on λ, Λ, B a bound on the L^2 -norm of u and the distance between \bar{U} and ∂Z .

Furthermore, if Γ' is a subset of ∂Z , and \bar{u} is bounded on Γ' by some bound $B_{\Gamma'}$, and $U \subseteq Z$ is an open subset of Z so that the distance between \bar{U} and $\partial Z \setminus \Gamma'$ is greater than 0, then $|u|$ is pointwise bounded on U by some bound depending only on λ, Λ, B a bound on the L^2 -norm of u , $B_{\Gamma'}$ and the distance between \bar{U} and ∂Z .

Of course we now fix our constant p that we introduced at the beginning of the previous section dependent on the constant n and large enough so that it is both ≥ 2 and large enough for the local bound theorem to work, concluding the setup and presentation of the required foundational results.

11.2.3. *The main result and its proof.* Now that we have the setup and the necessary preliminaries, we continue to show the main result. Concretely, we show that:

Theorem 47. (*Main result*)

In the setting from the first section, there is some p that only depends on n so that $\max_{(x,t) \in Z} |u(x,t)|$ can be bounded by some bound B_{max} that only depends on Z, λ, Λ, B .

From which we can then get, because the spatial partial derivatives of A as well as the Hölder norms of A, b, f don't influence the bound at all, via standard approximation by "regularized" systems and then passing to the limit, that:

Proposition 48. (*Main result variant*)

Even if we are not fully in the setting from the first section, with all requirements met, except that A now does not necessarily have spatial partial derivatives with any properties, there is some p that only depends on n so that $\max_{(x,t) \in Z} |u(x,t)|$ can be bounded by some bound B_{max} that only depends on Z, λ, Λ, B .

Now that the main result and the variant are stated, we prove the main result:

Proof of Theorem 8.

We prove this in three steps.

First we will see that we can in a sense extend the system and the solution, by a fixed length, say 1, without changing λ, Λ at all and changing B in a controlled way. This then obviously allows us to bound the original solution on the original cylinder by simply bounding the extended solution on the original cylinder, which now is a subcylinder of the new whole cylinder which is 1 longer.

Therefore, we can reduce the task of bounding $\max_{(x,t) \in Z} |u(x,t)|$ in all such settings to bounding $\max_{(x,t) \in \Omega \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)} |u(x,t)|$ in all such settings where the cylinder $Z = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ is longer than 1. Second, we will then see how developing such bounds on u for certain infinite collections of subsets of Z allows us, via a "finite cover extraction" argument, to bound u on all of $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ given a cylinder $Z = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ longer than 1.

Third, we will actually bound u on these subsets using a local bound from [LSU][SOURCE], completing the proof.

We start with the first step, and quickly notice that writing $Z = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ we can define an "extended" PDE:

$$u_t = \operatorname{div}(A(x,t)\nabla u) + b(x,t) \cdot \nabla u + f$$

on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2 + 1)$ via:

$$A^{ext}(x,t) := \bar{A}(x,\tilde{t}), b_i^{ext}(x,t) := \bar{b}_i(x,\tilde{t}), f^{ext}(x,t) := \bar{f}(x,\tilde{t})$$

for $\tilde{t} := \delta_{t \leq T_2} t + \delta_{t > T_2} (T_2 - t / (T_2 - T_1))$.

We do not change the initial datum or the boundary conditions for the extended system (and of course extend the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions to the new mantle).

Now clearly, the old λ, Λ values work for this new system as well, since it is extended with the "values" of the old system. Also, we get a new bound B on the extended system by multiplying the previous B by a factor of $(1 + 1/(T_2 - T_1))^{\frac{1}{p}}$ which only depends on Z , because obviously $\sup_{(x,t) \in Z} |b| = \sup_{(x,t) \in Z^{ext}} |b^{ext}|$, and also:

$$\begin{aligned} |f^{ext}|_{L^p} &= \left(\int_Z |f(x,t)|^p + \int_{Z^{ext} \setminus Z} |f^{ext}(x,t)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &= \left(\int_Z |f(x,t)|^p + (1/(T_2 - T_1)) \int_Z |f(x,t)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = (1 + 1/(T_2 - T_1))^{\frac{1}{p}} |f^{ext}|_{L^p} \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, by the definition of Hölder continuity, it is also clear, essentially because $\tilde{t}(t)$ is Lipschitz, that the new $a_{i,j}^{ext}, b_i^{ext} f^{ext}$ are Hölder continuous with the same exponents as well, and it is also intuitively clear (and could be proven with a uniform continuity argument), that since $a_{i,j}^{ext}$ have Hölder partial derivatives $\partial_{x_k} a_{i,j}^{ext}$ in space directions, we have the $\partial_{x_k} (a_{i,j}^{ext}(x, \tilde{t}(t))) = (\partial_{x_k} a_{i,j}^{ext})(x, \tilde{t}(t))$ are Hölder continuous as well, and so we have a system of the originally considered form again, and by Schauder theory, we get a unique solution $u^{ext} \in C^{2,1}(\Omega)$ to that extended system, as the system can be translated into a system in non divergence form as explained in the previous section which can be solved uniquely with standard Schauder theory results.

Now it makes sense that we denote that solution u^{ext} , because restricted to Z , it has to solve the original system, and since we know that solutions to such systems are unique, we then know that $u^{ext}|_Z = u$.

But then we have just effectively extended the system and the solution by 1 in the time direction, with the old λ, Λ values still working for the extended system, and $(1 + 1/(T_2 - T_1))^{\frac{1}{p}} B$, which depends only on B and the cylinder (p is a constant that depends on the constant n), working as new B and the other system properties still holding as well, only the cylinder is extended by 1.

But then obviously, if we can bound u^{ext} on the subcylinder $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2 + 1 - 1)$ of the extended cylinder by some bound that only depends on the extended cylinder, λ, Λ and the new B value, we have bounded u on its whole domain with some bound that only depends on the extended cylinder, $\lambda, \Lambda, (1 + 1/(T_2 - T_1))^{\frac{1}{p}} B$, or equivalently, since the extended cylinder is determined by the cylinder (by increasing the length by 1), we have bounded u on its whole domain with some bound that depends only on $Z, \lambda, \Lambda, (1 + 1/(T_2 - T_1))^{\frac{1}{p}} B$ or equivalently only on Z, λ, Λ, B since T_1, T_2 can be computed from Z .

So without loss of generality, it suffices if for all such systems as described in the setting section with a cylinder $Z = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ of length greater than 1, we can bound the solution on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$.

So the first step is now completed, and we can, without loss of generality, assume we have a cylinder $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ with length greater than 1, and only bound the solution on the subcylinder $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ in terms of Z, λ, Λ, B .

So now we continue with the second step, and note the following:

Assume somehow, for each $x \in \bar{\Omega}$, we could choose some ϵ_x and B_x only dependent on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$, so that on $Z_x := (B_{\epsilon_x}(x) \cap \Omega) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$, $|u|$ is bounded by B_x .

Then we could, for each combination Z, λ, Λ, B , choose some finite subset $A \subseteq \bar{\Omega}$, so that $\bigcup_{x \in A} B_{\epsilon_x}(x) \cap \Omega = \Omega$, and hence $\bigcup_{x \in A} Z_x = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$, by the subcover result from the previous section.

This would then obviously allow us, to obtain, for each combination Z, λ, Λ, B , a bound M on $|u|$ on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$, by simply setting $M := \max_{x \in A} B_x$ which depends only on $A, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$ and hence can also be viewed as depending only on Z, λ, Λ, B , since A was chosen in function of the combination Z, λ, Λ, B , concluding the proof.

So without loss of generality, it suffices if for each $x \in \bar{\Omega}$, we can find some ϵ_x and B_x only dependent on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$, so that on $Z_x := (B_{\epsilon_x}(x) \cap \Omega) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$, $|u|$ is bounded by B_x .

Now for $x \in \Omega$, this is simple, we simply choose ϵ_x to be say the supremum of $\epsilon > 0$ so that $B_{2\epsilon_x}(x) \subseteq \Omega$, so half the distance from x to the boundary, so that for the corresponding $Z_x = B_{\epsilon_x}(x) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$, the distance from Z_x to the mantle $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ with the Neumann boundary conditions is ϵ_x , only dependent on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$, the distance to the second cap of the whole cylinder, $\Omega \times \{T_2\}$, is 1 (this and the analogous ‘‘buffer’’ for the case $x \in \partial\Omega$ is why we needed that extension argument why bounding u only on $\Omega \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ suffices for the proof), and on the first cap $\Omega \times \{T_1\}$, the only part of the boundary of the whole cylinder Z which doesn't have at least distance $\min(1, \epsilon_x)$ to Z_x , we have that the continuous extension of u is bounded by B , and furthermore, the L^2 norm of u on Z is bounded with a bound depending only on Z, λ, Λ, B , too, as we noted in the previous section.

So we then can apply the local bound theorem to the system and the subset Z_x , yielding a bound B_x on $|u|$ on Z_x that only depends on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$.

This only leaves the case when $x \in \partial\Omega$. In this case, we obviously have zero distance to the mantle $\partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2)$ with the Neumann boundary conditions, which prohibits us from directly applying the local bound, but via a standard flattening and mirroring argument, commonly used for such purposes, we can roughly glue the system and the solutions together with properly “mirrored” copies in a way so that very roughly speaking the “corresponding space coordinate becomes interior to the crosssection”, so we can apply the local bound again, concluding the proof.

So now, we conclude the proof by doing the main part of the third step, given any $x \in \partial\Omega$, we choose some ϵ_x depending only on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$, and then bound u on Z_x by some B_x depending only on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$.

For this we first note that given a $\overline{C^3}$ diffeo $\phi : Z \rightarrow \tilde{Z} = \tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2); (x, t) \mapsto (\psi(x), t)$ so that $\overline{D\psi}$ maps the normal vector field of Ω to that of $\tilde{\Omega}$, the formulas from the previous section for transforming the PDE under diffeomorphisms yield that:

$$\forall (x, t) \in Z : u_t(x, t) = \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t)) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t) + f(x, t)$$

is equivalent to:

$$\forall (y, t) \in \tilde{Z} : u_t(y, t) = \operatorname{div}(A^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + b^\phi(x, t)\nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t) + f^\phi(y, t)$$

for:

$$A^\phi(y, t) := (D\psi^{-1})(y)^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t) (D\psi^{-1})(y)$$

$$b^\phi(y, t) := ((D\psi)(\psi^{-1}(y))b(x, t)) - (\nabla \det(D\psi^{-1})^{-1})(y)^T \tilde{A}^\phi(y)$$

$$f^\phi(y, t) := f(\psi^{-1}(y), t)$$

Now from the formulas we easily see that A^ϕ, b^ϕ and f^ϕ are Hölder since A, b, f are Hölder and our $\overline{C^3}$ diffeo has $|\phi|_{C^3}, |\phi^{-1}|_{C^3} < \infty$, so all the expressions related to the diffeo in our formulas are at least C^1 with finite C^1 norm, and hence, because our cylinder is Lipschitz, they are all Lipschitz so the via additions, multiplications and compositions of these functions with the $a_{i,j}, b_i, f$ composed $a_{i,j}^\phi, b_i^\phi$ and f^ϕ are at least Hölder. We also see similarly that because:

$$\partial_{x_i} A^\phi(x, t) = (\partial_{x_i}(D\psi^{-1})(x)^T) A(\psi^{-1}(x), t) (D\psi^{-1})(x)$$

$$+ (D\psi^{-1})(x)^T (\partial_{x_i} A(\psi^{-1}(x), t)) (D\psi^{-1})(x) + (D\psi^{-1})(x)^T A(\psi^{-1}(x), t) (\partial_{x_i}(D\psi^{-1})(x))$$

and we assumed the $\partial_{x_i} A(\psi^{-1}(x), t)$ to be Hölder, the $\partial_{x_i} A^\phi(x, t)$ are Hölder as well.

So the new system has Hölder coefficients and source term with the spatial partial derivatives of A^ϕ existing and being Hölder too, again.

We can also obviously also “transform” the initial data requirement similarly, requiring:

$$\forall y \in \tilde{\Omega} : \overline{(u \circ \phi)}(y, T_1) = u_{T_1}^\phi(y, t)$$

with $u_{T_1}^\phi := u_{T_1} \circ \psi$, equivalently to:

$$\forall x \in \Omega : u(y, T_1) = u_{T_1}(x, t)$$

with $u_{T_1} \circ \psi$ in some higher order Hölderspace $C^{2+a}(\Omega)$ because u_{T_1} is and ψ has bounded C^3 -norm, and $u_{T_1} \circ \psi$ having homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions because we assumed that $\overline{D\psi}$ maps the normal vector field of Ω to that of $\tilde{\Omega}$ and u_{T_1} has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions.

Finally, also the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions on u are equivalent to homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions on $u \circ \phi$, because we assumed that $\overline{D\psi}$ maps the normal vector field of Ω to that of $\tilde{\Omega}$.

So all in all, for any C^3 diffeo ϕ like that, we can transform our system:

$$\forall(x, t) \in Z : u_t(x, t) = \operatorname{div}(A(x, t)\nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t)) + b(x, t) \cdot \nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1} \circ \phi)(x, t) + f(x, t)$$

$$\forall x \in \Omega : u(y, T_1) = u_{T_1}(x)$$

$$\forall(x, t) \in \partial\Omega \times (T_1, T_2) : \overline{\nabla u}(x, t) \cdot n(x) = 0$$

to an equivalent system:

$$\forall(y, t) \in \tilde{Z} : u_t(y, t) = \operatorname{div}(A^\phi(y)(\nabla u)(y)) + b^\phi(x, t)\nabla(u \circ \phi^{-1})(y, t) + f^\phi(y, t)$$

$$\forall y \in \tilde{\Omega} : u(y, T_1) = u_{T_1}^\phi(y)$$

$$\forall(y, t) \in \partial\tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2) : \overline{\nabla u}(y, t) \cdot \tilde{n}(y) = 0$$

where \tilde{n} is the Normal vector field of $\tilde{\Omega}$, and the coefficient functions and initial datum fulfill all qualitative requirements from our setting, A^ϕ, b^ϕ the spatial partial derivatives of A^ϕ and f^ϕ are Hölder, the initial datum is in that higher order Hölder space and has Neumann boundary conditions, etc.

So we see that “transforming” the system via such a diffeo yields another such system of the type we are considering here regarding the “qualitative” requirements on the system, so now we have a look at the quantitative ones:

Firstly, we notice that via our formulas again, $|a_{i,j}^\phi|, |b_i^\phi|, |f^\phi|_{L^p}$ and $|u_{T_1}^\phi|$ can obviously be globally bounded by some bound B^ϕ chosen only dependent on B , the global bound on $|a_{i,j}|, |b_i|, |f|$ and $|u_{T_1}|$, and $|\phi|_{C^3}, |\phi^{-1}|_{C^3}$ (for $|f^\phi|_{L^p}$ this is the case since $\det D\phi, \det D\phi^{-1}$ are bounded, so the change of variables does not change the integral too much), so the new system of course does not have the same “ B ” as the old one, but the new B^ϕ only depends on the old B and $|\phi|_{C^3}$.

Now we could similarly obtain lower and upper bounds λ, Λ , but then we’d have the problem that λ in general would be negative. In order to avoid this, we refer back to our formulas for transforming the PDE, and note that the matrix is transformed via:

$$A^\phi(y, t) := (D\psi^{-1})(y)^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t) (D\psi^{-1})(y)$$

for $y := \psi(x)$, so that for any $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we have:

$$v^T A^\phi(y, t)v := v^T (D\psi^{-1})(y)^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t) (D\psi^{-1})(y)v = w^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)w$$

for $w := (D\psi^{-1})(y)v$.

Now we easily see that this formula is very fortunate, in the sense that if $A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)$ is positive definite, so is $A^\phi(y, t)$, and if we have any bound on $\max(|(D\psi^{-1})(y)|, |(D\psi^{-1})(y)^{-1}|) \leq B_{D\psi, (D\psi)^{-1}}$ (which we automatically have since $\phi \in \overline{C^3}$), we can, with an argument like the argument that follows, get that

$$v^T A^\phi(y, t)v \in [B_{D\psi, (D\psi)^{-1}}^{-2}\lambda, B_{D\psi, (D\psi)^{-1}}^2\Lambda]$$

so due to the fortunate structure of the formula, we wouldn’t get any issues with the new $A^\phi(y, t)$ not being positive definite, regardless of whether $D\psi^{-1}$ is close to the identity matrix or not. Therefore, we could in the next step simply choose the new $\lambda^\phi, \Lambda^\phi > 0$ depending on the old λ, Λ and ϕ , without

having to worry about λ^ϕ becoming nonpositive. This would again mean we would not have to restrict to diffeos that are sufficiently C^1 -close to the identity, and could therefore use a weaker version of the boundary flattening theorem that does not guarantee the existence of local flattening diffeos arbitrarily C^1 -close to the identity.

However, we choose to work with diffeos sufficiently C^1 -close to the identity because this makes the proof better generalizable to cases where the formulas don't magically turn out exactly right, and one actually has to worry about parameters like λ that have to be in some subset of \mathbb{R} like $\mathbb{R}_{>0}$ getting out of that subset, so the system would lose key properties, and require " $D\psi^{-1} \approx Id$ " to avoid that. Proceeding with this approach, if $(D\psi^{-1})(y)$ is say such that $|w| \in [9/10, 10/9]$ for all normalized v , we have that for all normalized v :

$$v^T A^\phi(y, t)v = w^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)w = |w|^2 (w^0)^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)(w^0) \in [(81/100)\lambda, (100/81)\Lambda]$$

for $w^0 := \frac{1}{|w|}w$, since for w^0 , we have by our ellipticity assumption that:

$$(w^0)^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)(w^0) \in [\lambda, \Lambda]$$

This obviously yields that if $\max(|(D\psi^{-1})(y)|, |(D\psi^{-1})(y)^{-1}|) \leq 10/9$, where the matrix norms are spectral norms, we get that for all normalized v :

$$v^T A^\phi(y, t)v = w^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)w = |w|^2 (w^0)^T A(\psi^{-1}(y), t)(w^0) \in [(81/100)\lambda, (100/81)\Lambda]$$

But then we can obviously choose a constant $\epsilon_{max, \phi}$ only dependent on the constant n so that if $\phi = Id + \xi$ with $|\xi|_{C^1} \leq \epsilon_{max, \phi}$ we get that $\sup_{y \in \tilde{\Omega}} \max(|(D\psi^{-1})(y)|, |(D\psi^{-1})(y)^{-1}|)$ becomes close enough to 1, the value for $\psi = Id$, so that we have $\max(|(D\psi^{-1})(y)|, |(D\psi^{-1})(y)^{-1}|) \leq 10/9$ and:

$$\forall v \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ with } |v| = 1 : v^T A^\phi(y, t)v \in [(81/100)\lambda, (100/81)\Lambda] \subseteq [\frac{1}{2}\lambda, 2\Lambda]$$

so that overall, if additionally $\phi = Id + \xi$ with $|\xi|_{C^1} \leq \epsilon_{max, \phi}$ for that $\epsilon_{max, \phi}$, dependent only on λ, Λ , we actually get that $u^\phi := u \circ \phi^{-1}$ fulfills a system just like our initial system on \tilde{Z} , with all the required properties, just with a new cylinder \tilde{Z} of course, the new Lambda values $\lambda^\phi := \frac{1}{2}\lambda, \Lambda^\phi := 2\Lambda$, and a new B value B^ϕ that only depends on B and $|\phi|_{C^3}, |\phi^{-1}|_{C^3}$.

Now the boundary flattening result allows us to, for each $x \in \partial\Omega$ and combination Z, λ, Λ, B , choose a diffeo ϕ_x that flattens the boundary around x and fulfills all the requirements on ϕ we needed, including $\phi = Id + \xi$ with $|\xi|_{C^1} \leq \epsilon_{max, \phi}$ for that constant $\epsilon_{max, \phi}$ dependent only on n .

Thus, we fix such a diffeo ϕ_x for each combination $Z = \Omega^Z \times (T_1^Z, T_2^Z), \lambda, \Lambda, B$ and each $x \in \partial\Omega_Z$, and now consider the diffeo ϕ_x we fixed for the $Z = \Omega \times (T_1, T_2), \lambda, \Lambda, B$ of the system we are currently considering and the $x \in \partial\Omega$ we are currently considering.

Now we note a particularly useful fact, writing $\phi_x = (Z \rightarrow \tilde{Z} = \tilde{\Omega} \times (T_1, T_2); (x, t) \mapsto (\psi(x), t))$ as usual, that because $\Omega, \psi(\Omega)$ are Lipschitz, and $|\psi|_{C^3}, |\psi^{-1}|_{C^3} < \infty$ because $|\phi_x|_{C^3}, |\phi_x^{-1}|_{C^3} < \infty$, we get that ψ and hence also its continuous extension are bilipschitz, so for any $\epsilon > 0$, we can choose a $\delta > 0$ only dependent on ϵ, x, ψ so that $\psi^{-1}(B_\epsilon(\psi(x)) \cap \tilde{\Omega}) \supseteq B_\delta(x) \cap \Omega$, because else, we would have to have a sequence of points in $\tilde{\Omega}$ yet outside of $B_\epsilon(\psi(x)) \cap \tilde{\Omega}$, so each of them is at least ϵ away from $\psi(x)$, which ψ^{-1} maps to a sequence of points converging to x , which is impossible for a bilipschitz map.

This means that if, setting $y := \psi(x)$, we manage to bound $|u^{\phi_x}| = |u \circ \phi_x|$ with some bound only dependent on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$ on some cylinder $\tilde{Z}_y = (B_\epsilon(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ for some ϵ only dependent on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$, this bound would of course also bound $|u|$ on $\phi_x^{-1}(\tilde{Z}_y) \supseteq (B_\delta(x) \cap \Omega) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1) =: Z_x$ for that δ only dependent on ϵ, x, ψ .

Therefore we would then have a bound on u only dependent on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$ on a cylinder $Z_x = (B_\delta(x) \cap \Omega) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ whose "radius" δ only depends on ϵ, x, ψ with this ϵ only dependent on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$, but since all the quantities $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}, \phi_x, \psi, x$ directly or indirectly

depend only on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$, we can then also express that bound and δ in function of only $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$, which then would be a local bound on a cylinder $Z_x = (B_\delta(x) \cap \Omega) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ around x with δ and the bound only dependent on $x, Z, \lambda, \Lambda, B$, as required, so we could simply choose $\epsilon_x := \delta, B :=$ that bound, concluding the proof.

So we now conclude the proof by showing that we can indeed bound $|u^{\phi_x}| = |u \circ \phi_x|$ with some bound only dependent on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$ on some cylinder $\tilde{Z}_y = (B_\epsilon(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ for some ϵ only dependent on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$:

For this, we leverage that because we flattened the boundary, we have a flat boundary around y . Specifically, this means for ϵ small enough, $B_\epsilon(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}$ is a half ball, we let ϵ be one fourth of the supremum of epsilon values so that $B_\epsilon(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}$ is a half ball, so certainly, $B_\epsilon(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}$ is a half ball, and set $\tilde{Z}_y := (B_\epsilon(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$, with the ϵ obviously depending only on y and the geometry of Z^{ϕ_x} , so only depending on quantities in the list $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$, as required.

Now for bounding u^{ϕ_x} on \tilde{Z}_y , we consider the larger and somewhat longer half cylinder $\tilde{Z}_y^{ext} := (B_{2\epsilon}(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}) \times (T_1, T_2)$, which still intersects only with the flat part of the mantle ‘‘around y ’’, and therefore still has a half ball crosssection, and contains \tilde{Z}_y .

We quickly note that by the energy method, we can bound the L^2 norm of u^{ϕ_x} on all of Z^{ϕ_x} so especially on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} by some bound B_{L^2} , just like we can bound that of u , in terms of $Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$.

Now letting ψ_m be the affine linear mirroring diffeo on $B_{2\epsilon}(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}$ that maps $B_{2\epsilon}(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}$ to the other half of $B_{2\epsilon}(y)$, which we’ll accordingly write as $\psi_m(B_{2\epsilon}(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega})$, and ϕ_m be the corresponding map on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} that maps it to the other half of the cylinder $B_{2\epsilon}(y) \times (T_1, T_2)$, just like in the mirroring theorems from the previous section, we can define a function $u_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}$ on all of $B_{2\epsilon}(y) \times (T_1, T_2)$ via essentially taking $u^{\phi_x}|_{\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}}$ and a mirrored $u^{\phi_x}|_{\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}}$ on the other half of the cylinder $Z_{loc,m}^{\phi_x} := B_{2\epsilon}(y) \times (T_1, T_2)$ and gluing them together, formally defining it, like in the mirroring theorems, via:

- $u_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}(x, t) := u^{\phi_x}(x, t)$ on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} , $u_m(x, t) := \bar{u}(x, t)$ on $C := Z_{loc,m}^{\phi_x} \setminus (\tilde{Z}_y^{ext} \cup \phi_m(\tilde{Z}_y^{ext})) \subseteq \partial \tilde{Z}_y^{ext}$
- $u_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}(x, t) := u^{\phi_x}(\phi_m(x, t))$ on $\phi_m(\tilde{Z}_y^{ext})$

Now since u^{ϕ_x} is a solution to a system just like our initial system it is in $C^{2,1}(\overline{Z^{\phi_x}})$, which means $u^{\phi_x}|_{\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}}$ is in $C^{2,1}(\overline{\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}})$ so we can, because $n \cdot \nabla(u^{\phi_x}|_{\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}}) = 0$ on C , where n is the normal of the surface C , because u^{ϕ_x} has homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions on $\partial \tilde{\Omega} \supseteq C$ (this is where the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions enter), apply the mirroring theorem III to get that $u_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}$ is in $C^{2,1}(\overline{Z_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}})$.

Also, the L^2 -norm of $u_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}$ is obviously exactly twice that of u^{ϕ_x} on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} , which as mentioned already we can bound by some B_{L^2} depending only on $Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$, so we also have that the L^2 -norm of $u_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}$ is bounded by some bound depending only on $Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$.

Moreover, more importantly, we can easily see that $u_{loc,m}^{\phi_x}$ solves a PDE defined via the functions:

- $A^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := A^{\phi_x}(x, t)$, $b^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := b^{\phi_x}(x, t)$, $f^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := f^{\phi_x}(x, t)$ on the half \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} , $A^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := \overline{A^{\phi_x}}(x, t)$, $b^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := \overline{b^{\phi_x}}(x, t)$, $f^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := \overline{f^{\phi_x}}(x, t)$ on $C = Z_{loc,m}^{\phi_x} \setminus (\tilde{Z}_y^{ext} \cup \phi_m(\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}))$
- $A^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := Q(A^{\phi_x}(\phi_m(x, t)))Q^T$ as matrices, $(b^{\phi_x,m}(x, t)) := Q(b^{\phi_x}(\phi_m(x, t)))$ as column vectors, with Q the mirroring matrix from the mirroring map ψ_m , and $f^{\phi_x,m}(x, t) := \overline{f^{\phi_x}}(\phi_m(x, t))$, on the mirrored half $\phi_m(\tilde{Z}_y^{ext})$.

That it solves the same PDE as u^{ϕ_x} on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} because it is identical to u^{ϕ_x} there is obvious, and because continuous functions that are zero on a dense subset are zero, and the relevant partial derivatives of u^{ϕ_x} are continuous on $\tilde{Z}_y^{ext} \cup C$ and the functions $a_{i,j}^{\phi_x,m}, b_i^{\phi_x,m}, f^{\phi_x,m}$ are continuous on $\tilde{Z}_y^{ext} \cup C$ as well, and the PDE is fulfilled on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} dense in $\tilde{Z}_y^{ext} \cup C$, we have that our PDE is also fulfilled on $\tilde{Z}_y^{ext} \cup C$

too, so especially on C too, that the definition for the coefficients on the mirrored half $\phi_m(\tilde{Z}_y^{ext})$ works follows from the formula for transforming our PDE under mirroring maps from the previous section.

Now this might seem somewhat strange, especially because our definition is “assymmetric” on C , we continuously continue the coefficients on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} to C , not the ones on the other half, which generally do not yield the same continuous continuation for A and b due to the transformations with Q , causing a discontinuity of the functions $A^{\phi_x, m}, b^{\phi_x, m}$ on C , where we then choose the values that one obtains from continuing the coefficient functions restricted to \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} to C . Indeed, we could have defined the PDE on C differently, continuously continuing the $a_{i,j}$ and b_i from the other half to C , and would still get that $u_{loc, m}^{\phi_x}$ solves them, and could even carry out the rest of the proof with that definition, which “restores” the symmetry. Now this might still seem strange, because that means that $u_{loc, m}^{\phi_x}$ essentially fulfills two different PDEs on C , until one realizes that the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions of u^{ϕ_x} restrict the behaviour of $u_{loc, m}^{\phi_x}$ on C , inducing this behaviour, and creating the counterintuitive situation that we get a strong solution to a discontinuous PDE with obviously measurable (since “piecewise continuous” on measurable subsets) coefficients.

Now the nice thing about this PDE is that because Q is orthogonal for all normalized $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$:

$$v^T(A^{\phi_x, m}(x, t))v = v^T Q(A^{\phi_x}(\phi_m(x, t)))Q^T v = v^T(A^{\phi_x}(\phi_m(x, t)))v \in [\lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}]$$

so the uniform ellipticity constants $\lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}$ work for the new PDE on the mirrored half, and they obviously work on \tilde{Z}_y^{ext} , and because we defined uniform ellipticity via \leq, \geq , via a continuous extension argument, the same uniform ellipticity constants $\lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}$ also work on C , so they work on all of $Z_{loc, m}^{\phi_x}$:

$$\forall(x, t) \in Z_{loc, m}^{\phi_x} : v^T(A^{\phi_x, m}(x, t))v \in [\lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}]$$

Furthermore, because Q is orthogonal, and B^{ϕ_x} bounds $|A^{\phi_x}|$ and $|b^{\phi_x}|$ pointwise, $2n^2 B^{\phi_x}$ also bounds all $|a_{i,j}^{\phi_x, m}|$ and all $|b_i^{\phi_x, m}|$ pointwise, by using that all elements of an orthogonal matrix have absolute value at most 1, and n is a constant [TODO make], and furthermore obviously also $|f^{\phi_x, m}|_{L^p} = 2|f^{\phi_x, m}|_{\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}}|_{L^p} = 2|f^{\phi_x}|_{\tilde{Z}_y^{ext}}|_{L^p} \leq 2|f^{\phi_x}|_{L^p} \leq 2n^2 B^{\phi_x}$, so we can, all in all, bound $|A^{\phi_x, m}|$ and $|b^{\phi_x, m}|$ pointwise and $|f^{\phi_x, m}|_{L^p}$ by $B^{\phi_x, m} := 2B^{\phi_x}$ (since we use the euclidean norm for vectors and the spectral norm for matrices, else we would get constants like $2n^2$ here) only dependent on the variable B^{ϕ_x} (since n is fixed).

Moreover, we can obviously also bound $u_{loc, m}^{\phi_x}$ on the front lid $B_{2\epsilon}(y) \times \{T_1\}$ by B^{ϕ_x} , since B^{ϕ_x} bounds $u_{T_1}^{\phi_x}$.

Furthermore, we quickly realize that $B_\epsilon(y) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ has distance at least $\min(1, \epsilon)$ from every point on the boundary that is not on the front lid where we have the bound B^{ϕ_x} .

So overall, we have $u^{\phi_x, m} \in C^{2,1}(\overline{Z_{loc, m}^{\phi_x}})$ and quantitatively L^2 bounds on $u^{\phi_x, m}$ and a minimum distance of $B_\epsilon(y) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ from all boundary points where we do not have B^{ϕ_x} as bound on u , both only dependent on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$, and $\lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}$ as uniform ellipticity constants for the PDE, $2n^2 B^{\phi_x}$ as bound on all $|a_{i,j}^{\phi_x, m}|$ and all $|b_i^{\phi_x, m}|$ pointwise and $|f^{\phi_x, m}|_{L^p}$.

This is what we needed the mirroring construction for, $B_\epsilon(y) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ even contains points that are on the boundary of Z^{ϕ_x} , but it is completely “interior” (except for the initial lid on which we have bounds via the initial data) in $Z_{loc, m}^{\phi_x}$ thanks to that “mirroring construction”.

Therefore, since A, b are, even though in general discontinuous, obviously measurable, and the other requirements are fulfilled as well, we can bound $|u^{\phi_x, m}|$ pointwise on $B_\epsilon(y) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ via the local bound theorem we have seen in the previous section, by some quantity only depending on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$. But since on the subset $Z_x = (B_\epsilon(y) \cap \tilde{\Omega}) \times (T_1, T_2 - 1)$ we have that $u^{\phi_x, m}(x, t) = u^{\phi_x}(x, t)$, this means we have bounded $|u^{\phi_x}|$ on Z_x by some quantity only depending on $y, Z^{\phi_x}, \lambda^{\phi_x}, \Lambda^{\phi_x}, B^{\phi_x}$, concluding the proof.

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